

Future Prospects on Railway Freight Transportation A Particular View of the Weight Issue on Intermodal Trains

vorgelegt von
Dipl.-Ing.
Armando Carrillo Zanuy
aus Barcelona, Spanien

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Promotionsausschuss:

Vorsitzender: Prof. Dr. phil. D. Manzey

Berichter: Prof. Dr.-Ing. J. Siegmann

Berichter: Prof. Dr.-Ing. M. Hecht

Berichter: Prof. B. Nelldal

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Armando Carrillo Zanuy 2012
ACarrillozanuy@railways.tu-berlin.de
Fachgebiet Schienenfahrwege und Bahnbetrieb
Technische Universität Berlin
Germany

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FOREWORD

This text is the outcome of 6 years of investigations and analysis on freight railways and intermodal transportation.

A very important part of this work feeds from the scientific context of the EU project VEL-Wagon for which the author himself is the project manager and core researcher. The texts in the present document that come from the VEL-Wagon project have all been written exclusively by the author.

All words, graphs, drawings and tables that are not explicitly attributed to another source have been produced by the author.

My especial thanks to my supervisor Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Siegmann for his guidance and support.

I hope you enjoy reading it.

To be read with the music of Chet Baker

ABSTRACT

The present work analyses the issue of the deadweight in intermodal trains and states that this weight is excessive for the current and future intermodal transportation. In this way, the common intermodal units are considered light elements that would be more efficiently transported in lighter railway wagons. An analysis of the actual railway and intermodal market with important statistics' inputs and trend forecasts is provided in order to demonstrate this affirmation.

The work also addresses the issue of the length of the intermodal wagons and how this has an influence on their loading properties (loading schemes). It concludes that longer surfaces without interruptions lead to better loading arrangements that cover a broader spectrum of loading cases.

The combination of these two concepts, longer and lighter wagons, crystalize in the form of VEL-Wagon, which is an EU project that has been deeply analysed in this thesis. The VEL-Wagon concept strives for longer loading surfaces with same or fewer wheels than regular wagons, resulting in lighter wagons for the intermodal transport. A non-articulated 80 ft container wagon is analysed.

Because of having fewer wheels per loading meter there is an increasing axle load that may have an influence on the infrastructure. Therefore an axle load extension would be interesting for light goods because it would permit to use more efficient wagons like VEL-Wagon.

Another important point analysed in this thesis is the loading gauge. The long wagons, with long distance between pivots, have an unfavourable condition when running the sharp curves by which the centre of the wagon is "overthrown" towards the curve centre, implying a loss of gauge. This could create some problems on small gauges, say G1 and GA but could be solved for GB and it will be no problem for GC.

Finally several business case are presented and discussed, being the most remarkable a 5-time-week shuttle train that could save up to 500.000 € a year if using the VEL-Wagon instead of regular intermodal wagons.

The thesis leads to the confirmation of the working hypothesis, which states that:

To achieve a better utilization of the track capacity, the trains and the wagons the loading length of these must be longer and at the same time with less or same number of axles.

Paving the way for enunciating the challenge:

The extension of the maximum axle load in European tracks, from 22,5 to 25 t and beyond, is a desired action that will benefit the light rail transports and will help to increase the competitiveness of freight railways against the road, leading to a more sustainable transport system.

1. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH

Since years scientists study the infrastructures, vehicles and operations that enable transportation. As more and more technologically-developed transportation systems are achieved, science in transportation broadens itself and scientific challenges become more and more specialized.

In the last times there is an important need set by governments to achieve sustainability and well-being when doing transportation, this encounters serious difficulties with the concept of growth and enlargement imposed by globalised economies and puts transportation science in a very challenging situation.

Among the many science contexts in transportation the railway is considered a quite rigid subject for development. This is mainly due to the constraints derived from its scarce, expensive and long-lasting physical path for transport, the railway infrastructure. It is also due to the inherent inelasticity of railway operations, which depend on the important volumes handled, the important economic pressures and the dependency on subsidies. And finally, when it comes to movable resources such as locomotives, wagons, coaches and railcars, railways have to deal with important initial investments and expensive maintenances, which interfere with having a dynamic strategy to face nowadays market, societal and environmental trends.

Hence, science and technological development for railways are mainly driven by economic interests on one side and political wills on the other.

Freight railways represent the foremost confrontation of these two issues. As an example, it can be observed the important discussion occurring on the subject of railway noise. In this matter, citizens, related industry and politicians are trying to find a solution that satisfies all parties altogether, enabling more railway traffic but quieter. Is this possible? Technological development and science are deploying an important effort to provide products and arguments that enrich and raise this discussion, yielding new technological and knowledge paradigms that may enable a compromised solution in the future.

In railway transportation the utilisation of the available train capacity plays a crucial role for the business productivity and infrastructure capacity use. To that aim trains are configured with wagons that meet users' specific demands leading to efficient transportations and benefits for railway stakeholders. Because of that, there is a great diversity of wagon types which are intended for specific transports, for example: containers, coal, iron ore, automobiles, oil, wood trunks, grain, steel coils, palletized cargo, chemicals, etc.; in that way, efficient railway exploitation utilises the right wagons for the right commodity.

But commodities of today are quite different from commodities of 100 years ago. There has been an important increase on transportation of finalized and semi-finalized goods which have changed the transportation habits and which demand more and more quality on transportation, a quality that is very well served by the road transportation.

Naïvely it can be said that more air in form of package is transported, and it is transported on longer distances. In this context, the road transportation has been able to offer quality solutions to these transports, which have been based on very low prices due to cheap fuel costs. But, how long will this be possible, or cheap? How will the sustainable transport mode of the future deal with such transportation habit? Are railways, as they look like today, this transport mode?

1.1. GOAL & HYPOTHESIS

The goal of this dissertation is to produce enough arguments to sustain that:

The freight trains have to become lighter* in order to lower the logistics costs and compete better against the road transport.

* Lighter per transported m³, which make the trains more oriented to volumetric goods rather than to heavy goods.

An important derived working hypothesis is that:

To achieve a better utilization of the track capacity, the trains and the wagons, the loading length of these must be longer and at the same time with less or same number of axles.

The increase of volume in trains encounters difficulties in Europe due to the small loading gauges. The “vertical” growth of the trains in Europe, like the double-stack trains in the U.S., requires very important investments in infrastructure which can only be achieved at very long term and at very high costs. Conversely, an extension of the longitudinal dimension is apparently easily achievable. This, together with the reduction of tare of vehicles, for example by reducing the amount of wheels, paves the way for achieving better utilisation of the train capacity at lower energy cost.

Hence a coherent path of this work aims at:

- Investigate the development of the market for intermodal rail freight and the future need for further development of different wagon types according to market needs.
- Evaluate the effects of longer and more efficient wagons for intermodal transport according to cost, capacity and external effects.

FIGURE 1: EXTENSION OF WAGON LENGTH.

1.2. METHODOLOGY

The scientific methodology has consisted in the following steps:

1.2.1. OBSERVE

– *System delimitation and scope of study*

The first step of the PhD dissertation is to delimitate the field of study. To that aim a brief description of the intermodal context is necessary, enabling the framing of the subject as well as the identification of main external dependencies. The introduction chapter is conceived as such task.

– *Literature review*

The literature review is fundamental to describe the state-of-the-art on the field and to reach the point for commencement of research. Fundamentals on intermodal transportation are extracted from academic, institutional and European-wide corporative sources. The important academic contribution of the Chair of Track and Railway Operations at the Technische Universität Berlin (Prof. Siegmann) is a fundamental basis for the description of combined transport. Furthermore important focus is given to the institutional sources as UN (United Nations) and ECMT (European Conference of Ministers of Transport) as well as to key railway-related and intermodal associations as UIC (International Union of Railways), UIRR (International Union of Combined Road-Rail Transport Companies) and EIA (European Intermodal Association).

– *Statistic data review, congruent data generation*

The statistic data was analysed in order to understand the evolution and trends on transportation and economics related to transportation. Both public and private statistic sources were consulted and compared. Among the consulted sources it is remarkable the Eurostat Database, Destatis Genesis Online (Germany), France Stats (France), Ministerio de Fomento (Spain), Port Authority of Rotterdam, Hamburg, Antwerp, UIC stats, SNCF, DB, RENFE, SBB, Containerisation International, Association of American Railroads, IANA (Intermodal Association of North America) and the U.S. Bureau of Transportation Statistics, among many other statistical sources.

The statistic data comprehension and trend identification has been very important to complete missing cells and correct singularities (mistakes). With this it has been possible to interpret possible future scenarios for analysis of the transportation behaviours.

1.2.2. ANALYSIS

– *Demand*

The demand of freight railways is described in the chapter of the same name. The gathered evidence and observations on demand trends, mainly from statistic processing, enables to enunciate theoretical trends on goods segmentation and increase of light transports. It furthermore adds a view on crisis impact on transportation demand.

– *Supply*

The supply analysis describes the operational aspects of the freight railways. It deals with the technical limitations for further transport capacity. The theorisation goes in the path for some parameters extension such as the maximal train length, maximal train weight and axle load extension. This section also describes and analyses the wagon fleet and its adequateness for freight transports.

– *Intermodal market*

The intermodal market is described and analysed in this chapter. A theoretical distribution curve that portrays the current container weights and proportion in European ports is employed to formulate traffic models that are employed for the simulations.

1.2.3. EXPERIMENT, PARTICULAR CASE (VEL-WAGON)

– *Longer wagons*

The state of the art on longer wagons focuses the attention towards countries outside of the EU. Then so, the U.S., Australia and Russia count with good examples on long wagons. In Europe there are as well interesting cases which are described and analysed.

– *VEL-Wagon and simulation of traffics*

VEL-Wagon is a concept of an 80 ft long wagon with 2 bogies which increases the loading factors of the trains that employs them. A simulation of its operational performance is presented in this section. The simulation parameters are based on the theoretical assumptions exposed in the previous stages of this work.

– *Effects on infrastructure and environment*

The long wagons with fewer axles per meter such as VEL-Wagon have an effect on infrastructure, namely increased axle load, reduction of loading gauge, benefit on noise emissions and capacity increase. These effects are exposed with a theoretical approach and a numerical simulation.

1.2.4. INTERPRET AND VALIDATE

– *Business case and future prospects*

A business case is formulated using the actual and typical parameters of train service exploitation. By this it is demonstrated that a longer wagon like VEL-Wagon leads to important benefits in terms of economic efficiency. A systematic analysis of sensitivity of the different assumptions enables further comprehension on variability and effects of the extension of vehicle parameters. This enables the formulation of future concepts for wagons and train operations.

– *Cost calculations*

Due to the enormous variability of train costing models (See Troche, G. “Activity-Based Rail Freight Costing”) it has been decided to utilize fixed parameters identified in the recent literature. By this the focus then has been put on identifying the influence that the variability of loading cases and weights have on the total train costs rather than the train costing models themselves. To that aim an important description of the different casuistic on loading schemes and weights distributions of container has been studied and classified.

– *Validation*

The theoretical models could only be validated with a real experimentation with wagon prototypes and real train services, which are absolutely out of the scope of this intellectual work. However the presented traffic simulations and business cases study yield enough arguments to confirm the initial hypothesis and working theories.

2. INTRODUCTION

The freight railways in Europe used to enjoy better times before the deindustrialization process in the late 1900s, affecting Western Europe gradually, and Eastern Europe very abruptly. This process is shifting the European production structure towards an economic system more dependent on information, services and technological development, imposing important quality requirements for transportation that freight railways are presently not able to meet. During such important development times the European railways have lost an important share of their freight market, which in the case of central and eastern European countries has been especially devastating. About 60% of the total tonne-km transported by railways in Eastern Europe disappeared between 1988 and 1993. [Himola]

FIGURE 2: FREIGHT RAILWAYS' PERFORMANCE IN EUROPE (MRD. TKM). SOURCE: UIC 2009/2012

Indeed, a major part of the decline of European freight railways can be attributed to the changed production structure; however other reasons such as the poor coordination of international cross-border scheduled routes necessary for longer distances of transportation as well as the inflexibility to connect railway freights to other modes brought an important worsening effect too. The large decline suffered by freight railways since the 1980s contrasts very much with the increase of other modes, particularly the road freight, which increased its tone-km output by 180% between the years 1980 and 2000. [Himola]

During the 20th and the early 21st century, road and sea freight underwent a phenomenal expansion, absorbing the major portion of new freight market created and taking market share from the railways. Unfortunately the environmental price paid for this was high, especially regarding the case of road transport. As European governments became aware of the environmental problems arising from such rapid transportation expansion, they were increasingly looking at freight railways that should offer a better energy utilisation and lower external costs, if used efficiently. Then, ideally, rail transport should be more competitive in an environmentally-concerned market of surface transportation.

At the beginning of the 21st century there was clear interest from administrations, lobbies and potential users of rail services in promoting the use of freight railways again. The so-called

“Revitalising the railways” as one of the principal measures proposed in the EC 2001 White Paper is a good example.

In many cases though, public and national-oriented management of freight railway transports did, and still do, hinder the proper evolution of rail freight businesses.

While other modes of freight transport enjoyed a propitious regulative context, freight railways were caught amidst monopolistic interests. The liberalization of the European rail freight market taking place from the year 1993 onwards, as in the UK, Sweden or Germany, is still is not accomplished by many countries at the time being, pretty the contrary, in some cases a re-nationalization, large privatizations, company fusions or acquisitions e.g. DB Holding in Netherlands, Denmark, UK etc. have occurred. This has produced different scenarios for freight railways in which international traffics still have impediments for being efficient. Today, a combination of interoperable networks and liberalized markets has paved the way for newcomers to produce benefits in some corridors and areas, especially in the container segment, e.g. the Rhine-Swiss-Italian corridor, and the hinterlands of Antwerpen, Rotterdam, Bremen and Hamburg. In this way, the EU is still looking for the best regulative framework that enables a satisfactory railway development.

Currently, environmental concerns of the society combined with unstable energy prices and increased demand of crude oil and other commodities has positioned railways in the spotlight of many potential users.

It is commonly accepted that in surface transportation the rail mode is more appropriate for transporting large and heavy consignments over long distances whereas road mode is more appropriate for small and light consignments over short distances. Between these extremes there are many transports’ demands that may choose one mode or the other one.

Typically, road transportation wins the mode choice in 80% of the cases (expressed in tkm).

FIGURE 3: EXAMPLE OF A MODAL SHARE IN SURFACE TRANSPORTATION (>600KM). (OWN ELABORATION)

Indeed, nowadays about 1,5 billion tkm are transported in Europe by lorry at distances further than 150 km, conversely only 0,4 billion tkm (20%) are transported by train (Eurostat 2011), this entails important costs for fossil fuels.

In the nearby future when transportation will be more sustainable it seems quite clear that freight railways will win the mode choice more often.

For this to happen though, it is necessary that freight railways, apart from lowering their prices, significantly improve the quality of transportation. In that sense, quality standards such as reliability, flexibility, availability, cargo security and safety, punctuality, customisation, marketability, traceability, complementary servicing and time for transport among others have to be improved.

Hence, rail freight has the challenge to become excellent and to gain in reputation.

There are many actions to increase quality in rail freight transport, one of them is the optimisation of the current wagon fleet to improve availability, flexibility, marketability, commercial speed, cargo security and cost. This optimisation has to respond to the actual trends of transport demand and has to be in consonance with the required and feasible infrastructure upgrades.

In European rail freight transportation the total amount of freight wagons has been gradually decreasing at an approximate rate of 3% per year until reaching approximately 650.000 units in the year 2010, on the other hand the offered tkm has been stagnating or slightly decreasing to reach around 400 milliard tkm in 2010 (UIC stats and Eurostat 2011).

FIGURE 4: AMOUNT OF WAGONS VS. FREIGHT RAIL PERFORMANCE. (OWN ELABORATION) DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT AND UIC 2011.

This mirrors the actual trend of utilising more efficiently the available wagon fleet, which is achieved by increasing the amount of productive km (loaded km) the wagons make per year.

An important part of this overall wagon efficiency can be attributable to the exhaustive utilisation of intermodal wagons, which have found a good place to perform in the globalised market of containerisation.

Intermodal wagons usually carry lighter cargoes that have high value, typically, the higher the value of the cargo the lighter it is and the more exigent in respect to quality standards, especially concerning security and safety.

Conventional wagons have the optimal physical and technical characteristics to transport some specific kinds of commodities – usually with lower value per ton – and fail in being versatile for other transports. There are exceptions as the H and L wagons that address general (palletised) cargo which have high value too.

The production system in which wagons are utilised has as well an important effect on the productivity. Then so, intermodal and company-dedicated wagons tend to run in point-to-point direct configurations with short turn-over times, while other conventional wagons may make use of the single wagon load system where they can be re-marshalled many times, reducing by this their total yearly mileage. A compromised solution has to be found to increase mileage while being flexible.

Graphically, the wagon type, mileage and % of loaded runs could look as follows:

FIGURE 5: EUROPEAN WAGON PRODUCTIVITY. (OWN ELABORATION) DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT, UIC 2010, [DB WETTBEWERBSBERICHT 2010] AND INTERNAL KNOWLEDGE.

The graph shows that the light wagons do much more loaded kilometres per year than the heavy wagons and that the intermodal wagons, a sub-group of light wagons, are the most efficiently employed overall.

Hence in a nearby future the productivity of wagons has to continue increasing in order to achieve better competition levels against road. This challenge will pave the way for the excellence in freight railways and will enable a more sustainable future of transportation.

3. OVERVIEW OF RAIL FREIGHT TRANSPORTATION DEMAND

Traditionally the best, and sometimes captive, clients of freight railways are those industries related to primary and secondary sectors that demand the regular transportation of large consignments (> 400 tonnes¹) of relatively low-value bulk cargo, as coal, oil, ores, raw materials, basic foods and forestry. Scheduled trainloads may cover satisfactorily this demand from about 20.000 tonnes per year and train relation². Likewise, the processed products of these industries, as chemicals, metal working products, oil derivatives, automobiles and parts thereof, machinery, construction materials, low-processed foods, processed timber, paper, etc. are also an important demand source for freight railways. TL (Trainload), SWL (Single wagonload) and CT (Combined transport) (see section 4.1) are typical participants of such markets too.

As the trend in modern logistics is to reduce the consignment size by increasing the number and frequency of consignments, reducing by this the carrying costs, there is also an important demand of medium-size consignments, 10 to 60 tonnes, that are affine to railway if properly consolidated in SLW or CT trains. These consignments have typically higher value and require higher quality on transportation, especially when it comes to the reliability on collecting and delivery time. Railways-based supply chains, especially SWL, are not always able to achieve this and therefore road transportation prevails. However long-distance consignments, e.g. more than 600 km, may be still attracted by railways if fair quality service exists.

¹ Based on statistical estimations of averaged train payloads in Europe, Eurostat 2010

² Based on the minimum volume demanded from RENFE to carry a unit train service, 2011

3.1. DISTANCE OF TRANSPORTATION

The distance of transportation plays an important role on the mode choice. Globalized economies imply an increase on transportation distances and on this subject railway transportation is able to achieve important economies of scale by longer hauls. However in Europe, given the geographic and economic characteristics, the distances of railway haul are not as long as they could be. Certainly the interoperability problems at national borders and the regulated markets for rail freight are majorly responsible for that. In the forthcoming years the efforts carried out in terms of TSI (Technical Specifications for Interoperability) and the international freight corridors' development should bring about a growth on international traffics and consequently an increase on railway transportation distance.

2008	EU 27			U.S.			CHINA			RUSSIA			INDIA	ARG
	10 ⁹ t-km	10 ⁹ t	km haul	10 ⁹ t-km	10 ⁹ t	km haul	10 ⁹ t-km	10 ⁹ t	km haul	10 ⁹ t-km	10 ⁹ t	km haul	km haul	km haul
Road	1900	18	106	2300	11	209	3830	22	173	180	5,2	35	n.a.	n.a.
Rail	400	1,3	300	3200	2,9	1103	2803	4	763	1800	1,1	1636	660	522
Inland Waterways	140	0,5	280	970	2	485	6116	3	1770	53	0,1	530	n.a.	n.a.
Total 3 modes	2440	20,1	121	6470	15,9	407	12750	29	435	2033	6,4	318	n.a.	n.a.
GDP (\$ 10 ¹⁵)	15			14			8			2			3,5	0,6
km ² (Mio.)	4,3			9,8			9,6			17			3,2	2,7
Population (Mio.)	500			310			1300			142			1100	40

Data source: Eurostat, BTS (U.S.), Federal State Statistics Service (RU), Secretaría de Transporte (ARG), National Bureau of Statistics of China, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (IN)

FIGURE 6: TRANSPORTATION PERFORMANCES AND AVERAGED DISTANCES OF TRANSPORTATION IN THE WORLD (OWN ELABORATION)

There is a relation between the surface of a country –or a company territorial domain- and the averaged distance of railway transportation, this is: the averaged railway distance tends to increase along with the surface extension. Logically there are a number of aspects affecting this distance, namely: country geographic characteristics, amount and distribution of population, railway network characteristics, railway company domains, mixture of traffic passenger-freight, policy on rail freight and a number of other macroeconomic variables.

In spite of the variability, a representation of the averaged railway distance over the country area for every country yields a fairly acceptable linear relation (Figure 7).

FIGURE 7: AVERAGED RAIL HAUL DISTANCES IN THE WORLD, (OWN ELABORATION) DATA SOURCE: UIC STATS AND INVOLVED RAILWAY UNDERTAKINGS, YEAR 2007

Theoretically, the averaged distance for overall railway transportation in the EU, if properly prepared for that, should be situated around 600 km, or even more if employed extensively. However nowadays this distance is only about 300 km which is far below of what a productive railway system would achieve in such free market territorial domain. As said, the interoperability problems between networks may be an explanation for that.

In spite of this, the averaged distance of international railway transportations within the EU economic area is around 400 km³, and there are some remarkable and productive cases as the combined traffic where the averaged transportation distance is 820 km⁴.

A summary of distances of transportation and trend thereof could look as follows:

EU Economic Area	Averaged National	International Intra-EU	Total EU	Total EU (prediction)
Rail haul	200 km	400 km	300 km	600 km
Tendency	⇒	↑	↑	
Road haul	80 km	600 km	100 km	150 km
Tendency	⇝	↓	⇒	

During these years of globalisation and economic buoyancy the demand for international transports within the EU has grown. Nowadays about 60% of the performed t-km inside the EU-Economic Area are produced by international transports, however these only represent 14% of

³ International railway transport Intra EU-27, calculated with data from Eurostat and UIC statistics, it has been rectified the double and triple counting of transported tonnes in cross-border railway transportations

⁴ Source UIRR statistics 2009

the total weight, which indicates that these kind of transports have a long haul distance, c.a. 900km.

An important achievement of this internationalisation has been canalized by the intra-EU maritime transportation, also known as short sea shipping (SSS). In so doing, SSS has grown the last decade at an annual average of 2% in weight, and of 3% in t-km, which indicates that the distance of SSS transportation has increased too. This increase is also observable in the averaged international railway distance.

Conversely, the distances in international road transportation shrank, especially as response to favourable economic conjunctures -increase of transport demand-. And vice versa, demand drops entailed sudden increases of road international transportation. This phenomenon can be observed in European context but it displays even more sharply in the German macroeconomic context, provided that Germany is an economy very dependent of the external trade.⁵

In the next figure it is possible to see how the averaged distance in international road transportation correlates inversely with GDP. (Note that red axis on the right that indicates the distance has an inverted scale)

FIGURE 8: EVOLUTION OF GERMAN GDP AND INTERNATIONAL ROAD TRANSPORT DISTANCE (INVERTED), (OWN ELABORATION) DATA FROM DESTATIS 2010

An explanation to this phenomenon may be that overall larger demands enable better and more efficient capacity utilisation of larger modes like SSS or railways, therefore an amount of long-distance freight, can be attracted by these modes, reducing by this the averaged road haul distance. Conversely, when the overall demand weakens, the capacity utilisation of larger modes may be inefficient and freight has to be shifted to road again.

As efficiency of railway transportation improves, more and more freight can be gained by larger modes and retained by them even by unfavourable conjunctures. This kind of freight may not shift to the road again, which could explain why the variability on road haul distance is

⁵ Whole section affirmations and figures based on observation of data from Eurostat 2011

diminishing over time. Eventually freight demand should shift from road to rail until a certain equilibrium point in which road and rail modes have the same opportunity cost because offering similar quality standards at same prices.

FIGURE 9: VARIATION OF THE DISTANCE OF TRANSPORTATION IN EUROPE (RIGHT AXIS) AND VARIATION OF THE EXTERNAL TRADE, TONES TRANSPORTED BY ROAD AND TONES TRANSPORTED BY RAIL. (OWN ELABORATION) DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

3.2. MODAL SHARE, ROAD COMPETITION & LIGHT TRANSPORTS

The demand of freight transportation in Europe has been affected severely by the recent economic crisis. According to Eurostat 2011 the crisis has cancelled out six years of growth in European road freight (in tkm). In rail transport the decline has been even worse, leading to further undesirable modal share.

FIGURE 10: MODAL SHARE IN EU25. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

In respect to the type of goods transported by road, the most affected segments were:

RANK OF CRISIS-AFFECTED GOODS (NST2007) IN ROAD TRANSPORT	2009 (Mrd.t-km)	2008 (Mrd.t-km)	Drop 09/08	Share (2008)	Drop x share
Basic metals; fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	117	147	20,31%	7,67%	1,56%
Other non-metallic mineral products	157	182	13,36%	9,48%	1,27%
Metal ores and other mining and quarrying products; peat; uranium and thorium	145	168	14,14%	8,78%	1,24%
Grouped goods: a mixture of types of goods which are transported together	104	123	15,00%	6,39%	0,96%
Machinery and equipment n.e.c.; office machinery and computers; electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c.; radio, television and communication equipment and apparatus; medical, precision and optical instruments; watches and clocks	59	73	19,56%	3,83%	0,75%
Unidentifiable goods: goods which for any reason cannot be identified and therefore cannot be assigned to groups 01-16. (Containers)	59	72	17,10%	3,74%	0,64%
Furniture; other manufactured goods n.e.c.	32	44	27,56%	2,31%	0,64%
Wood and products of wood and cork (except furniture); articles of straw and plaiting materials; pulp, paper and paper products; printed matter and recorded media	128	140	8,63%	7,28%	0,63%
Transport equipment	58	70	17,17%	3,65%	0,63%
Chemicals, chemical products, and man-made fibres; rubber and plastic products ; nuclear fuel	131	142	7,19%	7,38%	0,53%
Other goods n.e.c.	38	43	12,38%	2,24%	0,28%
Coke and refined petroleum products	54	59	8,92%	3,08%	0,27%
Food products, beverages and tobacco	298	303	1,73%	15,81%	0,27%
Equipment and material utilized in the transport of goods	35	38	9,63%	2,01%	0,19%
Textiles and textile products; leather and leather products	20	24	14,47%	1,25%	0,18%
Coal and lignite; crude petroleum and natural gas	12	12	6,86%	0,65%	0,04%
Products of agriculture, hunting, and forestry; fish and other fishing products	180	181	0,39%	9,42%	0,04%
Secondary raw materials; municipal wastes and other wastes	64	63	-0,60%	3,30%	-0,02%
Goods moved in the course of household and office removals; baggage and articles accompanying travellers; motor vehicles being moved for repair; other non market goods n.e.c.	7	7	-6,92%	0,36%	-0,03%
Mail, parcels	27	26	-4,46%	1,36%	-0,06%
TOTAL	1725	1917	10,01%	100%	10,01%

FIGURE 11: TYPE OF GOODS TRANSPORTED BY ROAD. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

In respect to the type of goods transported by rail, the most affected segments were:

RANK OF CRISIS-AFFECTED GOODS (NST2007) IN RAIL TRANSPORT	2009 (Mrd.t-km)	2008 (Mrd.t-km)	Drop 09/08	Share (2008)	Drop x share
Unidentifiable goods: goods which for any reason cannot be identified and therefore cannot be assigned to groups 01-16. (Containers)	70,5	85,5	17,50%	18,38%	3,22%
Basic metals; fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	34,6	49,2	29,70%	10,57%	3,14%
Other non metallic mineral products	10,6	21,7	51,36%	4,67%	2,40%
Metal ores and other mining and quarrying products; peat; uranium and thorium	44,4	55,5	20,02%	11,93%	2,39%
Other goods n.e.c.	11,5	17,7	34,75%	3,80%	1,32%
Chemicals, chemical products, and man-made fibers; rubber and plastic products ; nuclear fuel	26,9	32,1	16,14%	6,90%	1,11%
Transport equipment	8,6	13,4	36,02%	2,88%	1,04%
Wood and products of wood and cork (except furniture); articles of straw and plaiting materials; pulp, paper and paper products; printed matter and recorded media	17,4	21,7	19,78%	4,66%	0,92%
Coke and refined petroleum products	52,1	56,3	7,54%	12,11%	0,91%
Coal and lignite; crude petroleum and natural gas	48,5	52,4	7,42%	11,28%	0,84%
Secondary raw materials; municipal wastes and other wastes	8,1	11,3	28,55%	2,43%	0,69%
Products of agriculture, hunting, and forestry; fish and other fishing products	20,4	22,7	10,26%	4,88%	0,50%
Equipment and material utilized in the transport of goods	3,1	4,5	31,23%	0,96%	0,30%
Furniture; other manufactured goods n.e.c.	3,1	4,5	31,16%	0,96%	0,30%
Grouped goods: a mixture of types of goods which are transported together	3,7	4,6	19,34%	0,99%	0,19%
Food products, beverages and tobacco	9,2	10,0	7,94%	2,16%	0,17%
Machinery and equipment n.e.c.; office machinery and computers; electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c.; radio, television and communication equipment and apparatus; medical, precision and optical instruments; watches and clocks	0,9	1,5	35,90%	0,31%	0,11%
TOTAL	373,6	465,0	19,66%	100%	19,66%

FIGURE 12: TYPE OF GOODS TRANSPORTED BY RAIL. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

By looking at the type of goods affected by the crisis it seems quite clear that most of the decrease on transport demand has been due to heavy industries' slowing down processes. As railway transportation has an important share of this segment, the crisis has had an even more devastating effect on this transport mode.

It has to be said though that the crisis has just confirmed a trend happening on product transport segmentation, which is that:

“light” transports grow at a higher pace than “heavy” ones.

To sustain this observation the cargo types and goods types transported by road in the last 10 years are shown.

FIGURE 13: ABOVE) EU 27 CARGOES' SHARE BY ROAD. BELOW) EU27 FREIGHT ROAD EVOLUTION BY TYPE OF GOODS. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2010.

The palletised goods are gaining share over other “loose” cargo configurations e.g. dry bulk, liquid bulk and big bags. And not only this, apparently the palletised cargo is becoming lighter. The averaged net weight per vehicle with palletised cargo is decreasing from 12,2 tonnes in year 2001 to 11,3 in year 2009.

If looking at the type of goods, rather than the cargo types, the miscellaneous articles group, mainly represented by consumer goods, finished and semi-finished goods, containers and general cargo (typically palletized), has dominated and gained share in the last years. In the same situation are other “light” goods as foodstuff, textiles and clothing, as well as machines and parts thereof. In contraposition, raw materials, coal, chemicals, petroleum products and other heavy products transports have lost relative share.

This goods’ segmentation is making decrease the average net weight transported in medium and long distance lorries (>150km) from 13,4 tonnes per vehicle in 1999 to 12,4 tonnes per vehicle in 2009 (about one tonne in a decade) source Eurostat 2011. There are reasons to think that this trend will continue in the next years, mainly because further technological developments of the society will imply even more transportation of finished and semi-finished products to longer distances.

There is as well an increased share of large containers. This is a manifest trend appearing in the statistics of major ports and railways in Europe, where the share of 40 ft and 45 ft containers is increasing over that of shorter units.

Freight railway transport is showing this tendency as well. As example it is shown the product class evolution in German railways since 2005 and Swedish railways since 2000. The category “Machinery, transport equipment, manufactured articles and miscellaneous articles” has experienced the major increase.

FIGURE 14: ABOVE) EVOLUTION GOOD CATEGORIES ON GERMAN RAILWAYS. DATA SOURCE: DESTATIS. BELOW) EVOLUTION GOOD CATEGORIES ON SWEDISH RAILWAYS. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT

In container transportation there is a trend for the utilisation of longer units, this is, more TEUs per container unit.

FIGURE 15: LINEAR TREND LINES OF NO. TEU PER HANDLED CONTAINER IN DIFFERENT TRANSPORT CONTEXTS. DATA SOURCES: ROTTERDAM PORT STATISTICS BUREAU, ANTWERP PORT STATISTICS BUREAU, HAMBURG PORT AUTHORITY AND DESTATIS.

The standardization of the cargo facilitates many logistics operations, especially when it comes to systematising the handling processes at terminals, loading ramps and warehouses. It also has advantages on safety and security, which enable better liability on transport operations. Therefore it can be said that standardization helps to increase efficiency of transportation and logistics, yet it entails more packaging. A clear example of the standardisation can be seen today with the widespread containerisation and palletisation trend.

The pallet is the mainstay of cargo loading technique in the world. The most common pallet in Europe is the EPAL whose dimensions are 1,2 m x 0,8 m.

FIGURE 16: EPAL DIMENSIONS. SOURCE: WIKIPEDIA.

A conventional European lorry, say the typical articulated road vehicle of 16,5 m length, has a capacity of 33 Europallets.

FIGURE 17: MEGA LINER 3. SOURCE: KRONE.

Semitrailers are preferred over trailer combinations mainly because of the possibility to detach the tractor and the semitrailer and using them on different services contexts in a versatile manner.

The semitrailers also constitute an intermodal loading unit when they are loaded in intermodal trains. The amount of tkm transported in intermodal semitrailers has increased dramatically during the last decade. In Germany for example they represent 17% of total tkm of intermodal transports and the trend seems to indicate further growth.

FIGURE 18: EVOLUTION OF INTERMODAL LOADING UNITS' UTILISATION IN GERMAN RAILWAYS (2005=0, IN MIO. TKM). DATA SOURCE: DESTATIS.

Assuming a semitrailer maximal legal payload capacity of 22 t to 28 t (depending on configuration), the maximal payload per pallet slot is 666 kg to 800 kg. Pallets are however lighter than this, around 400 kg according to [K+P].

Pallets can be also stacked if the cargo admits it, however this practise may lead to exceeding the total allowed load capacity of the semitrailer, especially if stacking dense goods, e.g. tiles.

As the available volume of a conventional semitrailer is around 88 m³ the maximal density of the cargo, if volume is fully occupied, should be around 0,3 t/m³.

Recently the discussion on Giga-liners introduction in Europe is pledging for vehicle length extension but without an increase of the allowed total mass, this is by sticking to 40 t instead of going for 60 t as for Finnish and Swedish giga-liners [Wissmann]. This corroborates the trend towards lower cargo densities in road transportation.

Maximum densities and other characteristics of some loading units are displayed in the following table:

	Length x wide (interior)	No. EPAL	Max. payload per pallet slot	Max. density for whole volume and payload t/m³
20' container	5,931m x 2,35 m	11	2,89 t (pallet resistance exceeded))	0,95
20' container HC (pallet wide)	5,91 m x 2,42 m	14	2 t (technical mass limit of a pallet)	0,71
Swap body C715	7,015 m x 2,46 m	16	0,831 t	0,3
Swap body C745	7,315 m x 2,46 m	18	1,18 t	0,46
Swap body C782	7,685 m x 2,46 m	19	1,4 t	0,56
30' container	8,979 m x 2,35 m	18	1,71 t	0,618
40' container	12,027 m x 2,35 m	25	1,12 t	0,4
40' container HC (pallet wide)	12,08 m x 2,44 m	30	1 t	0,386
Swap body A1360	13,465 m x 2,44 m	33	0,89 t	0,35
45' container HC (pallet wide)	13,551 m x 2,44 m	33	1 t	0,386
Wagon Habbiins-14	22,6 m x 2,83 m	65	1 t	0,369
VEL-Wagon (Estimated)	25 m x 2,83 m	70	0,9 t	0,35
Standard semitrailer	13,6 m x 2,48 m	33	0,75 t	0,3
Giga-Liner (60t) sweden	(13,6+7,315) m x 2,48 m	51	0,78 t	0,33
Giga-Liner (40t)	(13,6+7,315) m x 2,48 m	51	0,39 t	0,163
Giga Liner (90 t) tests	13,6 x 2 x 2,48	66	0,80	0,35

FIGURE 19: DENSITIES OF VARIOUS LOADING UNITS. SOURCE: VARIOUS AND INTERNAL CALCULATIONS

If gicaliners were introduced this would introduce a new level of competition against the freight rail transportation.

FIGURE 20: GIGALINER CONFIGURATIONS. DRAWING SOURCE: P. HILS / PROF. DR.-ING. U. ADLER (FHE).

The Giga-liner increases the efficiency of road transportation especially when it comes to volumetric goods, which represent the majority of consignments. Furthermore, if the allowable maximum weight for giga-liners is proportionally increased the road transportation may be as well very competitive in the heavy segment, which is the market of the traditional railways. The same happens if the maximum allowable weight for conventional lorries is increased, it favours that the road transportation prevails over rail transportation.

This may lead to an undesirable modal shift from road to rail with a detrimental effect on ecology and sustainability.

The lorries are not always carrying the maximum possible payload, (~28 tonnes) actually, the averaged carried net tonnage is much lower. In long distance transportation, for instance above the 500 km, road vehicles carry an averaged net tonnage of 13,9 t. The graph below mirrors the averaged tonnage of lorries in long distance transportations. Noticeable is that the class 24 “miscellaneous articles” prevails over other goods.

FIGURE 21: NET TONNAGE PER EUROPEAN ROAD VEHICLE ON LONG DISTANCE TRANSPORTATION (>500KM), TYPE OF GOODS AND PERCENTAGE THEREOF. (OWN GREPH) DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

Assuming that empty runs on road transportation represent 22% of the total vehicle-km (calculated from Eurostat 2011), the averaged tonnage of a loaded long distance vehicle could be calculated as $13,9/0,78 = 17,8$ t which yields about **8 t per TEU**.

This can be compared to weights of loaded containers in Rotterdam, Antwerpen and on the German railways, being **9,55 t per TEU**, **13,9 t per TEU** and **12,9 t per TEU**, respectively. (Source Rotterdam Port Authority, Antwerp Port Authority and DESTATIS, data year 2009)

Furthermore, 8 t per TEU seems to be an asymptotic limit observed in container transportation when looking at the evolution of 45 ft container mass. Percentage of 45 ft containers is growing in Rotterdam.

FIGURE 22: WEIGHT OF LOADED TEUS OF 45 FT CONTAINERS IN ROTTERDAM. DATA SOURCE: PORT OF ROTTERDAM STATISTICS BUREAU.

Container lengths in Rotterdam

FIGURE 23: PERCENTAGE OF CONTAINER LENGTHS IN ROTTERDAM. DATA SOURCE: PORT OF ROTTERDAM STATISTICS BUREAU.

Considering the exposed material the author forecasts further segmentation of goods in favour of lower-density transports, reducing by this the necessary payload of lorries and increasing the volume of cargo units as 45 ft containers.

Some recent arguments coming from the road industry are aligned with this position too:

„Beim Lang-Lkw werden die Module von bisher drei zu zwei Lkw-Kombinationen zusammengestellt. [...] Das Konzept ergibt Sinn, weil heute bei rund 80% der Transporte das Volumen der begrenzen Faktor ist –nicht das Gewicht. Eine Erhöhung des Gesamtgewichts von Lang-Lkw gegenüber herkömmlichen Fahrzeugen ist deshalb nicht zwingend notwendig. Es bleibt bei 40 Tonnen beziehungsweise 44 Tonnen im Kombinierten Verkehr.“

“Today 80% of the transport is limited by volume, not by weight. An increase of the permissible mass on longer road vehicles, in comparison to standard road vehicles, is therefore not necessary. It stays in 40 t (44 for combined transportation)”. (Free summarized translation)

Matthias Wissmann President of the German automotive industry VDA. [Wissmann]

Another observed point in goods segmentation is that the light consignments (light goods) tend to travel longer distances. This fact can be observed very easily in the chart below, which shows the type of good and its distance of transportation for the international road transports in Spain.

It is important to remark that this case is even more representative considering that the Spanish international freight rail transport is very small and therefore road transportation is almost exclusive in this traffic. In other parts of Europe as Germany, the international rail transport, together with the inland navigation absorbs some of the heavy international traffic and therefore this segmentation is less representative.

FIGURE 24: INTERNATIONAL TRANSPORTS BY ROAD IN SPAIN, DISTANCE CLASSES VS. GOODS CLASSIFICATION. (OWN GRAPH) DATA SOURCE: SPANISH MINISTERIO DE FOMENTO 2011.

Concerning the growth of general transportation in absolute terms, the situation is unclear. The forecasts on economic conjuncture, and thus on transportation demand seem to show a higher variability. In spite of this, a moderate growth in transportation is assumed for the next 10 years.

3.3. CONCLUSIONS FOR THE DEMAND ANALYSIS

Light goods are the majority of goods.

The transport of light goods grows faster than other heavy goods' transports.

Longer and higher containers as 40 ft HC or 45 ft units are preferred over shorter units as the 20 ft or short swap bodies.

Light goods travel longer distances than heavy goods.

Light goods demand higher quality of transportation, which is satisfied by road transportation.

To increase rail share in the modal split there has to be a focus on light goods in the forthcoming years.

4. OVERVIEW OF RAIL FREIGHT TRANSPORTATION SUPPLY

The services offered in the European freight railway transportation can be divided in categories depending on the kind and size of shipments carried, namely (rank by shipment size):

- Trainload
- Single wagonload
- Intermodal transportation
- Less-than-wagonload

FIGURE 25: A CLASSIFICATION OF FREIGHT RAILWAYS' OFFER.(OWN ELABORATION)

4.1. CONVENTIONAL RAIL FREIGHT

Conventional rail freight or wagonload can be divided, according to the production system, into trainloads and single wagonloads

The traditional **trainload** (TL) is the simplest form of wagonload: one shipper, one consignee, one bill of lading, one train, one single commodity. Typical goods of European trainloads can be coal, ores, oil, steel and products thereof, sand and earths, crude and manufactured minerals, building materials, chemicals, fertilizers, grains, forest products, etc. Then so, the overall performance of trainloads depends very much on the secondary and primary sectors of the economy. Consequently trainload performance follows the trend of the basic economy and for that reason the performance will improve as the overall basic demand of the economy improves. Additional improvement of trainloads' performance may come along with more participation on international traffics, entering in concurrence with short sea shipping and inland navigation.

Trainloads are also termed unit trains. However companies tend more and more to utilise unit trains to connect intermodal terminals or freight consolidation stations on a regular and direct basis, being these trainloads making part of superior intermodal or multimodal production systems.

The **single wagonload** (SWL) is the sophisticated product of wagonload by which a wagon or a coupled group thereof are shunted into the facilities of a shipper, and once loaded, they are marshalled to form trains that run over longer distances. At arrival, wagons will reach unloading facilities of consignees by similar shunting procedures. Therefore, railway sidings, auxiliary

freight stations, railway junction stations and marshalling yards may be necessary for this transportation.

Due to the operations described above, the single wagonload needs important operational resources as shunting locomotives and personnel as well as an information and logistics network for the efficient organisation of transports.

The single wagonload is very sensitive to drops in demand because the final cost per transported unit has a high proportion of indirect costs. This influences very much the offered final price, which in turn, it depends on the overall output of the system. Similarly, reduced demand leads to reduced service frequency.

Furthermore SLW nowadays tends to fail in quality, among other reasons because it has:

- Decreased number of available private sidings (fail in availability)
- Problems with train scheduling, especially in international traffic (fail in punctuality, transport time)
- Incompatible service hours for last mile, delivering (fail in punctuality, transport time)
- Uncertain timing for collecting and delivering wagons (fail in traceability, punctuality)
- Still wagons at customer sidings, yards etc. (fail in transport time, flexibility, cargo security)
- Cargo damage during transport operations e.g. marshalling (fail in cargo safety)
- Insufficient knowledge of SWL performance level to enable accurate offer appraisal (fail in marketability, complementary servicing)

This overall quality decline weakens the SLW's competitiveness in modern logistics contexts. Hence, markets with demanding production strategies as the JIT (Just-in-Time) will use other transport options like the road-only.

Hence, the big challenge of SLW is to improve quality, gain in excellence and achieve reputation. Only by this higher-value markets can be addressed and modal shift can happen.

Typical single wagonloads' transported goods are the same as trainloads but in smaller consignments' sizes, this is, from a single wagon to a group thereof. It addresses also general palletized cargo, mainly with wagons of class H.

In Europe, the recession derived from the financial crisis of 2007 has accentuated the decline of conventional freight (wagonload) performance, being the business area of coal, iron ore and other mining products – including mineral oil – the most damaged. Then so, turnover drops on these products of 30% between 2008 and 2009 [DB Schenker] as the case of DB Schenker Rail, leader in rail freight in Europe, were a clear mirror of the situation on overall European wagonload.

FIGURE 26: COMBINED TRANSPORT VS. WAGONLOAD IN EUROPE. (OWN GRAPH) DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2010.

FIGURE 27: COMBINED TRANSPORT VS. WAGONLOAD IN GERMANY. (OWN GRAPH) DATA SOURCE: DESTATIS, EUROSTAT, DB AG WETTBEWERBSBERICHT 2010.

Apparently since the second quarter of 2009 a recovering trend of the German economy is taking place and this has brought about an increase on performance.

Without being extremely enthusiastic about this fact, it can be said for example that the transportation of wagonloads, especially in trainloads, in Germany, has recovered 20% in one year, enabling to reach again performance levels of 2007. At the finalisation of this thesis, June of 2012, it seems that again that a new recession is coming.

FIGURE 28: GERMAN RAIL TRANSPORTATION OF (IN TONNES): SOLID MINERAL FUEL, PETROLEUM PRODUCTS, ORES AND METAL WASTE, METAL PRODUCTS, CRUDE AND MANUFACTURED MINERALS, BUILDING MATERIALS, FERTILIZERS AND CHEMICALS (TYPICAL GOODS OF TRAINLOADS).DATA SOURCE: DESTATIS 2011.

In respect to the recovery trend of the German economy – view of Jan 2011 –, other European countries are following with a certain delay and different growth patterns. Hence the performance of wagonload could be intuitively sensed from these figures.

FIGURE 29: SEASONALLY ADJUSTED GDP AT MARKET PRICES IN SOME EUROPEAN COUNTRIES. SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

The trainload is the freight rail business working under the strictest price conditions overall in rail freight transportation. In so doing, quality parameters as: time for transportation, reliability and flexibility are of secondary importance with respect to final price per transported tonne. Still, trainloads usually enjoy fair quality standards since from a logistics point of view they are quite easy to program and to exploit within a given railway timetable, especially if they are domestic trainloads.

With the affordable raw materials and solid fuels coming from overseas, e.g. Iron ore from Brazil, coal from South Africa and Australia etc. the amount of international trainloads connecting European ports with industrial regions has grown and with them the averaged rail distance of transportation.

In western Europe, an important amount of trainloads importing coal and iron ore utilise mostly the ports of the northern range but also the ports located in southern range, namely:

Top ten EU ports ranked by dry bulk import (mostly iron ore and coal)	% of incoming dry bulk over total EU dry bulk ports import (EU import of ca. 600 mio tonnes/y 2009)
Rotterdam (NL)	8,6%
Amsterdam (NL)	4,5%
Grimsby (UK)	3%
Hamburg (DE)	2,5%
Taranto (IT)	2,4%
Dunkirk (FR)	2,3%
Ravenna (IT)	2%
Antwerp (BE)	1,8%
Gijon (ES)	1,8%
Ghent (BE)	1,7%

FIGURE 30: TOP TEN PORTS RANKED BY DRY BULK IMPORT. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

Trainloads also carry important amounts of coal originated in Poland to destinations in industrial regions of Germany (Rhine and Ruhr), these account by roughly 2 million tonnes per year (Destatis 2010).

Apart from coal and iron ore, trainloads in Western Europe carry many petroleum derivatives in tank wagons all over Europe. In so doing different kinds of diesel fuels, gasoline, kerosene, naphtha etc. are predominant in trainloads; only in Germany approximately 30 million tonnes per year – 11% of German rail transports and 20% of German trainloads tonnage – move at an average distance of 150 km between refineries, intermediate deposits and other facilities.

The chemical industry, mainly present along the Rhine Valley, large cities and ports' industrial areas is also benefitting from the performance of trainloads and single wagonloads, then so companies like BASF, Henkel and DOW are destination and source of such transports, for instance, tank trains/wagons or dry-bulk trains/wagons.

The wagonload is also participating very much on the transportation of sand, earths, loose materials, gravel, raw minerals, cements, etc. These transportations would represent about 20% of the total tonnage of wagonloads in Western Europe.

Finally, the transportation of steel industry products, and machinery parts as well as finalized vehicles occupies another important share of total conventional rail freight. There is a thumb rule that says that for every produced tonne of crude steel by the industry, the trains carry four

tonnes of inputs and products thereto, namely: coal, iron ore, semi-finished products, and finished products as automobiles. [Siegmann 1].

Summarizing, wagonloads in Western Europe occupy a key share within total rail freight transportation of about 70% on total tkm. However single wagon load services are being rationalised due to poor productivity and some markets are being lost, f.i. SNCF announced a decrease of about 60% on SWL in order to cut back losses on this kind of traffics. [AUTF]

The share of trainloads over total rail freight exceeds 40% in overall amount of tkm in most of the European countries; in some countries with poor performance in SWL as Spain [DG TREN] the share of trainloads is even higher. In countries with high performance in combined transportation and SWL like Switzerland the trainloads performance is much lower.

The following table depicts the share of trainloads, single wagonloads and intermodal transportation over total rail freight performance in the top 19 European rail freight performers.

2009	Mio. t-km	TL	SWL	CT
Germany	95834	42%	27%	31%
Poland	43445	61%	31%	8%
France	32130	46%	25%	29%
United Kingdom	21168	n.a.	n.a.	30%
Sweden	19155	42%	30%	28%
Latvia	18725	n.a.	n.a.	1%
Italy	17791	41%	15%	44%
Austria	17767	38%	37%	26%
Czech Republic	12791	44%	43%	13%
Lithuania	11888	n.a.	n.a.	0%
Romania	11088	46%	46%	8%
Switzerland	10565	23%	26%	51%
Finland	8872	60%	35%	6%
Hungary	7673	33%	48%	19%
Spain	7547	77%	1%	22%
Slovakia	6964	47%	48%	6%
Belgium	6374	40%	28%	32%
Estonia	5947	n.a.	n.a.	6%
Netherlands	5578	40%	21%	39%
TOP 19	361302	~47%	~30%	23%

FIGURE 31: 2009 COUNTRY-BASED PERCENTAGES ON TL, SWL AND CT IN EUROPE IN T-KM (CALCULATED). DATA SOURCE: VARIOUS (SEE BELOW).

Since there are few dedicated statistics that address this subject particularly, the above values have been estimated from different statistical inputs (Eurostat, national statistics offices, UIC stats), recent studies examination namely: [ERIM], [DIOMIS], [CER] Business Cases Study – data of 2006 – and company consultations. An adaptation to 2009 has been done considering an averaged decrease of SWL in 20%, and increases of TL and CT in 3% and 17% respectively. This trend has been inferred from the evolution of different types of cargo transported in German railways from 2006 to 2009 and has been crosschecked with business reports of the companies Trenitalia, DB AG, SNCF and RCA.

The author acknowledges certain inaccuracy on calculated results, especially when it comes to TL and SWL percentages as they are not usually reported separately in statistics databases.

Another interesting point is the amount of train-km occurring in European networks. The following table has been estimated together with the table of tkm percentages, in this case mainly from traffic data from the CER corridors study, 2006.

2009	1000 Tr-km	TL	SWL	CT
Germany	202294	33%	28%	40%
Poland	64176	53%	36%	11%
France	74209	36%	26%	38%
United Kingdom	36959	n.a.	n.a.	39%
Sweden	37778	33%	31%	36%
Latvia	11326	n.a.	n.a.	2%
Italy	46248	30%	15%	55%
Austria	49061	29%	38%	33%
Czech Republic	29811	36%	46%	18%
Lithuania	8095	n.a.	n.a.	0%
Romania	17201	38%	51%	11%
Switzerland	29519	16%	24%	60%
Finland	14899	51%	41%	8%
Hungary	17076	26%	50%	25%
Spain	23331	67%	1%	32%
Slovakia	10969	39%	53%	8%
Belgium	11677	31%	29%	40%
Estonia	3226	n.a.	n.a.	8%
Netherlands	9460	30%	21%	49%
TOP 19	697316	~36%	~30%	33%

FIGURE 32: TRAIN-KM OCCURRING IN EUROPEAN NETWORKS. SOURCE: VARIOUS (SEE EXPLANATION).

4.1.1. TRAIN WEIGHT, AXLE LOAD AND LENGHT

As a result, an estimation of the average net tonnage transported per train in the TOP 19 countries could look as follows:

2009	Averaged	TL	SWL	CT
Germany	474	613	457	370
Poland	677	784	585	474
France	433	553	412	334
United Kingdom	573	n.a.	n.a.	444
Sweden	507	651	485	393
Latvia	1653	n.a.	n.a.	1141
Italy	385	516	385	312
Austria	362	468	349	283
Czech Republic	429	529	394	319
Lithuania	1469	n.a.	n.a.	1038
Romania	645	780	581	471
Switzerland	358	510	380	308
Finland	595	688	513	416
Hungary	449	580	432	350
Spain	323	372	277	225
Slovakia	635	762	568	460
Belgium	546	710	529	429
Estonia	1843	n.a.	n.a.	1281
Netherlands	590	782	583	472
TOP 19	518	671	513	358

FIGURE 33: ESTIMATED AVERAGED NET TONNAGE TRANSPORTED PER TRAIN IN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES. SOURCE: VARIOUS (SEE EXPLANATION).

Due to the coupling technology – screw coupler and buffers – the European trains have technical limitations – coupler max. tension and other longitudinal dynamics constraints – to operate efficiently heavy loads on certain lines. For instance, German operating rules limit train mass to 4000 tons with screw couplers, while Sweden regularly operates trains of 3200 tons on 17‰ grades.

Trains with central couplers, as used in the Baltic countries and Russia have this problem too but to a lesser extent, hence longer as well as heavier trains are typical there. In other parts of the world, e.g. the U.S., apart from having central coupler many trains have distributed power. This is more than one working locomotive along the train, enabling it to negotiate steeper ramps. These locomotives communicate with each other via radio and deploy simultaneous efforts in different parts of the train. This improves longitudinal dynamics and reduces stresses. However these systems are not established in Europe and remain under investigation.

Typical trainload traffic utilises heavier trains than SWL trains or intermodal trains (the lightest ones). For that reason trainloads usually do not fully use the allowed train length, since they reach the mass limitation before; it is what is called a mass-constrained train. On the other hand, SWL and CT trains are more prone to be length-constrained since they use to be lighter per length unit, specially the CT trains.

Empty runs of wagons decrease the averaged net tonnage transported in TLs (in SWL and CT too). It is estimated that about 40% of the total wagon-km are done in empty runs (Eurostat 2010). It is assumed that the percentage of empty km done by conventional wagons of TLs is higher than the average. A 50% empty usage for wagons of TL seems quite realistic. In SWL, due to re-routing of the wagons to find backloads, the percentage of empty runs should be sensibly lower than the average; from 30 to 35% could be a plausible range. In CT, the empty run percentage could be even lower – around 15% – however it has to be bore in mind that there is an important transportation of empty containers – 25% according to Eurostat 2010 – which from an operative standpoint are not considered empty runs.

Loaded trains of TL are the heaviest trains circulating on the networks. In countries with automatic central coupling, trains can be more than twice as heavy and twice as long as in countries with screw coupler and buffers. Typical train weights of loaded TL in countries with screw coupling can be around 2500 tonnes if the topography is flat, being reduced to about 1500 tonnes or less if the topography is more adverse. In some sections the topography is so adverse that an uncoupled push locomotive has to be added behind the train to negotiate a particular ramp.

The loaded trainloads do not usually exhaust the allowed train length since they reach a weight limitation before. Typical lengths of loaded trains on the trainload segment should be below 450m if they do not have upgraded rolling stock (more and/or more powerful locomotives, central coupler, distributed power, etc). Trains with metal products (e.g. steel coils) are usually shorter, around 200m.

The wagons' length of TLs varies between 12 m (Shimmnss) and 15 m being most of them 4-axled bogie wagons, there are as well 6-axled wagons for the transportation of steel products and heavy materials and there are wagons with central coupling for the transportation of large consignments of iron ore in Germany. Remarkable exceptions as the 4-axle wagons for the transportation of iron ore along the Malmbanan can be found in Sweden, with 30 t/axle and central coupler too, in trains of normally 8600 tons.

The following graph could have a signification for trainloads length and weight; it has been produced following the idea of Voges and Sachse. [Voges und Sachse]

FIGURE 34: TRAIN LENGTH - CARGO DENSITY GRAPH (I).

The graph is a representation of the train length over the cargo density and it has the following assumptions:

The maximal train length is 740m

The maximal axle load is 22,5 tonnes

The maximal train gross weight is 2500 tonnes

The wagon lengths, tares and loading cross sections are (Data from Tatravagonka):

Talns=15m, 25t and 5,1 m3/m

Sgns 60'=19m, 19t and 5,4 m3/m

VEL 80'=25m, 22t and 5,4 m3/m

The graph has a secondary Y-axis (to the right) for representing the gross tonnage of the train and its available volume.

Main observations:

- Axle load increase is in principle significant for dense materials but it has to be accompanied by extended train weight to make better use of rail slots. Without extended train weight it would lead to fewer wagons (and axles) per train which would imply an important saving on wagons' costs. However, infrastructure charges, locomotive, energy and indirect costs of the train would remain more or less the same. Another lecture of

axle load increase benefit can be done also for light goods if the amount of axles is reduced.

- Train weight increase, say up to 4000 t, without axle load extension would mean trainloads fully using the available max. length (700m), further weights increases would need axle load increases for having a meaning, for example 5000 t of train weight should need 25 t/axle, 6000 t should need 30t/axle (or more axles per wagon), in any case upgraded rolling stock and/or improved train dynamics should be necessary (central or reinforced coupler, distributed traction and/or more powerful locomotives). Infrastructure charges should be higher by higher axle loads and also because increased train weight, the power consumption should be higher too, however some indirect costs would remain the same and that would mean lower unitary costs per transported tonne (economies of scale).
- Train length extension, say up to 1500 m, would be useful for light transports, e.g. containers, automobiles, paper, but it should be as well accompanied by a train weight increase in order to take advantage of the length.
- A rough concept of VEL-Wagon, VEL80' as described above, under the current conditions, would offer a capable multipurpose platform for a number of commodities categorized in the light segment, taking advantage of the available length and with lower number of axles and thus a cost saving.

The following graph proposes a coordinated extension of some parameters:

Train length from 740 to 1500 m

Train weight from 2500 to 5000 t

Axle load from 22,5 to 25 t

FIGURE 35: TRAIN LENGTH - CARGO DENSITY GRAPH (II).

Although not shown in the graph, larger loading gauges will also increase wagon loading and train mass, even without increasing train length. Many lines in Sweden and even the Øresund link to Denmark are cleared for intermodal gauge P/C 450 (4.83 m tall), which is useful not only to intermodal load units but also to e.g. packaged lumber.

In a future situation where longer and heavier trains may be more frequent, wagonloads could cut costs in infrastructure charges by making better use of rail slots.

4.1.2. COSTS

An overview of cost categories' percentages for a typical European trainload is provided in the following graph:

FIGURE 36: COSTS PERCENTAGES EXAMPLE OF A DOMESTIC TRAINLOAD IN GERMANY. SOURCE: TUB INTERNAL KNOWLEDGE BASED ON PREVIOUS PROJECTS CALCULATIONS.

A graphical representation of typical SWL trains' costs would be too inaccurate in the sense that it would not include correctly the proportional part of the fixed costs involved, which are very dependent on overall traffic output. However, Prof. Siegmann indicates that an efficient SWL transport would have 60% of the costs related to the long rail haul (as represented in the above exhibit) and 40% for the rest, including marshalling and last kilometre transport. [Siegmann 2]

In any case, by looking at the costs' distribution of conventional freight trainloads it is possible to see that wagons do not represent the biggest share overall, but "infrastructure", "other" and "energy" do. Hence, an investment in wagons that would improve the overall efficiency of the system, in terms of availability, energy consumption, capacity utilisation, etc. would have an important effect with little proportional cost.

For more information on railway costs please consult [Troche, Dissertation].

4.1.3. LESS-THAN-WAGONLOAD TRAFFIC

The less-than-wagonload traffic, also known as part-load traffic, LCL (Less-than-Carload), LTL (Less-than-Truckload) is a minor segment in freight railways that competes directly with pure road in the medium distances and with the air freight in the long distances. The users of these products require for example the transportation of mail and parcels under very strict time

conditions, or in other cases, the transportation of small containers, pallets and other cargos' forms, that do not make up a full wagon or an ITU, under given time conditions.

The railways have created some product offers that match with these demand requirements, then so, for example there are fast trains (TGV postal, Parcel Intercity) that carry mail and parcels overnight. However these transports are marginal if compared to total rail freight transports.

There are in Europe trains that carry consolidated LCLs between multimodal freight stations where lorries and trains interchange cargo after little or no intermediate storage. The logistics term for this production system is cross-docking, the German company DB Schenker utilizes the commercial name Railport© for a similar concept, in Austria there is as well a supply using a similar system.

FIGURE 37: RAILPORTS© IN EUROPE. SOURCE: DB SCHENKER.

4.1.4. CONVENTIONAL WAGONS SUPPLY

The conventional freight wagons employed in trainload traffic and single wagonload traffic present a wide diversity on wagon classes. The following table is based on the UIC classification of goods wagons:

Class	Wagon type	Main cargo
E	Ordinary open high-sided wagon	Coal, scrap, minerals
F	Special open high-sided wagon, (bottom-dump)	Loose materials, minerals
G	Ordinary covered wagon	General cargo -Old-

H	Special covered wagon	General & Palletised cargo
I	Refrigerated wagon	Temperature-sensitive cargo, - not representative-
K*	Ordinary flat wagon with separate wheelsets	General cargo, lumber -old-
L*	Special flat wagon with separate wheelsets	Automotive, forest products, containers
O	Open multi-purpose wagon (composite open high-sided flat wagon)	Loose materials -old-
R*	Ordinary flat wagon with bogies	General, long cargo
S*	Special flat wagon with bogies	Sdg and Sg Intermodal, Sa, Sh for heavy steel products
T	Goods wagon with opening roof	Loose materials
U	Special wagons	Various
Z	Tank wagon	Liquids

** With denomination "g", for intermodal transport, in majority "Sg"*

FIGURE 38: CLASSIFICATION OF GOODS WAGONS. SOURCE: UIC.

In Germany for example, the wagon classes' distribution could look as follows:

Based on [VPI] and DBAG estimations, stand 2008:

FIGURE 39: WAGON CLASSES IN GERMANY 2008. (OWN GRAPH) DATA SOURCE: VPI AND DBAG.

In the diagram, the clear-coloured wagon classes indicate light wagons (tare <1,2 t/m; rank: L,H,S,R); exceptions are “Sa” and “Sh” which are heavy duty wagons for the transportation of steel products, e.g. plates and coils.

H wagons are usually employed for the transportation of general, packaged, rolled and palletized cargo that is moisture-sensitive. In comparison with their predecessors -G-wagons with sliding doors – they have sliding walls to enable an easier (un)loading process with forklifts or other handling equipment.

These wagons are the conventional wagons closest to be “road competitors” since they can address similar markets as the road does. As an example, in the below figure is shown a latest-generation temperature-controlled wagon employed nowadays by the Swiss railways.

FIGURE 40: HBBILLS-UY FOR TEMPERATURE-CONTROLLED CARGO, FOR 38 EUROPALLETS. PHOTO SOURCE: SBB.

It has to be said though that Swiss policy is very favourable towards the use of environmentally-friendly transportation modes as railways. Hence single wagonloads that would not be economically viable in other parts of Europe are possible there.

Furthermore, H-wagons are widely employed in most of European countries, one of the largest ones is the Habbiins, with loading length of 22m, loading width of 2,84m and a capacity for 63 Europallets (payload ~1 t/pallet slot).

EXHIBIT 1: 63-PALLET LOADING SCHEMA OF HABBIINS.

FIGURE 41: 61-PALLET LOADING SCHEMA OF HABBIINS IF INTERMEDIATE WALLS ARE USED.

An equivalent two-axle wagon type “L” would be the Laaiis, with a loading length of ~25m, and a capacity for 36x2 Europallets (payload per pallet slot 880 kg).

FIGURE 42: TWO-AXLE WAGON TYPE "L". SOURCE: TRANSWAGGON.

EXHIBIT 2: 7 LOADING SCHEMA OF A LAIIS, LEFT WITH 36 EUROPALLETS, RIGHT WITH 30 INDUSTRY PALLETS. PICTURE SOURCE: TRANSWAGGON.

To be able to accommodate three rows of industry pallets (1x1,2m) this wagon is more than 3 m wide.

Conventional light wagons L, R can be employed for the transportation of cargo that is not moisture-sensitive and therefore it can be transported at open-air, e.g. logs, lumber, automobiles, trucks, plastic pipes etc.

FIGURE 43: LAAS, 27M, TARE 26T. SOURCE: TRANSWAGGON.

FIGURE 44: LAADKS, 27M, TARE 24,5T, LOADING HEIGHT 0,8M. SOURCE: TRANSWAGGON.

FIGURE 45. LAEKK(Q)S, 26,2M, TARE:25,5T, LOADING HEIGHT 0,64M. SOURCE: ATGLOGISTIK.COM.

Finally in the last times there are more and more examples of conventional rail freights that are being containerised and/or standardized in detachable units. Some examples are shown below.

FIGURE 46: TANK CONTAINERS ONTO 60' WAGONS BEING HUMPED AT SEDDIN (NEARBY BERLIN). PHOTO: TUB, SCHIENENFAHRWEGE UND BAHNBETRIEB.

FIGURE 47: WOODTAINER XXL OF INNOFREIGHT. SOURCE: INNOFREIGHT.

FIGURE 48: AUSTRALIAN 40 FOOT / 64.4M3 'CFCLA 400XX' CONTAINER ON WAGON AND ON THE GROUND SHOWING QUAD DISCHARGE DOORS. SOURCE: WONGM'S RAIL GALLERY.

FIGURE 49: ROUND WOOD PALLET OF INNOFREIGHT. SOURCE: INNOFREIGHT.

FIGURE 50: NESKA 30-FOOT BLACK BOXX FOR THYSSENKRUPP MINENERGY. SOURCE: DUISPORT MAGAZIN 2/2010.

FIGURE 51: WASCOSA FLEX FREIGHT SYSTEM, 60' E-BOX. SOURCE: WASCOSA, HECHT TUB

FIGURE 52: REXWALS DUALWAGEN GENERATION 1. SOURCE: DVZ 28.08.2007.

FIGURE 53: REXWALS DUALWAGEN GENERATION 2. SOURCE: BAHNONLINE.CH 2009.

FIGURE 54: LAAIILPS (TRANSWAGGON FOR VW) WITH DETACHABLE SUPERSTRUCTURE. SOURCE: DREHSCHIEBE-FOREN.DE, USER: MICHAEL K.

4.1. CONCLUSIONS FOR THE SUPPLY ANALYSIS

The conventional railways have lost market share in total railways, especially when considering the single wagon load branch, this is mostly due to a fail on quality. The economic crisis has accentuated this trend.

European railways performed about 400 Mrd. t-km in 2010 of which: ~45% were trainloads TL, ~25% single wagonloads SWL and ~25% intermodal loads.

Intermodal trains are the lightest trains with ~350 net tons per train, then SWL trains with 510t and finally TL trains with 670 t.

The combined transport has increased its share on railways and has resisted better the crisis.

Intermodal trains are growing rapidly in terms of amount of trains and distance of transportation (~600 km). Train averaged length is 650 m (Germany).

Intermodal wagons represent about 15% of the total fleet and they perform about 25% of the total t-km, are by large the most efficiently-employed wagons.

The combined transport has increased very much its share on international transports, interoperability and administrative progresses among countries (e.g. freight corridors) are helping.

Freight railways and intermodal transports become more competitive by longer distances, which are possible due to border free operations.

An investment in wagons that would improve the overall efficiency of the system, in terms of availability, energy consumption, capacity utilisation, etc. would have an important effect with little proportional cost.

Axle load extension is very interesting for light goods if lighter wagons with fewer wheels are employed. This may be even more interesting than train length extension.

In the last times there are more and more examples of conventional rail freights that are being containerized and/or standardized in detachable units.

H-wagons are the conventional wagons closest to be “road competitors” since they can address similar markets as the road does.

Intermodal wagons are able to address different markets in a multipurpose way too.

5. INTERMODAL TRANSPORT

The intermodal road/rail traffic in Europe, in contrast to conventional rail freight traffic, has been aligned with the general growth pattern of European economy, performing in most cases even on a superior level.

FIGURE 55: EVOLUTION OF INTERMODAL AND CONVENTIONAL RAIL FREIGHT IN EU27 IN COMPARISON TO GDP EVOLUTION. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011.

The major part of this success has come along with the recent growth of overseas container transportation, which has demanded numerous rail transports of containers along and across the European hinterlands. Another important reason for growth of intermodal transports, and of rail freight transports in general, has been the increased participation of international traffics. This participation was encouraged and procured by the recent advances on interoperability of European railways systems and was aligned with administrative agreements between the different European countries. In that context, the forthcoming future will bring about even more advances in terms of interoperability, to name one example, the [TAF-TSI] (Technical Specifications for Interoperability for Telematic Applications for Freight) that drafts a standardized playground for the European IT deployment on rail freight operations and data exchange between different railway actors.

The advances in interoperability of systems combined with an appropriate legislation will pave the way for a European rail network for competitive freight.

The traffic in intermodal road/rail transportation can be classified in four large groups depending on the nature of the market addressed and the geographic coverage of it, namely: hinterland (maritime) or continental and international or domestic traffic.

FIGURE 56: SHARE OF INTERMODAL TRAFFICS IN TKM 2005 AND 2010. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011, UIRR STATISTICS 2010 AND AGENDA 2015 FOR COMBINED TRANSPORT IN EUROPE [UIC 2].

The charts show an important participation and growth of hinterland (maritime) traffics, as said, majorly motivated by the container trade booming during these last years. It is also remarkable the growth of international traffics, majorly due to the recent advances on interoperability between railway systems (international freight corridors). Conversely, the domestic continental rail services have decreased in share in spite of undergoing an important growth too.

Apparently the trend indicates a further increase of hinterland and international traffics, which are being more and more deployed on a freight corridor basis. In that way, the REGULATION (EU) No 913/2010 lays down rules for the establishment and organization of international rail corridors for competitive rail freight. Most of these corridors are very relevant for the intermodal transportation.

5.1. TRAFFIC CLASSIFICATION BY GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE: INTERNATIONAL / NATIONAL

In the past intermodal service providers tended to be specialized either on international services or in domestic services exclusively. Hence, they generated traffic that had a clear geographic distinction. Nowadays though, there are more and more intermodal providers addressing both markets at the same time.

An 83-company survey commissioned by the Combined Transport Group of the UIC revealed that 46% of the intermodal service providers are addressing both markets indistinctly. These companies represented 80% (growing trend) of the total intermodal market share in 2009 (measured in TEUs). The figures are contained in the “2010 Report on Combined Transport in Europe” of [UIC 5] (pg. 18). An illustrative chart from this report is shown below.

Source: 83 intermodal service providers

FIGURE 57: GEOGRAPHIC INTERMODAL SERVICE PORTFOLIO BY COMPANIES AND TEU: 2005, 2007, 2009. SOURCE: 2010 REPORT ON COMBINED TRANSPORT IN EUROPE [UIC 5]

By looking at these charts there are reasons to think that today in intermodal transportation the distinction between international and national traffics has lost some sense, the following arguments also induce to that thought:

- Interoperability between different railways systems and rolling stock is being achieved and the advances have been very important during the last decades, facilitating the cross-border services, e.g. corridor between Rotterdam and Switzerland.
- European infrastructure managers and operators intend to homogenize criteria on railway infrastructure use (booking, charges, timetables, etc.) and services coverage on a pan-European basis. Example: RNE corridors, EC Rail Freight Corridors.
- There are more and more intermodal services operating in a corridor-basis rather than on exclusively national or international basis. In intermodal transportation the point-to-point shuttle connection can be deployed on a corridor section regardless of the number of national borders to be crossed.
- Railway transports are more efficient on increased longer transport distances; this requires in many cases to cross more than one national border. E.g. larger port hinterlands.

In that way, the desirable situation of European railway system seems to go for a homogenized pan-European context in which intermodal companies can address the demand without paying much attention to the number of national borders to be crossed. Naturally, custom procedures and common member legislation have to be aligned with this situation.

Today the statistic data in European intermodal transportation shows about a 50/50 proportion of international traffics over domestic traffics. The International Union of combined Road-Rail transport companies (UIIRR) is reporting an important amount of the total performed tkm in European intermodal transportation, see table below:

Intermodal traffic in mio. tkm	Domestic	International	Total
EU27+CH 2009	~42.000	~42.000	~84.000
UIRR 2009	8.443	30.455	38.898
Share of UIRR in EU27+CH	~20%	~72%	~46%

FIGURE 58: INTERMODAL TRAFFICS IN 2010. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011, UIRR STATISTICS 2010.

The rail performance of UIRR companies is especially important in the **international traffic** segment where they perform about 72% of the total European international intermodal transportation.

This fact is very interesting for data analysis purposes since the UIRR keeps a very thorough statistics database on intermodal traffics. Hence, some conclusions obtained from these statistics, especially when it comes to techniques employed, corridor specific performance and averaged distances of transport, could help to interpret what happens in the whole European context of international intermodal transports.

According to 2010 data of UIRR, the most important international relations in Europe can be ranked as follows (it includes accompanied and unaccompanied intermodal transports):

#	UIRR relation	TEUkm in 2010 (mio.)	% of total EU27+CH international TEUkm	Averaged distance of transport	Gross tones per TEU
1	Germany → Italy	439	10,7%	760	14
2	Italy → Germany	427	10,5%	707	12
3	Belgium → Italy	198	4,8%	1.075	13
4	Italy → Belgium	180	4,4%	1.055	10
5	Austria → Germany	110	2,7%	1.000	10
6	Germany → Austria	97	2,4%	929	11
7	Germany → Poland	83	2,0%	961	7
8	Netherlands → Italy	79	1,9%	1.145	13
9	Italy → Netherlands	69	1,7%	1.119	11
10	Belgium → France	64	1,6%	863	10
Total UIRR TOP 10 international relations		1746	43%	855	12
Total UIRR international traffic		2.941	72%	836	11,7
Total international EU27+CH traffic		3.342	100%	~840	~11,7
		TEUkm in 2010 (mio.)	% of total EU27+CH international TEUkm	Averaged distance of transportation	Gross tones per TEU

FIGURE 59: INTERMODAL RELATIONS IN EUROPE IN 2010. DATA SOURCE: UIRR STATISTICS 2010.

Some of the relations described above can be identified in the following train traffic density map of ERIM 2007 (UIC):

FIGURE 60: MAIN INTERMODAL TRAFFIC AREAS IN EUROPE. BACKGROUND GRAPH SOURCE: ERIM UIC 2008.

The utilization of the different loading techniques (ILUs) is also reported by UIRR. The following chart shows three important trends:

- Share decrease on rolling motorways (RR)
The author considers the rolling highway technique a rudimentary railway solution to unfavourable road transport conditions e.g. bad mountain roads, traffic bans, geographic obstacles etc.
- Increase of utilization of longer units (longer than 8:30m, mostly 40 ft and 45 ft containers)
This is happening because the consignments need more volume.
- Decrease of averaged gross weight of consignment (1 consignment = 2 TEUs)
This happens because the volume-oriented consignment has more intrinsic value than the heavy-oriented consignment. Volume-oriented consignments are more typical of advanced logistics systems.

FIGURE 61: UIRR INTERNATIONAL TECHNIQUES' SHARE (IN NO. CONSIGNMENTS) AND AVERAGE GROSS WEIGHT PER CONSIGNMENT. DATA SOURCE: UIRR. (NOTE: SHORT ILU < 8,3 M, LONG ILU >8,3 M)

The **domestic (national) traffic** in intermodal transportation is the one having origin, destination and full route within the domains of a given national railway network. For this reason, the averaged domestic distance of transportation is usually shorter than of international transportations. The averaged domestic distance in Europe is around 400 km (calculated from Eurostat 2010 data).

FIGURE 62: AVERAGED TRANSPORT DISTANCES IN EUROPEAN INTERMODAL TRAINS.

The companies of the UIRR only generate the 20% of the national transport (measured in tkm) the remaining 80% is carried out by a large group of companies, among which there are some subsidiaries of former national companies and other new entrants.

5.2. TRAFFIC CLASSIFICATION BY MARKET NATURE: HINTERLAND /CONTINENTAL

There is another classification criterion has much more influence on the characteristics of the traffic than the previous one. It basically distinguishes two kinds of trains with different loading patterns:

- Hinterland container trains with ISO containers.

- Continental trains with swap bodies, semitrailers, full lorries and other kinds of domestic units.

5.2.1. HINTERLAND (OR MARITIME) TRAFFIC

This kind of traffic has its origin in overseas container transportation. Typically the trains are the terrestrial link (land leg) between seaports and inland terminals in European mainland. The busiest container ports in Europe (Rotterdam, Antwerp, Hamburg, Bremen, Le Havre, etc.) are connected via rail and via hub with the important hinterland regions in Europe, namely Northern Italy, South and West Germany, Alpine Range, Central Europe and Paris.

There are basically two dominating container sizes:

- 20 ft ISO Containers and
- 40 ft ISO Containers

FIGURE 63: TYPE OF MARITIME CONTAINERS IN EUROPE (INCLUDES TR, NO, CH) (2000 & 2010), IN NUMBER OF TOTAL CONTAINERS HANDLED. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011

In the past, the 20 ft containers were the majority, for instance in 1970 the TEU/Container ratio in Rotterdam was 1,45, which indicates that there were 55% of 20 ft units and 45% of 40 ft units (Rotterdam Port statistics).

Nowadays it is the opposite situation, with 40 ft containers being majority (55% share) and 20 ft containers' share decreasing to 41% (Eurostat 2011); 20 ft containers' share decrease is a clear trend observed in all European ports.

There are as well two other types of containers in Europe, 30 ft and 45 ft which represent nowadays less than 4% share in total.

The 30 ft containers are less and less employed (<1% share) and 45 ft containers are more and more employed, especially when it comes to the Short Sea Shipping traffic and the traffic between Northern Europe and Western Europe, e.g. UK to Rotterdam.

The below figure shows the principal sources and destinations of 30 ft and 45 ft containers.

45 ft units are mostly employed in intra-EU transports with 45-ft-adapted short sea vessels, conversely in deep ocean transport 40 ft and 20 ft units are practically exclusive, with only little transport of 45 ft containers.

The pallet-wide 45 ft container with length 13,716 meters must nowadays have chamfered corners to comply with European Directive 96/53/EC (road vehicle dimensions) and thereby be able to cross European borders by lorry.

There is a manifest increasing trend on the use of 45 ft containers (Eurostat 2011); the author envisages further growth of this unit length in European ports (short sea shipping and deep ocean shipping), railway terminals (continental and hinterland) and European road transportation, as it matches with the maximum allowed semitrailer dimensions in Europe

FIGURE 64: SOURCE AND DESTINATION PORTS OF 30 FT AND 45 FT CONTAINERS. DATA SOURCE: EUROSTAT 2011

FIGURE 65: SHORT SEA SHIPPING VESSEL WITH 45 FT UNITS, VIEW OF STORAGE AREA AND RAIL TRACKS IN ROTTERDAM PORT. SOURCE IMAGE: GOOGLE EARTH 2011.

Container type	Length (m)	Width (m)	Height (m)	Tare (kg)	Max. gross weight (kg)	% of total dry containers	Averaged gross weight loaded (kg) 2010
20 ft dry standard	6,096	2,438	2,591	2.230	30.480	41% (trend ↯)	19.500
40 ft dry standard	12,192	2,438	2,591	3.700	32.500	23% (trend ↓)	22.500
40 ft dry high cube	12,192	2,438	2,896	3.830	32.500	33% (trend ↑)	22.500
45 ft dry high cube	13,716	2,438	2,896	4.000	32.500	3% (trend ↗)	23.000

FIGURE 66: MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF ISO CONTAINERS. SOURCE VARIOUS, SEE BELOW.

The 20 ft and 40 ft containers are employed extensively in deep ocean transportation; the most common units are the dry containers, which dimensions, shares in total container fleet and averaged gross weights are presented (source dimensions: Maersk line; source percentages: Ci-Container Census 2003 and own calculations for 2010; source avg. gross weight: Rotterdam, Antwerp, Le Havre and Hamburg port statistics):

Dry containers are the most common containers in the world since they represent about 89% of total units, reefer containers represent around 5% and other special types the remaining 6%,

including tanks, open-top, flatracks, cellular pallet-wide, platform, ventilated, etc. (Data source: Containerisation International Market Analysis: World Container Census 2003)

High-cube 40 ft containers are replacing rapidly the standard 40 ft containers, which are ~30 cm shorter in height; 45 ft containers do not represent more than 2% of the total fleet

FIGURE 67: SEA CONTAINER LENGTHS IN THE WORLD BY TEUS AND NO. CONTAINERS. DATA SOURCE: CI-CENSUS 2003 AND OWN CALCULATIONS TO INTERPRET 2010 SHARE.

Both in Europe and North America there are also containers a bit wider than the above mentioned ones, these are called pallet wide containers (PW, width ~ 2,5-2,6 m) and are able to accommodate more pallets per unit length due to a better dimension arrangement. Unfortunately these PW containers do not represent more than 4% of total containers and they are used mostly used on US-domestic, intra-EU transports and short sea shipping.

FIGURE 68: SEA CONTAINER TYPES AND WIDTHS IN THE WORLD BY NO. CONTAINERS. DATA SOURCE: CI-CENSUS 2003 AND CI-CENSUS 2008 (EXCERPT).

The sea containers' maximum gross weight indicates the maximum possible mass that the tare of the container plus the goods inside can reach without compromising the safety of it when handled. Obviously, not all the containers are carrying the maximum payload possible every time. They actually carry on average much less than this.

The average gross weight of a **loaded TEU** in European ports must be nowadays somewhat closer to **12,8t** (as calculated from statistic data ranked from lighter to heavier containers' weight in Rotterdam Port, Hamburg Port and Antwerp Port). If considering empty TEUs, then the averaged gross weight per TEU is around 11 t.

The average gross weight of the containers has increased by 1,5 t (per container) in the last ten years, this is containers become heavier and heavier. However, as containers become longer too, the weight increase per TEU may decrease or increase slightly, depending on which port is considered.

The following chart shows the weight increase per container and per TEU in the port of Antwerp. Apparently the port of Antwerp handles the heaviest containers (on average) in Europe, this is mainly motivated by the dominating export trade lane with heavier containers.

FIGURE 69: INCREASE OF GROSS TONNAGE IN ANTWERP PORT LOADED CONTAINERS SINCE 1995. DATA SOURCE: ANTWERP PORT STATISTICS 2011.

In Rotterdam the containers are lighter than average, around 12 gross tonnes per loaded TEU, and do not increase their weight that fast, having increased ca. 1,5 tonnes per container during the last decade.

This means that the average weight of the loaded TEU in Rotterdam has practically not changed during these last ten years (source: data analysis from Rotterdam port statistics) and even has decreased if looking at the long time series. In that sense, TEUs' net weight (loaded + empty) has decreased around 1 tone in the last 25 years.

FIGURE 70: ROTTERDAM PORT NET TONNES /TEU GRAPH. SOURCE: ROTTERDAM PORT STATISTICS

An explanation to this is that containers are transporting more and more finished and semi-finished goods that are being manufactured overseas, where labour costs are lower; Rotterdam traffic with Far East is very high.

20 ft containers are usually the heaviest containers on average and their weight is increasing about a tone every five years. Apparently this is happening because 20 ft containers are attracting more and more goods with high density, or goods packaged with higher density. Conversely, 40 ft and 45 ft containers seem to have reached an asymptotic value of ca. 11 tones per TEU.

FIGURE 71: INCREASE OF GROSS LOADED TEU TONNAGE IN ANTWERP AND ROTTERDAM PORTS. DATA SOURCE: ANTWERP AND ROTTERDAM PORT STATISTICS 2011.

The following trends become apparent:

Short Containers (20 ft)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease on share (could stabilize on ~20%*) • Increase on weight (with current limit on 30,5 t) • Disappearing of 30 ft units
Long Containers (mostly 40 ft)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase on share • Increase of HC type (Standard 40 ft almost replaced by 40 ft hi-cube around 2020) • TEU gross weight stabilized in 11 t (max. limit is 16,25 t/TEU) • Increase share of 45 ft (Market breakthrough depending on ocean carriers long term strategy)

FIGURE 72: TRENDS IN CONTAINERS

* 20% of 20 ft containers over total units is a stabilized share observed in US. intermodal domestic transportation market and in German railways.

Assuming these trends the envisaged share on container lengths for 2020 could look as follows:

FIGURE 73: FORECAST OF SEA CONTAINER LENGTHS SHARE IN THE WORLD BY TEUS AND NO. CONTAINERS

The averaged weights of the containers could stagnate around:

13 tones per loaded TEU in 2020.

This figure is conservative, it implies that all 20 ft container are weighting 30,5 t, which is improbable since there are many trade lanes utilizing 20 ft containers for light goods too, so the averaged TEU gross weight could be somewhat lower, around 12,5 t. If 40 and 45 ft containers would reach the maximum possible weight (32,5 t) too, then the gross weight of the loaded TEU in 2020 would be 17,6 t. In this case all containers would be carrying always the maximum payload without exception, which is very improbable.

Empty containers represent approximately 20% of all TEUs and 16% of all containers (Eurostat 2011). This means that the average gross weight of the TEU is around 2 tonnes lower than the loaded TEU.

Another interesting question is the weight distribution in a typical container sample. There are some reiterating container weight distributions that respond to different trade lanes.

Up to this point becomes necessary to make another division of hinterland container traffic, namely:

import container traffic vs. export container traffic

Basically, import containers in Europe are lighter than export containers. A rough explanation of this fact is that nowadays many import containers come from Far East (mainly China) and carry mostly light consumer goods for European markets, whereas export containers may carry a lower proportion of consumer goods and more chemicals, fertilizers, metal products, waste paper, and machines for export, which makes them heavier.

The following simplified charts provide an Idea of weights and proportions of loaded 20 ft and 40 ft containers in different trade lanes observed in European key ports.

FIGURE 74: LOADED SEA CONTAINER LENGTHS AND GROSS WEIGHTS PER TRADE LANE IN HAMBURG AND ROTTERDAM. SOURCE DATA: 2011 EUROGATE AND EUROMAX TERMINAL DATA ADJUSTED WITH ANNUAL EUROSTAT DATA.

The main distinguishable attribute of these charts, and this can be said for the whole EU too, is that the trade balance is negative (there is more importation than exportation). This entails an endemic empty container accumulation in Europe.

This empty accumulation generates a derived traffic of empty container repositioning that follows alternative and indirect paths, e.g. using empty container depots. The depots are scattered around the ports and all over the European consumption areas, hence, the empty repositioning traffic is quite difficult to predict and to simulate. On the other hand, loaded container traffic follows the commerce paths and generates dedicated trains; in case of these trains having empty spaces on wagons they can serve as reposition vehicles.

Not all important European container ports have negative trade balance; contrariwise the Antwerp container port trade balance is positive, which means that there is more exportation than importation. This causes that there containers are heavier on average.

FIGURE 75: LOADED SEA CONTAINER LENGTHS PER TRADE LANE IN ANTWERP AND IN EU27 PORTS. DATA SOURCE: 2011 EUROSTAT. (NOTE: IN ANTWERP AVERAGE GROSS WEIGHT OF LOADED 20 FT IS 21 T, AVERAGED LOADED 40 FT IS 22 T, ANTWERP PORT STATS).

Antwerp is an important export port for chemicals, steel products, iron, fertilizers, and flour among other things which can be categorized as heavy or very heavy goods. Therefore the use of 20 ft containers is more frequent than in other ports. In spite of this, the utilization of 40 ft containers still dominates and is increasing as the economies and industries become more and more technical and specialized.

The EU27 share on loaded containers is very similar to the share observed in the north range ports. The author forecasts a further growth on technical specialization and therefore an increase of trade on lighter products. This will require longer and volume-oriented containers, namely the 40 ft and 45 ft types.

An analysis of disaggregated container weight data is very revealing in terms of weight distribution on different container lengths and trade lanes. The following distribution patterns have been observed for the ports of the north range.

<i>Container type</i>	<i>Light ~6t/TEU</i>	<i>Medium light ~14 t/TEU</i>	<i>Heavy ~23t/TEU</i>	<i>Very heavy 30t/TEU</i>	<i>% in number of containers</i>	<i>Containerized goods description</i>
40 ft import	22%	8%	0%	0%	30%	Consumer goods, white goods, brown goods, textiles, clothes, machines and parts.
20 ft import	7%	5%	9%	3%	23%	Chemical base products, wood, cellulose, raw materials (bags), granulates, cereals, oilseeds, fuels.
40 ft export	11%	14%	0%	0%	25%	Machinery & equipment, steel products, fertilizers, chemical products, consumer goods, general scrap, paper waste.
20 ft export	3%	4%	11%	5%	22%	Steel semi-products, metal scrap, waste materials, animal feed, processed products (granulates).
Category	43%	30%	19%	8%	100%	

FIGURE 76: PERCENTAGE IN NO. CONTAINERS OF EUROPEAN RAIL TERMINALS IN ROTTERDAM AND HAMBURG. DATA SOURCE: EUROMAX AND EUROGATE RAIL TERMINALS 2011, ANTWERP PORT STATISTICS AND EUROSTAT.

The following graph provides valuable information on container weight distribution in European container ports.

FIGURE 77: GRAPH ABOUT WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION IN EUROPEAN CONTAINER TRAFFIC (IN NO. CONTAINERS AND GROSS WEIGHTS). SOURCE DATA: 2011 EUROGATE AND EUROMAX TERMINALS, ANTWERP PORT STATISTICS AND EUROSTAT.

Group 1: Light goods 43%

The dominating group of container traffic relates to light consumer goods. It contains all kinds of white goods (household and industry appliances), brown goods (electronic equipment), finished machines and parts thereof, textiles, clothing and other manufactured articles. They represent about 43% of total number of containers, of which 2/3 is imported and 1/3 exported. The average gross weight of such containers is 6 t/TEU, having a range between 3 and 10 t/TEU. The majority of these goods are packed in 40 ft containers, but they would fit better, or take better profit of space, in 45 or 53 ft containers. 20 ft containers carrying light goods are not employing optimally their payload capacity; in that way some of them may be carrying light goods in order to be repositioned from Asia to Europe.

Group 2: Medium-light goods 30%

The second largest group is the one categorized as medium-light goods. In Europe this group is represented mainly by export containers, principally 40 ft containers. The average gross weight per TEU is 14 t (range 10 to 17 t/TEU), which means that 40 ft containers are carrying almost their full payload capacity. The exported goods are mainly finished and semi-finished products, heavy machinery, wood base products, packed chemical products and fertilizers, heavier consumer products (brown goods, semi-processed food, beverages), plastic scrap and paper waste among others. Here 40 ft containers are employed more efficiently in respect to volume and payload capacity utilization, being 45 ft containers also very interesting for these applications. 20 ft containers may be used for the heavier products, e.g. bagged granulated chemicals.

Group 3: Heavy goods 19%

The third group represents less than 1/5 of the total number of loaded containers handled in the analysed European ports. The typical goods in this group may be chemical products or semi-products (in barrels, bags or other packages), non-ferrous scrap, flour and other processed grains, animal feed, processed minerals and other basic products as chemical basic materials. Depending on which port is considered the share import-export may be different, then in Antwerp the trade balance is positive, while in Hamburg and Rotterdam is slightly negative (more imports than exports); in the whole EU27 the balance of these kinds of goods could be assumed positive. The average gross weight is 23 t/TEU, with a range between 18 and 26 t/TEU. In principle the 30 ft container would offer a better payload/volume relation, however this unit is in clear disuse in deep sea transportation although is still widely employed in European domestic transportation as are 25-30 ft swap bodies, domestic bulk containers, silo and tank containers.

Group 4: Very-heavy goods 8%

This small group of containers carries the heaviest-possible-containerisable goods. These may be steel products, metal scrap, granulates, chemical liquids in barrels, oil seeds and other heavy waste materials. The average gross weight is 29 t/TEU (ranging from 26 to 30,5 t/TEU), which indicates that the containers are almost at their full payload capacity, with density close to 1 t/m³ (water density). In this case, the utilization of 20 ft containers is completely justified. The share between export and import containers may vary depending on the considered port, then so in Antwerp the share of export containers is higher than import, contrariwise in Hamburg and Rotterdam there are more heavy 20 ft containers of import than of export. Apparently in the whole EU27 there is more export than import of this kind of containers.

5.2.2. CONTINENTAL TRAFFIC

This kind of traffic has its origin basically in the EU-internal trade.

In continental traffic the assortment of loading units is much more diverse than in hinterland traffic because the units do not have to follow the deep-sea container ship dimension arrangement standards.

The most common units are:

- Semitrailers.
- Swap-Bodies.
- Tank and silo containers.
- Other domestic containers including 30 ft and 45 ft containers and pallet wide containers.
- 20 and 40 ft ISO maritime containers, although these are not typical continental units they may be found in continental trains as well.

The following table gives an overview of the principal characteristics of the standard intermodal loading units employed in Europe. There are also many other, non-standard units used for specific commodities or by specific shippers. Source [ICF]

Intermodal Loading Unit Name/Description:	Exterior						Interior								Pallets		Leeway		Stacking	Top-lift	Marine	Weight				
	Length mm	Width mm	Height mm	Length ft	Width ft	Height ft	Length mm	Width mm	Height mm	Length ft	Width ft	Height ft	Volume m ³	Floorspace m ²	Euro 8 x 1.2	UK 1 x 1.2	Euro Pallets width length	No. boxes	Yes/No	Yes/No	Gross	Tare	Payload			
ISO 1CC 20	6,058	2,438	2,591	19.9	8.0	8.5	5,893	2,330	2,392	19.3	7.6	7.8	32.8	1,160	13.7	147.8	11	10	330	293	7	Yes	Yes	30.5	2.2	28.3
ISO 1CC 20	6,096	2,438	2,591	20.0	8.0	8.5	5,931	2,350	2,392	19.5	7.7	7.8	33.3	1,177	13.9	150.0	11	10	330	293	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	2.2	31.8
ISO 1BB 30	9,144	2,438	2,591	30.0	8.0	8.5	8,979	2,330	2,392	29.5	7.6	7.8	50.0	1,767	20.9	225.2	18	15	330	379	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	3.1	30.9
ISO 1AA 40	12,192	2,438	2,591	40.0	8.0	8.5	12,027	2,330	2,392	39.5	7.6	7.8	67.0	2,367	28.0	301.6	25	22	330	27	7	Yes	Yes	30.5	3.7	26.8
ISO 1AAA 40	12,192	2,438	2,896	40.0	8.0	9.5	12,039	2,352	2,698	39.5	7.7	8.9	76.4	2,695	28.3	304.5	25	22	352	39	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	3.9	30.1
ISO 2CC	7,430	2,591	2,591	24.4	8.5	8.5	7,265	2,502	2,400	23.8	8.2	7.9	43.6	1,541	18.2	195.6	18	14	102	65	7	Yes	No			
ISO 2CCC	7,430	2,591	2,896	24.4	8.5	9.5	7,265	2,502	2,705	23.8	8.2	8.9	49.2	1,736	18.2	195.6	18	14	102	65	7	Yes	No			
ISO 2AA	14,900	2,591	2,591	48.9	8.5	8.5	14,735	2,502	2,400	48.3	8.2	7.9	88.5	3,125	36.9	396.8	36	28	102	335	7	Yes	No			
ISO 2AAA	14,900	2,591	2,896	48.9	8.5	9.5	14,735	2,502	2,705	48.3	8.2	8.9	99.7	3,522	36.9	396.8	36	28	102	335	7	Yes	No			
Maritime 45 HC	13,716	2,438	2,896	45.0	8.0	9.5	13,551	2,350	2,705	44.5	7.7	8.9	86.1	3,041	31.8	342.7	27	24	350	351	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	4.5	29.5
Maritime PW 20 HC	6,080	2,470	2,896	19.9	8.1	9.5	5,910	2,420	2,700	19.4	7.9	8.9	38.6	1,364	14.3	153.9	14	10	20	310	7	Yes	Yes	30.5	2.9	27.6
Maritime PW 40 HC	12,192	2,500	2,896	40.0	8.2	8.5	12,080	2,440	2,700	39.6	7.9	7.9	79.6	2,469	29.5	313.5	30	24	40	80	7	Yes	Yes	35.0	4.2	30.8
Maritime PW 45 side-curtain	13,716	2,500	2,591	45.0	8.2	8.5	13,575	2,440	2,400	44.5	7.9	7.9	79.5	2,774	33.1	352.3	33	26	40	375	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	3.8	30.2
Maritime PW 45 chamfered side	13,716	2,500	2,591	45.0	8.2	8.5	13,575	2,440	2,400	44.5	7.9	7.9	79.5	2,774	33.1	352.3	33	26	40	375	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	3.8	30.2
Maritime PW 45 HC	13,716	2,500	2,896	45.0	8.2	9.5	13,575	2,440	2,700	44.5	7.9	8.9	89.4	3,127	33.1	352.3	33	26	40	375	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	4.5	29.5
Maritime PW 45 chamfered HC	13,716	2,500	2,896	45.0	8.2	9.5	13,575	2,440	2,700	44.5	7.9	8.9	89.4	3,127	33.1	352.3	33	26	40	375	7	Yes	Yes	34.0	4.5	29.5
Swap Body C715	7,150	2,500	2,670	23.5	8.2	8.8	7,015	2,440	2,479	23.0	8.0	8.1	42.4	1,498	17.1	184.2	16	14	40	615	1	Some	No	20.0	2.9	17.1
Swap Body C715	7,150	2,550	2,769	23.5	8.4	9.1	7,015	2,460	2,526	23.0	8.1	8.3	43.6	1,539	17.3	185.8	16	14	60	615	1	No	No	16.0	2.7	13.3
Swap Body C745	7,450	2,500	2,670	24.4	8.2	8.8	7,315	2,440	2,479	24.0	8.0	8.1	44.2	1,563	17.8	192.1	18	14	40	115	1	No	No	16.0	3.0	13.0
Swap Body C745	7,450	2,550	2,769	24.4	8.4	9.1	7,315	2,460	2,526	24.0	8.1	8.3	45.5	1,605	18.0	193.7	18	14	60	115	1	No	No	24.0	2.7	21.3
Swap Body C782	7,820	2,500	2,670	25.7	8.2	8.8	7,685	2,440	2,479	25.2	8.0	8.1	46.5	1,642	18.8	201.8	18	14	40	485	1	No	No	20.0	3.2	16.8
Swap Body C782	7,820	2,550	2,769	25.7	8.4	9.1	7,685	2,460	2,526	25.2	8.1	8.3	47.8	1,686	18.9	203.5	18	14	60	485	1	No	No	30.0	2.8	27.2
Swap Body A1219	12,192	2,500	2,703	40.0	8.2	8.9	12,057	2,440	2,512	39.6	8.0	8.2	73.9	2,610	29.4	316.7	30	24	40	57	1	No	No	30.5	4.0	26.5
Swap Body A1250	12,500	2,500	2,670	41.0	8.2	8.8	12,365	2,440	2,479	40.6	8.0	8.1	74.8	2,641	30.2	324.8	30	24	40	365	1	No	No	34.0	4.2	29.8
Swap Body A1360 - Ro-Ro	13,600	2,500	2,670	44.6	8.2	8.8	13,465	2,440	2,479	44.2	8.0	8.1	81.4	2,876	32.9	353.6	33	26	40	265	3	Yes	No	34.0	4.8	29.2
Swap Body A1360	13,600	2,500	2,703	44.6	8.2	8.9	13,465	2,440	2,512	44.2	8.0	8.2	82.5	2,915	32.9	353.6	33	26	40	265	1	No	No	34.0	4.6	29.4
UTI-NORM Short ILU	7,450	2,550	2,900	24.4	8.4	9.5	7,285	2,460	2,709	23.9	8.1	8.9	48.5	1,714	17.9	192.9	18	14	60	85	4	Yes	No	24.0	2.7	21.3
UTI-NORM Long ILU	13,600	2,550	2,900	44.6	8.4	9.5	13,435	2,460	2,709	44.1	8.1	8.9	89.5	3,162	33.1	355.7	33	26	60	235	4	Yes	No	34.0	4.2	28.0

The **semitrailer** segment has experienced an important growth during these last years. The consulted statistics depict the following situation.

Semitrailer vs. container growth (in TEUs)

FIGURE 78: CONTAINER TRANSPORT VS. SEMITRAILER TRANSPORT IN EU27 (IN TEUS). SOURCE DATA: 2011 EUROSTAT.

Indeed, semitrailer transport has more than doubled in the last decade, going from a modest representation of 6% of total intermodal transports in 2004 to about 10% in 2010, measured in TEUs, being a semitrailer equivalent to 2 TEUs.

Semitrailers are not transported in all countries equally, there are countries, especially the Nordic Countries, where the transportation of semitrailers has been, and it is nowadays, very important. The following ranked list depicts the importance of semitrailer transport in European countries.

Percentage of semitrailer transport over total intermodal transports.

Sweden	Denmark	Switzerland	Norway	Finland	Italy	Austria	Germany	France	Hungary
31%	30%	16%	16%	16%	16%	14%	12%	7%	6%

FIGURE 79: PERCENTAGE OF SEMITRAILER TRANSPORT OVER TOTAL INTERMODAL TRANSPORTS. SOURCE EUROSTAT, MEASURED IN TEUS

As expected, the semitrailer transport is more present in those countries where the loading gauges, in this case intermodal gauges, are gentler, namely Sweden, Denmark, Finland, Austria and Germany.

The necessary intermodal gauge to transport standard semitrailers on standard pocket wagons is P70/P400, being this gauge large enough to allow 4 m tall semitrailers transportation. By smaller intermodal gauges, either the semitrailers have to be shorter in height or the pocket level has to be lower.

There are exceptional lines where special actions need to be taken in order to fit 4 m standard semitrailers in smaller gauges. To name one example, the gauge GB1 (upper part) combined with a special gauge G13 (under part) allows the transportation of standard semitrailers with suspensions deflated and loaded on pocket wagons with pocket height of only 22 cm above the top of the rail. This case is happening between Luxemburg and Perpignan and employs the technology Modalohr. This system enables the transportation of all kind of semitrailers, being these craneable or not. However it requires especial and expensive terminals.

Then so, there are two important points to bear in mind when dealing with semitrailers for intermodal transport:

1. The immense majority of European semitrailers cannot be lifted by an ordinary intermodal crane. To address this problem the technologies Cargobeamer, Modalohr, ISU, and Megaswing among others are available.
2. A craneable semitrailer is nowadays equivalent in price, life cycle costs and payload capacity to a non-craneable one. As road fleet is replaced quite frequently it can be assumed that in a future, and if necessary, an important part of the semitrailer fleet could be craneable without major investment.
3. Horizontal handling of semitrailers tend to lose its economic advantages by longer distances of transportation as the handling costs lose weight in total transport costs.
4. There are many important railway lines in Europe which loading gauges do not allow the transportation of standard 4 m tall semitrailers. This affects basically the Mediterranean countries; apparently the solution is a loading gauge extension.

In most of the European countries the maximum allowed weight of a full road vehicle in intermodal operation is 44 t. This means that a semitrailer could weigh up to 39 t (considering min. 5 tones of the tractor), which is very close to the technically possible gross weight of a semitrailer. However this maximum weight is far away from what it is actually the averaged weight of semitrailers transported by rail, which is around 27 t (Eurostat). And it looks that this average weight tends to decrease.

The following graph depicts the evolution of the semitrailer weight in German and Swedish railways. It considers only loaded semitrailers, the empty transport of semitrailers by rail is quite rare.

Semitrailer weight vs. semitrailer output in Sweden

Semitrailer weight vs. semitrailer output in Germany

FIGURE 80: SEMITRAILER WEIGHT VS. SEMITRAILER RAILWAY TRANSPORT IN SWEDEN AND IN GERMANY. SOURCE DATA: 2011 EUROSTAT AND DESTATIS.

Apparently the averaged weight of semitrailers in railway transportation tends to decrease when the transportation output increases, and vice versa. A reasonable explanation to that

phenomenon is that when conjuncture is favourable, railways are able to attract larger consignments that may contain lighter goods, reducing by this the averaged semitrailer weight. Conversely, during the recessions many goods may go back to road, remaining by railways majorly the heavy ones. This phenomenon is also observed in overall freight trains when looking at the evolution of averaged train weight.

The freight railways have the competitive advantage to transport heavier semitrailers, up to 39 t, and apparently semitrailers transported on rails are somewhat heavier than the semitrailers going on pure road transport. The maximum allowed vehicle weight for intermodal transports is 44 t, four tones more than pure road vehicles (40 t).

The road-only semitrailers have also decreased their averaged weight in the last decade; this has been motivated by the increase of the light transport segment. The next figure portrays the evolution of semitrailer net weight (payload) in the EU27 during the last 12 years (empty transports included).

FIGURE 81: NET WEIGHT EVOLUTION IN EUROPEAN SEMITRAILERS ON ROAD TRANSPORTATION. DATA SOURCE: 2011 EUROSTAT, VEHICLE COMBINATION TRACTOR 2-WHEEL + 3-WHEEL SEMITRAILER.

Long distance semitrailers are doing around 12% of the kilometres empty (Eurostat 2011), which means that:

The average gross weight of a loaded semitrailer in Europe in 2010 is 27t.

(Calculated as $17,91 \times 1,12 = 20$ t; plus average deadweight of a 3-wheel semitrailer, $20 + 7 = 27$ t)

By looking at the average weight evolution of semitrailers it can be interpreted that in the following years their average gross weight will somewhat decrease and oscillate between 27 and 26 tones.

Apart of the average gross weight, it is also very important to look at the distribution of semitrailer weights, the following chart introduces a supposition on how this distribution might be.

FIGURE 82: LOADED SEMITRAILER GROSS WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION IN EUROPE. (OWN INTERPRETATION BASED ON GOODS' WEIGHT SEGMENTATION OBSERVED IN CONTAINERIZED TRAFFIC, KEEPING AVERAGED GROSS WEIGHT OF 27 T AND MAX GOODS' DENSITY OF 0,33 T/M3, SEMITRAILER MAX DENSITY).

This graph respects the averaged gross weight of semitrailers (27 t) and introduces 4 categories of semitrailer weight, namely:

- 1 light semitrailers (e.g. consumer goods, white & brown goods, food and beverages, grouped, palletized and general cargo) 46%
- 2 medium light semitrailers (e.g. machines and parts) 12%
- 3 medium heavy semitrailers (e.g. chemicals, oil products) 24% and
- 4 heavy semitrailers (e.g. cereals, steel coils) 18%.

This distribution has been obtained after analysing the Eurostat data concerning groups of goods transported by road (Eurostat) and weights thereof. It has been observed that they have very similar weight distribution as the containerized cargo. A supposition has been made on how the containerized goods would be transported in semitrailers obtaining the depicted distribution. The averaged values have been validated with statistical results of semitrailers

weight by group of goods transported by road, and the average gross weight of loaded semitrailers (27t); Main data sources have been Eurostat, Destatis (DE) and ISU. Results have been cross-checked with statistical data of UIRR on semitrailers transport.

It is important to note that lighter goods tend to be transported longer distances; the graph on next page gives an idea of how far is transported every kind of good. The graph corresponds to the international road transports in Spain, being Spain a country where the modal share is almost absolutely dominated by road, especially in international transport.

Then so, consumer goods, say white goods, brown goods, foodstuffs, machines as well as semi-finished manufactured goods increase their relative share on semitrailer transports in longer distances of transportation, whereas heavier goods as minerals, building materials, oils and fertilizers dominate on shorter distances.

FIGURE 83: INTERNATIONAL TRANSPORTS BY ROAD IN SPAIN, DISTANCE CLASSES VS. GOODS CLASSIFICATION. DATA SOURCE: SPANISH MINISTERIO DE FOMENTO 2011.

Furthermore, the longer the distance of transportation the more suitable it is for rail or combined transport, which means that in a foreseeable future, when more semitrailers can be carried by rail, these transports may become lighter, this is, around 21 t on average. In spite of this, to be conservative, this analysis will consider the whole spectrum of semitrailers' weight to determine a loading pattern (averaged weight 27 t).

Then, the probability on cases of semitrailers goods' segmentation could look as follows:

Semitrailer gross weight	10 t	11 t	12 t	13 t	14 t	15 t	16 t	17 t	18 t	19 t	20 t	21 t	22 t	23 t	24 t	25 t
Probability	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	1,1%	2,0%	2,8%	2,9%	3,6%	3,8%	3,7%	3,7%	4,7%	3,8%	4,1%	3,0%	3,7%
Semitrailer gross weight	26 t	27 t	28 t	29 t	30 t	31 t	32 t	33 t	34 t	35 t	36 t	37 t	38 t	39 t	40 t	41 t
Probability	2,6%	3,1%	3,9%	3,6%	3,9%	4,3%	5,3%	5,4%	3,7%	3,4%	3,9%	5,3%	4,3%	3,3%	0,6%	0,1%

FIGURE 84:PROBABILITY OF SEMITRAILER WEIGHT.

Another different question is to know how these semitrailers are being distributed on trains. The following questions arise:

- What is the probability that a train carries only light semitrailers?
- What is the probability that a train carries only heavy semitrailers?
- Is it typical that a train carries a combination of different semitrailer weights? How often? Which are the most probable combinations?
- How often semitrailers coexist with other units (domestic containers) on trains?

To answer these questions properly it would be necessary to investigate the very reasons originating the transport of semitrailers, namely: the corridors, the goods segmentation, the logistics of combined transportation, the clients demand (e.g. if they have a dedicated train), the season, the weekday, the hour, etc. and compare it with the domestic container flows. In definitive, a quite complicated bottom-up analysis out of the scope of this project.

The top-down analysis on the other hand is the investigation of current transportation of semitrailers in a given sample of intermodal traffic. This analysis has been done with the data of a company and it has been employed to validate a hypothesis on semitrailer distribution on trains. The results of the top-down analysis are confidential, but the validation has proved the following distribution of cases.

The following 15 cases are obtained as probability combination of 4 groups of semitrailers, namely: 1 light, 2 medium light, 3 medium heavy and 4 heavy.

Then, the probability on cases of trains with semitrailers could look as follows:

Train with...	Only 1	Only 2	Only 3	Only 4	Mix 12	Mix 13	Mix 14	Mix 23	Mix 24	Mix 34	Mix 123	Mix 124	Mix 134	Mix 234	Mix 1234
Probability	6%	2%	3%	2%	7%	9%	8%	5%	4%	5%	10%	10%	11%	7%	13%
ST avgd. Weight (t)	20,4	27,7	32,2	37,6	22,0	24,5	25,2	30,7	33,5	34,5	25,0	25,7	27,2	33,0	27,2

FIGURE 85: SEMITRAILER AVERAGED WEIGHT PROBABILITY

This means for example that in 100 trains 13 would have onboard a combination of semitrailers of all groups with an averaged semitrailer gross weight of 27,2. Or, in 100 trains 2 would have only semitrailers of type 4 having an average gross weight of 37,7 t per semitrailer.

The remaining question is to know how often semitrailers are combined with other units on trains, or if contrariwise, semitrailers tend to travel alone.

Other continental units

In intermodal continental transportation the typical distribution of units may have this appearance:

FIGURE 86: CONTINENTAL INTERMODAL TRANSPORT IN EU27 IN % OF UNIT LENGTH EMPLOYED (ONLY LOADED UNITS). DATA SOURCE: COMBINATION OF DATA FROM EUROSTAT, DESTATIS AND UIRR STATISTICS; VALIDATED WITH THE DATA OF A BIG INTERMODAL OPERATOR. (IT DOES NOT INCLUDE 20 AND 40 FT SEA CONTAINERS)

The current trends indicate a strong growth and demand for semitrailers, in second place it comes the growth on long 45 ft domestic containers or bodies, in third place the 30 ft containers (mostly bulk containers, silos and tanks) for domestic transport, finally 26 ft containers (swap bodies and smaller tanks) are proportionally decreasing their share.

It seems that 30 ft containers are quite appropriate for bulk, in this case the optimal wagon for 30 ft containers would be the classic 60 ft container wagon.

The average gross tonnage of each length group looks as follows (it refers only to loaded units):

Unit length	< 26 ft (mostly tank containers and swap bodies)	26 to 35 ft (mostly 30 ft containers, and silo containers)	35 to 45 ft (mostly 45 ft containers)	semitrailers
Gross weight, <i>(years' average 2005-2010)</i>	16,3 t	29,3 t	18,3 t	27 t
Weight per TEU	<i>(/1,2)</i> 13,6 t	<i>(/1,5)</i> 19,5 t	<i>(/2,25)</i> 8,1 t	<i>(/2,25)</i> 12 t

FIGURE 87: DATA SOURCE: DESTATIS, EUROSTAT, UIRR

Nowadays it is typical to find all kinds of domestic units sharing surface on trains, in so doing it is common to see semitrailers together with short swap bodies, or tank containers, or 45 ft units loaded on the same train or even on the same wagon. This becomes even more typical considering the bundling of traffics happening on main relations, e.g. Germany-Italy shuttles. On the other hand, it is also possible, to find one-unit trains, for instance a train loaded only with semitrailers dedicated to a single client, for instance LKW Walter. In spite of this, the trend seems to point at more mixture of units on trains which requires an optimization of the wagon length and loading factor.

It is proposed to proceed with a categorization of units in order to approach the vast variability of loading cases.

The following simplified division designates 6 groups with averaged gross weights:

Codes: Length / length percentage / drawing / gross weight of loaded unit / percentage of category / category.

FIGURE 88: CATEGORIZATION OF CONTINENTAL UNITS

The 6 categories are:

Group 1a; Swap bodies

Typically these are 7,45m long boxes for the transportation of palletized cargo in lorry configurations of 3+2 axles, being these formed by a tractor with a box (3 axles) and a coupled trailer with 2 axles. These 7,45m swap bodies -there are also 7,82 m bodies- have legs to enable intermediate depot and horizontal transfer between road vehicles. They are usually bottom lifted. They carry usually light goods like consumer goods. Their maximal allowed gross weight is 16 t, with an average gross weight of 10 t.

FIGURE 89: SWAP BODY. DATA: DESTATIS, PHOTO: THE INTERMODAL CONTAINER WEB PAGE

Group 1b; Tank containers

Typically these units are represented by 20 ft, 7,15 m, 7,45 m and 7,82 m tank bodies. They carry all kind of liquids, also dangerous goods, chemicals, oil products, liquid foodstuffs, pressurized goods etc. Typically they have no legs and are top lifted like standard dry ISO containers. Their maximal gross weight is 34 t although due to the different densities of carried stuffs, their averaged weight is 24 t.

FIGURE 90: TANK CONTAINER. DATA: DESTATIS, PHOTO: THE INTERMODAL CONTAINER WEB PAGE

Group 2; 30 ft containers

These units are majorly 30 ft long and are employed for the transportation of dry bulk (silos and dry boxes) or for liquid bulk in tank configurations. The products carried are diverse and very similar to the ones of group 1b. 30 ft containers are also employed for the transportation of mineral products, waste materials and other loose cargo configurations. Maximal gross weight is around 35 t and their averaged loaded gross tonnage is 29 t. Trend indicates stabilization.

FIGURE 91: 30FT CONTAINER. DATA: DESTATIS, PHOTO: THE INTERMODAL CONTAINER WEB PAGE

FIGURE 92: 45FT BODY. DATA: DESTATIS, PHOTO: THE INTERMODAL CONTAINER WEB PAGE

Group 3; 45 ft bodies

Either as dry boxes or refrigerated vans or curtain siders, etc. the 45 ft unit is becoming quite popular in European railways. Most of them are employed to transport light goods (consumer goods). They are usually bottom-lifted but there are also some top-lifted ones. The trend indicates a further growth on these kind of units in detriment of shorter swap bodies (Group 1a). They are carried on semitrailer platforms taking full advantage of loading length and being compatible with European regulations. Typical averaged gross weight of a loaded unit is 18 t.

FIGURE 93: LIGHT SEMITRAILER. PHOTO: DYBAS

Group 4a; light semitrailers

The semitrailer transport has experienced an important growth during the last years, especially when it comes to the light segment. Nowadays almost 80% of the road transportations of semitrailers are volume oriented rather than weight oriented (Kögel Trailer GmbH & Co.KG) and this will be noticed in combined transportation too. In order to be loaded on pocket wagons, semitrailers have to be prepared for vertical lifting, unfortunately not all count with this feature (only 5%). Semitrailers have a max. gross weight of 39 t, light semitrailers weight 20 t on average. The trend indicates further growth of this segment.

FIGURE 94: HEAVY SEMITRAILER PHOTO: MODALOHR

Group 4b; heavy semitrailers

The heavy segment of semitrailers may be represented by cisterns, silos, semitrailers for coils and other metal products, bulk semitrailers and the like. These semitrailers use to run shorter distances than lighter semitrailers and therefore they may be not that interesting for railway transportation. In spite of this, as lorries in combined traffic may carry 4 tones more than regular ones, there is still a market for them in combined transportation. Typical averaged gross weight is 35 t.

The combination of these six categories yields 63 possible cases, they are listed here:

No.	Case	No.	Case	No.	Case	No.	Case
1	Only 1a	17	Mix24a	33	Mix1b24a	49	Mix1a234b
2	Only 1b	18	Mix24b	34	Mix1b24b	50	Mix1a24a4b
3	Only 2	19	Mix34a	35	Mix1b34a	51	Mix1a34a4b
4	Only 3	20	Mix34b	36	Mix1b34b	52	Mix1b234a
5	Only 4a	21	Mix4a4b	37	Mix 1b4a4b	53	Mix1b234b
6	Only 4b	22	Mix1a1b2	38	Mix234a	54	Mix1b24a4b
7	Mix1a1b	23	Mix1a1b3	39	Mix234b	55	Mix1b34a4b
8	Mix1a2	24	Mix1a1b4a	40	Mix24a4b	56	Mix234a4b
9	Mix1a3	25	Mix1a1b4b	41	Mix34a4b	57	Mix1a1b234a
10	Mix1a4a	26	Mix1a23	42	Mix1a1b23	58	Mix1a1b234b
11	Mix1a4b	27	Mix1a24a	43	Mix1a1b24a	59	Mix1a1b24a4b
12	Mix1b2	28	Mix1a24b	44	Mix1a1b24b	60	Mix1a1b34a4b
13	Mix1b3	29	Mix1a34a	45	Mix1a1b34a	61	Mix1a234a4b
14	Mix1b4a	30	Mix1a34b	46	Mix1a1b34b	62	Mix1b234a4b
15	Mix1b4b	31	Mix1a4a4b	47	Mix1a1b4a4b	63	Mix1a1b234a4b
16	Mix23	32	Mix1b23	48	Mix1a234a		

FIGURE 95: CASES ON CONTINENTAL TRANSPORT

Certainly, in the continental transportation it should be possible to define even more cases depending of the weight of the units; however this would elevate the study case analysis to an unpractical level.

To understand the wagon choice from a qualitative point of view some conceivable examples can be described:

- 1) It can happen for example that a client requires the transportation of only 30 ft bulk containers in one direction. For this, the utilisation of 60 ft wagons would be optimal; however the back trip of this service (considering that the 30 ft containers are not coming back empty) could have other load pattern, say 45 ft swap bodies, which would make the 60 ft wagons less profitable.
- 2) In small companies with only one kind of unit, or by big companies with a fixed and predictable client demand, the optimal wagon for the production could be clear. For example, a full truck load company moving only semitrailers back and forth between A and B may find the TWIN 106 ft for two semitrailers (also megatrailers) perfect (LKW Walter). Whereas for a company moving majorly long swap bodies (45 ft), the right wagon would be the articulated 90 ft.
- 3) For an intermodal operator consolidating different units from a multi-client network the optimal wagon is not clear; it depends on the relation and combination of units on each service/train. The more diverse the mix of units, the more unclear the right wagon or combination thereof, especially if considering that the mixture of units vary with the time. Apparently the mixture of wagons utilised for these cases is a combination of 60 ft wagons with articulated 104 ft (with and without pocket) together with small amount of articulated 90 ft and 4-axle wagons for one semitrailer. In some of the cases tough, this mixture of wagons would be determined from what is available rather from what is optimal, however it is important to bear this in mind for future wagon fleet renewal strategies.

5.2.3. INTERMODAL ROLLING STOCK

The typical intermodal wagon fleet distribution in Europe may look as follows:

FIGURE 96: STRUCTURE OF THE EUROPEAN INTERMODAL WAGON FLEET IN TEU CAPACITY. ROLLING HIGHWAY WAGONS ARE EXCLUDED. (OWN ELABORATION BASED ON DATA FROM DIOMIS REPORT, VEL-WAGON PROJECT AND PROSPECTS FROM INTERNAL KNOWLEDGE)

The most popular intermodal wagon is the 60' container wagon able to carry 3 TEU's in multiple loading schemas. This wagon is a universal wagon which versatility has been commended in many cases and for many users. It is able to transport 2 swap-bodies as well up to 7,82 m long, if having the right pin or twist-lock positions. Its market price is between 60.000€-70.000€ (2008)

Two-axle container wagons, can carry 2 TEU's within limitations on weight (max. payload 28 t). Certain longer designs are also able to carry as well 2 swap-bodies, however 40'-container wagons are only able to carry maximum one single swap body (if they are equipped for it). Market price of a standard two-axle container wagon is around 50.000€ (2008). They are in clear disuse.

Articulated wagons, pocket wagons, and low floor wagons stand for the remaining half of the total wagon capacity. A huge number of different designs address different markets and customer needs. In many cases these wagons are designed for specific infrastructure restrains, for example in England where low floor wagons are widely employed, due to the narrow loading gauge. The cost per wagon is difficult to approximate due to the variability, but can be roughly estimated to be between 18.000€-20.000€ per TEU.

Intermodal wagons are conceived for the transportation of few different kinds of intermodal loading units, mainly ISO-containers and swap bodies, and partly also Semitrailers. The majority of intermodal consignments though are ISO-container shaped due to the huge amount of traffic of deep sea nature participating in combined transportation.

The wagons weight efficiency can be as well visualized with a XY diagram, with the payload/tare-ratio on the abscissa and the TEU/tare-ratio on the ordinate. By looking at the graph, wagons follow a trend line that can be employed to characterize their condition as volume-oriented or weight-oriented. It can be noted that American and Australian wagons can carry double-stacked intermodal units, which place them in a comparative advantageous position.

FIGURE 97: INTERMODAL WAGON COMPARISON. GREEN: EUROPEAN WAGONS, RED: AUSTRALIAN WAGONS, BLUE: AMERICAN WAGONS. SQUARE: ARTICULATED WAGONS, TRIANGLE: BOGIE NON-ARTICULATED WAGONS, DIAMOND: NON-BOGIE WAGONS

This analysis shows that the most modern intermodal wagons tend to align towards the area of light and efficient. The averaged maximal tonnage offered (per TEU) is around 20 tonnes.

The most common wagons for intermodal transportation are:

Sgns 60'

FIGURE 98: CONTAINER WAGON CLASS SGNS 60' (SOURCE: KOMBIMODEL)

It is a European wide employed wagon able to carry containers in different load configurations - until 3TEUs depending on loading schema- or two C-type Swap Bodies, or one A-Type Swap Body. It is a compromised solution between a volume-oriented and weight-oriented wagon. In spite of this advantage, its overall weight efficiency can be called into question if compared to other existing wagons. In the last times though, modifications in the design and construction procedures have brought about important reductions on tare weight –up to 2 tones by having lightened central beams (picture)- which has increased substantially its weight efficiency. Yet, an important logistic hindrance with these wagons in respect to maritime container flows is the empty spaces on trains if the proportion of 40's units its superior to the 20's, which happens very commonly.

Articulated wagons

FIGURE 99: SGRSS 80 FT (SOURCE:TATRAVAGONKA)

In articulated wagons the payload/tare rate ratio increases because of sharing a bogie –also called Jacob bogie- between two identical wagon frames. By this, wagons can be longer and have fewer axles. Furthermore the total train length usage can be increased by reducing the number of couplings, although this advantage is not very significant in short trains. The most popular wagon nowadays is the 80 ft wagon which is very demanded on the maritime segment. It has the capacity for 4 TEUs.

In continental transport there is a higher variability on types of units and that means that the wagon fleet is more diverse. Nowadays the intermodal wagon fleet dedicated to continental transport of a big intermodal company could look as follows.

Fleet for Continental Combined Transport

FIGURE 100: ESTIMATED FLEET IN % OF UNIT LENGTH DEDICATED TO CONTINENTAL INTERMODAL TRANSPORT. OWN INTERPRETATION BASED ON REPORTED INTERMODAL WAGON FLEET STOCKS OF DB CONTAINED ON WEBSITE DYBAS (NON-OFFICIAL), ARROWS INDICATE TREND (BASED ON RECENT ACQUISITIONS AND YEARS OF MANUFACTURE, ST MEANS WAGON FOR SEMITRAILERS).

Apparently, the sector is demanding more and more wagons for semitrailers, which are also able to transport a combination of swap bodies and containers alike. This multipurpose feature is important as regards as the “shuttleization” happening in intermodal transportation by which the companies intend to simplify their services by consolidating the consignments in fixed relations.

Shuttles have the advantage of maximizing the productivity of the wagons while decreasing shunting and personal costs; however they are sensitive to demand variations, which eventually could make them quite unproductive.

Intermodal companies may try to rationalize much of their combined traffic in shuttles, or at least the principal flows in order to avoid the complicated work of finding and allocating the optimal wagon for every single case. In so doing, former national companies tend to have more flexible wagon allocation while new entrants are more prone to deploy shuttles and direct trains.

A modern and popular wagon used nowadays in continental transportation is the articulated 106 ft for two semitrailers.

FIGURE 101: TWIN SDGGMRS(S) (AAE) AND SDGGMRS. SOURCE: TATRAVAGONKA

This wagon has capacity for two semitrailers and it is also able to transport diverse combinations of containers and swap bodies with different weights and lengths. The wagon has a tare of c.a. 35 t and it is able to carry in total around 100 t of payload, however due to the shared central bogie the practical payload is somewhat lower.

This wagon is the most modern solution to be found in the market for the transportation of semitrailers, it is also quite good at the transportation of swap bodies, 30 ft containers, tanks and 45 ft bodies. The wagon can be loaded with heavy units until the axles reach the allowed axle load (22,5 t), this can happen easily on the central bogie as it is shared by the two wagon halves.

In the following figure is presented a loading schema of a Twin wagon (source: Green Cargo), it is possible to see that it can carry up to 3 heavy short units of 25 t having still a left slot for a light unit of max. 12 t. The transportation of 4 heavy units would be impossible due to the axle load limitation on the central bogie.

The author opines that this kind of wagons would represent nowadays the better available solution for the continental intermodal transportation since it offers a good loading factor for many combinations of units.

FIGURE 102: EXCEL®-BASED LOADING SCHEMA FOR A TWIN WAGON. SOURCE: GREEN CARGO

A simulation has been run in order to know the amount of these wagons necessary to transport a given combination of units in continental transport.

5.3. CONCLUSIONS FOR THE INTERMODAL TRANSPORT

There is a manifest increase of utilization of longer units (longer than 8:30m, mostly 40 ft HC and 45 ft containers)

There is a decrease of the averaged gross weight of consignment

The averaged weights of the containers could stagnate around 13 tones per loaded TEU in 2020

Goods transported in containers can be classified in 4 groups: light goods (~6 t/TEU, 43%), medium light goods 14 t/TEU (~14 t/TEU, 30%), heavy goods (~23 t/TEU, 19%) and very heavy goods (~30 t/TEU, 8%).

The optimal wagon length for such combination of units is 80 ft. Hence, a popular wagon nowadays is the 6-axled 80 ft wagon; however this wagon may be over-dimensioned in terms of deadweight and axles for many transport cases.

Continental transport is participated mainly from semitrailers, swap bodies and tank, bulk and silo containers.

The semitrailer segment has experienced an important growth during these last years. The average gross weight of a loaded semitrailer is 27 t. Apparently, this weight is decreasing as semitrailers carry more and more volumetric goods.

A craneable semitrailer is nowadays equivalent in price, life cycle costs and payload capacity to a non-craneable one. As road fleet is replaced quite frequently it can be assumed that in a future, and if necessary, an important part of the semitrailer fleet could be craneable without major investment.

45 ft unit is quite common and is growing in share in continental transports.

The light goods in continental transportation tend to travel longer distances than the heavy goods. Hence, it is expected to see a decrease of the average TEU weight for continental intermodal trains.

6. PARTICULAR CASE ON TRAIN WEIGHT REDUCTION; LONGER WAGONS, VEL-WAGON

6.1. STATE OF THE ART IN LONG WAGONS

Non-articulated long wagons, say longer than 25 m, are present in North America. There, 93-foot long wagons (90 ft -27 m- loading length) can be employed for transporting two semitrailers of 45 ft. There are as well 90 ft long wagons (85 ft -26 m-loading length) with a payload of 102 t for the transportation of containers.

FIGURE 103: NORTH AMERICAN FLATCAR. SOURCE: G.TROCHE.

As a result of the very high allowed axle load - 32,4 t/axle - on North American tracks, the 85 ft cars can carry 25,5 t per TEU. This is about 2 t more per TEU than the standard wagon in Europe, the 60 ft wagon, and about 3 t less per TEU than the European articulated 80 ft wagon.

FIGURE 104: NORTH AMERICAN HEAVY DUTY 85 FT FLAT CAR. SOURCE: GREENBRIER.

However in North America the basis for the intermodal transportation has shifted from the above presented flatcars to the double stack cars, which make use of the tall loading gauge existing there to transport more containers per axle. Double stack cars have superior dimensions for the transportation of containers.

In the following figure is presented a heavy duty, stand-alone double stack car. It can transport multiple combinations of container lengths from 20 ft to 53 ft.

FIGURE 105: NORTH AMERICAN HEAVY DUTY DOUBLE STACK CAR. SOURCE: GREENBRIER.

The capacity of this car is 5,3 TEU (considering a 53 ft container equivalent to 2,65 TEUs) and the tare of the wagon is 23 t, hence the technical payload should be $32,5 \times 4 - 23 = 107$ t, which gives about **20 t/TEU**.

However typically, double stack cars are used in articulated multiple units, reducing by this the amount of necessary axles and hence reducing the averaged payload per well.

FIGURE 106: 5-UNIT DOUBLE STACK CAR. SOURCE: GREENBRIER.

Tare of the 5-unit combination is 53 t; technically max. gross load 390 t ($=32,5 \times 12$); theoretical max. payload 337 t; max. payload per well 67,4 t; capacity per well 4,65 TEUs (40 ft plus 53 ft); This yields **~14,5 tonnes per TEU** (17 t/TEU if considering only 4 TEUs per well). (Note: The manufacturer of the 5-unit double stack car declares an averaged load limit of only 124.700lbs per well which gives **only 10,7 t/TEU**)

Hence these multi-unit double stack cars would not be appropriate for 20' containers, especially if heavy. However container techniques in the U.S. favour the utilisation of longer units, which are more appropriate for lower density commodities. The domestic unit of 53 ft long and 8,5 ft wide represents an important gain in productivity of North American intermodal logistics.

FIGURE 107: CONTAINER TECHNIQUES IN NORTH AMERICAN INTERMODAL TRANSPORTATION, 2007. DATA SOURCE: INTERMODAL ASSOCIATION OF NORTH AMERICA.

In Europe the share of 20 ft containers is similar and there is an important utilisation of short swap bodies (>20 ft to 25 ft). However the trend is to employ more and more longer units, namely 40 ft and recently 45 ft.

FIGURE 108: CONTAINER TECHNIQUES IN GERMAN INTERMODAL TRANSPORTATION, 2010 (ARROWS INDICATE TREND). DATA SOURCE: DESTATIS 2011.

In Australia and CIS countries longer wagons, >25m, are widely utilized, for instance the CQMY and 13-7024 respectively.

FIGURE 109: 13-7024 FLAT CAR, JSC KRYUKOV CAR BUILDING WORKS, 25,6 M, TARE 22,3 T. SOURCE: HEKMAT GMBH.

[Hilmola 2] concludes in his 2008 report “Railway Wagon Market Analysis and New Multi-Purpose Wagon Solution for Freight Transports –Finnish Manufacturing Perspective” with:

Currently forty foot containers are favoured over twenty foot ones – this should be driving factor in freight wagons. In one side it favours really long wagons, but on the other hand wagons having length of one 40 foot container. Wagons being stuck in between seem to hold considerable disadvantage.

(The author analyses in the report mainly non-articulated platforms)

In Finland the wagon Sdggngqss-w has a loading length of 24,8 m and a payload of 68,5 t (25 t/axle) it can be employed for transporting trucks and semitrailers (similarly to North American flatcars).

FIGURE 110: SDGGNQSS-W, 26M, TARE 31,2T. PICTURE SOURCE: VAUNUT.ORG.

The SAIL project, Semitrailers in advanced intermodal logistics, of year 2000, had a preliminary discussion on the ideal length and capacity for an intermodal wagon for semitrailers. In principle a wagon concept should accommodate two semitrailers over 4 axles. However the payload of a 4-axle wagon would not be enough for two loaded semitrailers - 36 t each -, hence an articulated version was preferred. Nowadays an increase of axle load to 25 t would allow the more compact 2-semitrailers-in-4-axle solution.

Swedish State Railways (SJ) in the 70's procured a longer wagon able to carry 4x20 ft containers or two semitrailers. Its payload was quite low, only 52 t, line class C (21 t/axle).

FIGURE 111: SJF 636.1, 26M LONG, TARE 28T. PICTURE SOURCE: STINSENSFORUM.SE, USER BJ.

In mid of the 1990s Hupac and Talbot developed a long wagon with a loading length of 22,6 m that is able to transport different combinations of containers and swap bodies (up to 3x C745) with a maximum payload of 68 t. However this wagon is not long enough to transport 2x40 ft containers.

FIGURE 112: SGGNS 73', 23,9 M, TARE 22 T. PICTURE SOURCE: GOEDERENWAGENS.NL.

Longer-than-25 m wagons do exist in Europe; however they are not typically employed for intermodal transportation.

An example is the Rbns with 25 m of loading length employed for the transportation of long cargo units, e.g. rails, steel profiles, pipes etc. Payload is 63 t, loading height (without wood floor) is 1,25 m (7,5 cm more than the UIC intermodal standard). This wagon is hump-able and has a minimum turning radius of 75 m.

FIGURE 113: RBNS, 26,3 M, TARE 27 T . PICTURE SOURCE: DYBAS.

Another example was the Habbiks 340" produced in the 1970s for the car manufacturer Opel. It had 22,4 m of loading length and a very low payload of only 25 t, the volume was 195 m³, hence the optimal cargo density was 0,13 t/m³ (air freight levels). The wheel diameter was small too, 680 mm.

FIGURE 114: HABBIKS 340, 25,2M, TARE 31T. PICTURE SOURCE: DYBAS.

Recently a Sggns 80 ft has been manufactured by the Polish company TABOR M. Dybowski S.J.

Payload is 66 t and it can transport 2x40 ft in its 24,9 m of loading length. It has interoperable loading gauge UIC505-1 (G1).

FIGURE 115: SGGNS 80 FT FLATCAR, 25,9 M, TARE 24 T. SOURCE: TABOR M. DYBOWSKI S.J.

The shipping company Ignazio Messina & C. S.p.A. utilizes purpose built 80 ft long container wagons.

FIGURE 116: SGGNS 80 FT. SOURCE: TRENOMANIA.ORG, USER MARCOCLAUDIO.

FIGURE 117: SGG80 FT, LOADING LENGTH 24,6 M, TARE 21,4 T. SOURCE: IGNAZIO MESSINA & C.S.P.A.

In 2008 Diomis project issued a report on wagons for intermodal transportation entitled “Assessing new technologies in the wagon field”. It analyzed the actual wagon fleet for combined transportation and looked at aspects of efficiency, more in concrete:

- Utilisation of loading units for combined transportation
- Wagon types
- Utilisation of train length
- Utilisation of wagon weight and total train weight
- Train speed
- Wagon handling in terminals

The report concludes with recommendations on wagon lengths and types:

- *Short single wagon for heavy tank swap bodies*
- *60' and 80' wagon for maritime traffic (80' = 4x20')*
- *104' and 90' wagon for continental traffic (90' = 2 x 45')*
- *Articulated wagon having a good length and weight balance*
- *Pocket wagon for the growing demand of semi-trailers*

Unfortunately the study does not present any statistical figure on averaged container weights nor distribution thereof nor trend thereof; rather it works with maximum possible container weights to discuss about the optimal wagon weight performance. Apparently, to have wagons optimized for the heaviest possible combination of containers (e.g. heavy 20 ft) is a criterion of usability for wagon users.

An interesting point of this report was the discussion about weight of a CT train. It works with a value of 1500 t for a CT train running at 100 km/h on an easy topography. If considering a 600 m long train with capacity up to 90 TEUs, this would entail about 900 t of payload per train, which means about 10 t per TEU. To be able to transport for instance 25 t/TEU - as articulated 80 ft wagons can do - the train should be able to carry 2800 t (or to be much shorter), which is a quite high value for a CT train.

Hence apparently, CT wagons are being designed for much more payload than averaged CT trains.

With regards to operating speeds, due to the high congestion on many mainlines and the prevalence of higher-speed passenger trains during daytime, there is an increasing need for freight trains to travel at higher speeds than 100 km/h – as is common today – to be able to increase the number of freight train paths by slotting more freight trains between passenger trains during daytime.

6.2. VEL-WAGON

VEL-Wagon is a European research project that investigates the properties of long wagons for the intermodal transportation. It postulates that longer uninterrupted surfaces increase the loading factors of trains and take better advantage of the available capacity, in terms of weight, length and energy consumption.

The basic idea is displayed as follows.

Longer loading surfaces without interruption, as well as more capable platforms with higher axle loads and with lower loading heights to increase the capacity of the freight railway transportation

VEL-Wagon also intends to design a specific wagon that achieves a compromised solution between feasibility, market attractiveness and technical development.

VEL-Wagon stands for: Versatile, efficient and Longer wagon for the intermodal transportation.

After many operational simulations of intermodal traffic as well as thorough structural calculations and 3d dynamic simulations, a compromised solution for the wagon design was obtained.

FIGURE 118: VEL-WAGON DESIGN IN APRIL 2012, SOURCE: TATRAVAGONKA

The wagon would have a tare of roughly 21 t and a loading length of 80 ft for 4 TEUs.

The offered payload capacity (considering an axle load of 22,5 t) would be 17,25 t/TEU.

A model simulation of the performance of the wagon under given traffic paradigms was done by the author. It is presented as follows.

6.2.1. SIMULATION ON MARITIME TRAFFIC

The maritime-container trains may have two principal directions, namely:

A) Import trains

Trains loaded with import containers departing from the port terminals with destination to inland terminals or hub or gateway terminals, e.g. from Voltri (Genoa Port) to Busto Arsizio (Milan area).

B) Export trains

Trains loaded with export containers departing from inland or hub terminals or gateway terminals with destination to port terminals, e.g. from Madrid to Valencia port.

There would be also trains loaded with import containers departing from inland or hub or gateway terminals with destination to inland or hub or gateway terminals, e.g. from Duisburg to Munich, and back with export containers. The mix of import and export containers in the same train is assumed to be very rare.

The criteria to load the trains with containers may depend on a high number of variables, namely: trade lane, destination, operator production system and productivity, client(s) consignment size and time deadlines, clients' train exclusivity, customs procedures and requirements, opening hours, wagon availability, conjuncture, season, day, hour, etc. This makes the possible cases on train loading schemes just as large as the amount of container trains in Europe. Due to the impossibility to analyse such huge sample of cases, we will work on probabilities based on container traffic observed in port rail terminals as described above. Hence, the following 30 cases result from the combination between the following variables:

- Goods groups 1 to 4 (light to very heavy) and
- Two directions (import and export).

Case	Combination (1-4)	Trade lane	Case	Combination (1-4)	Trade lane
1	Mix 1234	Import	16	Mix 14	Export
2	Mix 1234	Export	17	Mix 23	Import
3	Mix 123	Import	18	Mix 23	Export
4	Mix 123	Export	19	Mix 24	Import
5	Mix 124	Import	20	Mix 24	Export
6	Mix 124	Export	21	Mix 34	Import
7	Mix 134	Import	22	Mix 34	Export
8	Mix 134	Export	23	Only 1	Import
9	Mix 234	Import	24	Only 1	Export
10	Mix 234	Export	25	Only 2	Import
11	Mix 12	Import	26	Only 2	Export
12	Mix 12	Export	27	Only 3	Import
13	Mix 13	Import	28	Only 3	Export
14	Mix 13	Export	29	Only 4	Import
15	Mix 14	Import	30	Only 4	Export

FIGURE 119: LOADING CASES ON HINTERLAND TRANSPORT

Information of **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** is employed to calculate the conditional probability of each combination.

For example:

Mix 14 Import probability is obtained as:

43% (Group 1) multiplied by (51% (Import 40s)+16%(Import 20s))=32%

32% is divided by the sum of all combinations in order to obtain the overall proportion, final result is 3%, which means that in 100 trains, probably 3 trains would have this combination of units, or a very similar one.

The rank of the combinations with their probability and VEL-Wagon affinity is presented as follows, **an 80 ft long VEL-Wagon with tare 21 t is considered for this analysis:**

Combination (1-4)	Trade lane	Probability	VEL-Wagon affinity	Combination (1-4)	Trade lane	Probability	VEL-Wagon affinity
Mix 1234	Import	6,6%	😊	Mix 13	Export	3,1%	😊
Mix 123	Import	6,3%	😊	Mix 234	Import	3,0%	😐
Mix 1234	Export	5,9%	😊	Mix 24	Export	2,8%	😐
Mix 124	Import	5,6%	😊	Mix 23	Import	2,7%	😐
Mix 123	Export	5,3%	😊	Mix 14	Export	2,3%	😊
Mix 12	Import	5,2%	😊	Only 2	Export	2,2%	😊
Mix 134	Import	5,1%	😊	Mix 24	Import	2,0%	😐
Mix 13	Import	4,7%	😊	Mix 34	Export	1,9%	😞
Mix 124	Export	4,5%	😊	Only 1	Export	1,8%	😊
Mix 234	Export	4,1%	😐	Only 2	Import	1,6%	😊
Mix 14	Import	4,0%	😊	Mix 34	Import	1,5%	😞
Mix 12	Export	4,0%	😊	Only 3	Export	1,3%	😞
Mix 134	Export	3,7%	😊	Only 3	Import	1,1%	😞
Only 1	Import	3,6%	😊	Only 4	Export	0,6%	😞
Mix 23	Export	3,5%	😊	Only 4	Import	0,4%	😞

FIGURE 120: EVALUATIONS OF CASES IN HINTERLAND TRANSPORTATION

The VEL-Wagon affinity has to be interpreted as a mere forecast of the author. However the prior results would indicate that VEL-Wagons would perform:

- 😊 better in 78,8% of the cases,
- 😐 equal in 14,5% of the cases, and
- 😞 underperform in 6,7% of the cases.

The calculation of the affinity is presented below with some examples.

Better 😊

Loading scheme of a Mix1234 Import:

No. Containers 50	1 Light (6t/TEU)	2 Medium light (14t/TEU)	3 Heavy (23t/TEU)	4 Very heavy (29t/TEU)	Total No. containers	Total TEUS 79
40 ft import	21	8	0	0	29	58
20 ft import	6	4	8	3	21	21

Mix 1234 Import						Probability	
						6,6%	
Train with wagon type	Tare	Amount wagons	TEU capacity	TEU transported	Train weight	Axles	Length
60 ft standard	19 t	29	87	79	1393	116	574 m
80 ft articulated (REF)	27,5 t	20	80	79	1392	120	528 m
VEL 80 ft	21 t	20	80	79	1242	80	518 m
VEL80 ft (same train weight as REF)	21 t	23	92	90	1409	92	596 m
Wagon Type	Tare	Amount wagons	TEU capacity	TEU transported	Train weight	Axles	Length

This means that with same train weight and few axles VEL-wagon train could transport ~15% more TEUs than regular trains, which could save about a full train every 6 trains of the operator.

This advantageous situation happens in 18 cases more, which represent the 78,8% of the trains.

Equal 😊

No. Containers 50	1 Light (6t/TEU)	2 Medium light (14t/TEU)	3 Heavy (23t/TEU)	4 Very heavy (29t/TEU)	Total No. containers	Total TEUS 67
40 ft import	0	17	0	0	17	34
20 ft Import	0	9	18	6	33	33

Loading scheme of a Mix234 Import:

Mix 234 Import						Probability	
						3%	
Wagon Type	Tare	Amount wagons	TEU capacity	TEU transported	Train weight	Axles	Length
60 ft standard (REF)	19 t	22	66	66	1614	88	416 m
80 ft articulated	27,5 t	17	68	67	1664	102	449 m
VEL 80 ft non-articulated	21 t	20	80	67	1596	80	518 m

In this case a VEL-Wagon train:

- is <100 m longer 😞, (Increase air friction)
- is 18 t lighter 😊,
- has two fewer wagons 😊, (neutralize capital cost) and
- has eight fewer axles 😊 (decrease rolling friction and maintenance)

than a 60 ft-wagon train. (reference), which could lead to a neutral situation. (The comparison with an articulated-80 ft-wagon train yields even a better performance of VEL Wagon)

Underperform 😞

Loading scheme of an Only3 Export:

No. Containers	1 Light (6t/TEU)	2 Medium light (14t/TEU)	3 Heavy (23t/TEU)	4 Very heavy (29t/TEU)	Total No. containers	Total TEUS
50					50	50
40 ft import	0	0	0	0	0	0
20 ft Export	0	0	50	0	50	50

Only3 Export						Probability	
						1,3%	
Wagon Type	Tare	Amount wagons	TEU capacity	TEU transported	Train weight	Axles	Length
60 ft standard	19 t	17	51	50	1473	68	321 m
80 ft articulated REF	27,5 t	13	52	50	1508	78	343 m
VEL 80 ft non-articulated	21 t	25	100	50	1650	100	648 m

To offer the same performance than an 80 ft articulated train (reference) VEL-wagon train should:

- have 12 wagons more ☹️ (increase capital costs),
- be ~300 m longer ☹️ (increase air friction) ,
- be 142 tones heavier ☹️, and
- have 22 more axles ☹️ (increase rolling friction)

(The comparison with REF. 60 ft train yields somewhat less bad results for VEL-Wagon)

In this case, more VEL wagons are needed and the result is a longer train which implies more air friction, the amount of necessary axles has to be higher too, which increases the rolling friction. The author speculates that VEL-Wagon would have an underperformance of 32% being this the worst case possible; fortunately the possibilities to find such loading schema are very low. Only one case in 100 would have this schema, and the operator would probably avoid it by loading the empty spaces with empty containers, or combine it with other loads in order to get a consistent loading schema.

The analysis case by case for all the 30 cases yields the following results:

Combination (1-4)	Trade lane	Probability	Benefit/loss in %	Combination (1-4)	Trade lane	Probability	Capacity increase %
Mix 1234	Import	6,6%	15%	Mix 13	Export	3,1%	15%
Mix 123	Import	6,3%	16%	Mix 234	Import	3,0%	0%
Mix 1234	Export	5,9%	12%	Mix 24	Export	2,8%	1%
Mix 124	Import	5,6%	15%	Mix 23	Import	2,7%	0%
Mix 123	Export	5,3%	16%	Mix 14	Export	2,3%	14%
Mix 12	Import	5,2%	16%	Only 2	Export	2,2%	17%
Mix 134	Import	5,1%	18%	Mix 24	Import	2,0%	0%
Mix 13	Import	4,7%	16%	Mix 34	Export	1,9%	-16%
Mix 124	Export	4,5%	12%	Only 1	Export	1,8%	14%
Mix 234	Export	4,1%	-3%	Only 2	Import	1,6%	14%
Mix 14	Import	4,0%	15%	Mix 34	Import	1,5%	-16%
Mix 12	Export	4,0%	17%	Only 3	Export	1,3%	-32%
Mix 134	Export	3,7%	14%	Only 3	Import	1,1%	-32%
Only 1	Import	3,6%	16%	Only 4	Export	0,6%	-8%
Mix 23	Export	3,5%	18%	Only 4	Import	0,4%	-6%

FIGURE 121: RESULTS OF VEL-WAGON TRAIN PERFORMANCE IN HINTERLAND INTERMODAL TRANSPORT.

Important note: Empty containers transportation is not considered in this analysis, but it would be beneficial for VEL-wagon in any case.

Benefit or loss percentages are calculated as follows:

$$\text{Capacity increase \%} = \frac{TEUs\ VEL - TEUs\ REF}{TEUs\ REF}$$

Where:

TEUs VEL are the TEUs transported by a train with VEL-Wagons

TEUs REF are the TEUs transported by a train with reference wagons

In both cases VEL-Train and REF train have same or very similar gross weight and length.

The overall calculation would yield the following results:

Hinterland Traffic	Probability	Capacity increase in %
Import trains	53,1%	6,1%
Export trains	46,9%	4,5%
Total trains	100%	10,6%

As expected, the sum of capacities' increases offsets the decreases, yielding a positive balance for VEL-Wagon trains of 10,6%.

The analysis has been done considering a VEL-Wagon with a loading length of 80 ft and a tare of 21 t, which yields a payload of 69 t. An increase of the tare, e.g. to 22 t (payload 68 t) would have an influence on the worst cases but in generally the VEL-wagon would remain in the same level of capacity increase. Further increases of tare could jeopardize the payload capacity of the VEL-wagon thereby eroding its efficiency.

Another consideration to be done is the utilisation of VEL-Wagon in conventional trains, this is, trains with conventional wagons and VEL-Wagons mixed. The interpretation in principle is positive since VEL-Wagon could transport the lighter containers and 40 ft containers without any problem, while other heavy containers could be transferred to the other wagons, e.g. to 60 ft or 80 ft articulated. In this way a train with mixed wagon types would have more chances to address a higher number of cases. In any case a compromised solution between logistics requirements, amount of axles, train weight and train length should be reached.

The breakthrough of the 45 ft container in the hinterland container market is not expected for the moment. It is true that there is an important presence of this container type in the traffics with North Europe (U.K. and Scandinavia) but not when it comes to the major container ocean carriers. Should this be the case, the articulated 80 ft wagon could become obsolete as it does not allow the transportation of 45 ft units at all. A VEL-Wagon with 80 ft could transport 45 ft containers and it still would have place for another short unit. A concept of VEL-Wagon of 85 ft would have to be evaluated again in some years if the 45 ft container starts to be present in the hinterland transport.

Finally, the transportation of empty containers would be beneficial for VEL-Wagon and would increase even more its efficiency.

6.2.2. CONCLUSIONS OF THE SIMUTAION ON MARITIME TRAFFIC

An 80 ft wagon would offer a number of benefits for maritime transports:

- Better loading factor of trains (more TEU per length, better arrangement of units)
- Fewer axles per length which may imply:
 - Less energy consumption (decreased rolling resistance)
 - Less maintenance
 - Less noise (fewer axles and increased axle load)

- Better aerodynamics (fewer bogies and fewer gaps between containers due to better compression factor of units)

6.2.3. SIMULATION ON CONTINENTAL TRAFFIC

A VEL-Wagon for continental intermodal transport could have different configurations; the author investigated the following two concepts:

- **Concept 1**

90 ft VEL-Wagon for one semitrailer and a 45 ft body

This wagon concept is able to transport:

- C.a. 67 t of payload (tare ~23 t)
- 3 x Light short swap bodies (≤ 30 ft)
- 2 x Heavy bodies (≤ 30 ft) + 1x light swap body (≤ 30 ft)
- 2 x 45 ft containers or bodies
- 1 x Semitrailer + 1 x long body (≤ 45 ft)
- 2 x 40 ft containers
- 4 x 20 ft containers

- **Concept 2**

80 ft VEL-Wagon for one semitrailer and a ≤ 35 ft container

This wagon concept is able to transport:

- C.a. 68 t of payload (tare ~ 22 t)
- 3 x Light short swap bodies (≤ 26 ft)
- 2 x Light short bodies and a container ≤ 30 ft
- 2 x Heavy bodies (≤ 26 ft) + 1x light swap body (≤ 26 ft)
- 2 x 30 ft containers + 1 x 20 ft container
- 1 x 45 ft container or body + 1 x body ≤ 35 ft
- 1 x Semitrailer + 1 x body (≤ 35 ft)
- 2 x 40 ft containers
- 4 x 20 ft containers

And the employed wagons for doing the comparison.

- **Reference wagon 1**

106' for 2 semitrailers (e.g. Twin)

This wagon is able to transport:

- C.a. 100 t of payload (tare ~35 t)
- 4 x Light short swap bodies (≤ 26 ft)
- 3 x Heavy bodies (≤ 26 ft) + 1x light swap body (≤ 26 ft)
- 2 x 30 ft containers
- 2 x 45 ft containers or bodies
- 2 x semitrailers
- 2 x 40 ft containers
- 4 x 20 ft containers

- **Reference wagon 2**

60' wagon for one semitrailer

This wagon is able to transport:

- C.a. 70 t of payload (tare ~20 t)
- 2 x Short swap bodies (≤ 26 ft)
- 2 x 30 ft containers
- 1 x 45 ft container or body
- 1 x semitrailer
- 1 x 40 ft container
- 3 x 20 ft containers

- **Rejected Concept**

90' Compact version for 2 semitrailers

From a logistical point of view this solution would offer the optimal performance for transportation of semitrailers, however it is technically rejected due to the necessary long distance between the bogie centres, which is technically incompatible with the actual regulations and loading gauges of the European railway system.

A total of 10 scenarios have been chosen for the analysis, namely:

1 Shuttle 2011	Average mix of units in a shuttle	6 Only FTL	Full Truck Load traffic, only light swap bodies and semitrailers
2 Shuttle 2020	Average mix of units in a shuttle for 2020	7 Only semitrailers	Only semitrailers
3 No FTL	No Full Truck Loads, no light swap bodies, no semitrailers	8 Only light swap bodies	Only light swap bodies
4 Bulk	Only tanks, silos and dry bulk containers	9 Only 45 ft	Only 45 ft containers
5 No semitrailers	Only containers and Swap bodies	10 Only 30 ft	Only 30 ft containers with bulk

These scenarios represent a part of the continental traffic reality. The simulation of the total reality would be too costly and even in case of achieving it, the information to be extracted from it would be not practical for the project.

For each scenario four types of train have been evaluated. Each train is formed by wagons of one single type. The trains are based on the concepts and reference wagons described more above, then so we have:

- Train with only 106 ft 6-axled wagons; REF 1
- Train with only 60 ft 4-axled wagons; REF 2
- Train with only 90 ft 4-axled wagons; VEL 90
- Train with only 80 ft 4-axled wagons; VEL 80

The initial input is the proportion of units' types existing in each scenario. With this proportion it is calculated the maximum amount of units of each type that could be transported in a 500 m long REF train, this can be REF 1 or REF 2 depending which is best. It is important to note that the proportion of units' types remains always steady.

For the distribution of units to each train it is necessary an iterative algorithm of unit assignation. The algorithm is different for each wagon, it has the following conditions:

- Length utilisation of the wagon has to be maximized
- Axle load of max 22,5 t has to be respected for each axle

Once obtained the amount of units of each type to be transported in a 500 m long REF train, the same amount of units is employed for the analysis of the other trains. In this way the other trains have to be designed to transport optimally such amount of units.

In some cases shorter and lighter trains with fewer axles are able to transport the same amount of units than the REF train, which means that these trains are performing more efficiently than the REF case. This is marked with green (the opposite case it is marked with red).

A train with a combination of different kinds of wagons would yield an intermediate result between the pure case analyses.

The wagon target cost is calculated as follows:

Target cost of wagon =(cost of REF wagon * amount of REF wagons) / amount of wagons

The employed REF wagon costs are (source Tatravagonka):

- REF 1: 150.000 € for a 106 ft wagon
- REF 2: 90.000 € for a 60 ft wagon

Scenario 1

The continental intermodal trains carry a proportional mixture of all units according to the statistical information on continental transportation:

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	29%	29%	12%	13%	8,5%	8,5%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	12	12	5	5	3	3

This case represents the whole spectrum of continental intermodal transportation, which does not necessarily mean that the mentioned loading schema has to be typical in the majority of continental trains in Europe. Pretty the contrary, this case could be possible in fixed shuttles carrying consignments from different clients, but by particular clients the loading schema could be radically different. However, trains with “Scenario 1” composition could be observed in the Rhine corridor, e.g. crossing the Alps.

Scenario No. 1	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+18%	-22%	-15%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	82% REF	+0%	+2%	+10%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	+2%	-1%	-7%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1313 REF	+5%	-7%	-6%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+77% 84.700€	+18% 127.400€	+28% 117.000€

Comments:

VEL 80 with capacity for 1 semitrailer would offer a fair advantage in respect to REF wagon, the 106' with two pockets. The major advantage would be in the reduced amount of axles for same transportation performance, in concrete a 15% reduction on axle need. This would entail savings in wagon maintenance (fewer wheels to reprofile) and lower energy consumption because having lower rolling resistance. Furthermore, due to the better loading factor (+10%) the gaps between the containers or bodies would be reduced and this would mean less aerodynamic resistance. Finally the train would have lower deadweight which would imply lower energy consumption.

Scenario 2

Forecast 2020. The forecast has been done after observations on unit preferences during the last decade and specially after interpreting the consequences of the 2009 crisis on unit demand (differential demand decrease).

To obtain values for the year 2020 these interpretations have been applied:

Decrease on light short unit, this is also observed in road transportation where the long units (45 ft boxes and semitrailers) are preferred over road trailers (3+2 axles).

Increase on heavy short units, both 7,82 m and 30 ft tanks and silo containers which are in a clear increasing trend.

Increase on long 45 ft unit goes almost in parallel with the increase on semitrailers, being the semitrailers, and specially the light ones, the most demanded in the last times.

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	5%	25%	11%	19%	35%	5%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	2	8	4	6	12	2

Again, the depicted unit distribution should not be interpreted as the typical or most common unit distribution on the continental trains, but rather as an indicator of the averaged unit proportion in the whole system. In that sense, a trend could be that in a future a big operator with important continental flows could try to consolidate large amounts of cargo on fixed relations (shuttles) between hub terminals. In this case, statistically, the shuttle trains would tend to have the above-mentioned distribution of units.

Scenario No. 1.1	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+21%	-17%	-2%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	80% REF	-1%	-2%	-3%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	+4%	+4%	+7%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1280 REF	+7%	-5%	0%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+81% 83.000€	+24% 121.000€	+47% 100.000€

Comments:

The shifting in proportions of the units would benefit the longer ones, namely 45 ft and semitrailers. Bulk and tank containers would maintain their quote and this would entail better market position for the 90 ft in comparison with an 80 ft.

Scenario 3

Traffic without semitrailers and without light swap bodies.

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	0%	54%	22%	24%	0%	0%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	0	20	8	8	0	0

This scenario would be concentrated on bulk, tank and 45 ft containers. Related companies examples: Hupac, Kombiverkehr, Fercam, Hoyer, Samskip, Van den Bosch, Bertschi, Unit 45, Ambrogio, etc., Present in Rhine corridor.

Scenario No. 2	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+1%	-19%	-13%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	71% REF	+18%	-2%	8%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	-13%	2%	-6%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1388 REF	0%	-7%	-6%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+52% 99.000€	+22% 123.000€	+30% 115.000€

Comments:

The 80 ft wagon would be better suited for this kind of traffic as it has better length capacity than the reference, especially when it comes to 45 ft unit.

Scenario 4

Without 45 ft, only 30 and 26 ft bulk, silo, and tank containers

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	0%	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	0	35	15	0	0	0

Traffic of containerized liquids, dangerous goods, foodstuffs etc.

Scenario No. 2.1	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	+15%	100 REF	0%	0%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	-26%	90% REF	-33%	-21%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	33%	500 REF	45%	26%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	7%	1867 REF	3%	0%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	-24% 117.000 €	+25 90.000€	0% 90.000€	0% 90.000€

Comments:

This scenario would be also very well covered by the 60 ft wagons which are quite abundant in the European fleets. The VEL 80 ft wagon would be the second best solution, 106' and VEL 90 would be not that appropriate.

Scenario 5

Traffic without semitrailers

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	35%	35%	14%	16%	0%	0%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	15	15	6	7	0	0

This scenario only considers the transportation of containers. It mirrors the case of comparing the VEL-80 and -90 as only container wagons with no pocket.

Scenario No. 2.2	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+14%	-21%	-15%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	82% REF	+2%	+1%	+10%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	-1%	-1%	-8%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1334 REF	+4%	-8%	-7%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+72% 87.000€	+18% 127.000€	0% 150.000€

Comments:

In a scenario without semitrailers the 80 ft wagon improves all relevant operational parameters in comparison with the best reference.

Scenario 6

Traffic only with semitrailers and light swap bodies.

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	40%	0%	0%	0%	35%	25%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	14	0	0	0	13	8

This traffic would mirror the market of the full-load road vehicle in intermodal transportation, which is a product offered by intermodal companies on door-to-door basis. Related examples: Hangartner, Winner Spedition, LKW Walter, etc.

Scenario No. 3	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+33%	+8%	+15%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	87% REF	-11%	-21%	-15%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	15%	+36%	+25%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1200 REF	+11%	+8%	+6%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+95% 75.000€	+62% 92.000€	+73% 86.000€

Comments:

The Twin wagon is the best solution for this scenario.

Scenario 7

Only Semitrailers

The results are even more favourable to 106'.

Hence: VEL-Wagon is not recommended for the only-semitrailer segment.

Scenario 8

Only light swap bodies

Scenario No. 3.2	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+32%	-12%	-11%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	94% REF	-10%	-9%	+5%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	+14%	+10%	-3%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1150 REF	+11%	-5%	-7%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+98% 75.000€	+31% 114.000€	+33% 112.000€

Comments:

In this case the VEL 80 offers better performance than the reference as it can transport 3 swap bodies in one wagon.

Scenario 9

Traffic of only 45 ft containers.

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	0	0	0	30	0	0

Traffic specialized in Nordic Countries and UK, Short Sea Shipping, ferry lines and the like.

Scenario No. 4	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	90 REF	+33%	-33%	+31%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	84% REF	-11%	19%	-29%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	500 REF	+14%	-15%	+43%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	1100 REF	+12%	-15%	+12%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	15 REF 150.000 €	+99% 75.500€	+1% 150.000€	+97% 76.500€

Comments:

This case would be the perfect case for a 90 ft VEL-Wagon, VEL 80 ft would be a very bad choice.

Scenario 10

Only Bulk, 30 ft containers.

Unit Class	1a (Light short swap body)	1b (Heavy short swap body≤26 ft)	2 (30 ft Container)	3 (45 ft container)	4a (Light semitrailer)	4b (Heavy semitrailer)
Unit proportion	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%
Amount in a 500 m REF long train	0	0	50	0	0	0

Traffic of containerized bulk segment, f.i. InterBulk.

Scenario No. 5	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Amount of axles (related to maintenance & energy)	+49%	100 REF	0%	0%
Loading factor (used loading length, aerodynamics)	-44%	100% REF	-33%	-22%
Train length (m) (related to infrastructure & operation)	+73%	500 REF	+45%	+26%
Train weight (t) (related to energy, operation & infra)	+16%	2050 REF	+2%	0%
Amount wagons) (related to capital costs) Wagon should cost less than...	0% 90.000 €	25 90.000€	0% 90.000€	0% 90.000€

Comments:

This scenario would be covered with 60 ft wagons which offer an unbeatable performance for this kind of loads. The 80 ft VEL-Wagon would be the less bad solution.

Summary:

A summarized evaluation could look as follows:

Red: Disadvantageous; Green: Advantageous

	REF 1 (106' ST)	REF 2 (60' ST)	VEL 90 (90' ST)	VEL 80 (80' ST)
Scenario 1 (Shuttle)				
Scenario 2 (Shuttle 2020)				
Scenario 3 (No FTL)				
Scenario 4 (Bulk + Tank)				
Scenario 5 (No Semitrailers)				
Scenario 6 (FTL)				
Scenario 7 (Only semitrailer)				
Scenario 8 (Light Swap body)				
Scenario 9 (Only 45 ft)				
Scenario 10 (Only 30 ft)				

Concluding that:

- 106 ft wagon suits optimally the FTL (full truck load, semitrailers) segment and performs quite reasonably in other segments except the pure bulk ones.
- 60 ft wagon is the optimal wagon for the pure bulk segment.
- 80 ft wagon would offer better performance than 106 ft in averaged situations (mainstream shuttles), but it is not recommended for specialized FTL transports, however it performs better than 106 ft wagon in bulk segments.
- 90 ft wagon would offer better performance than 80 ft if in the future the 45 ft unit is widely introduced.

6.2.4. CONCLUSIONS OF THE SIMULATION ON CONTINENTAL TRAFFIC

Intermodal continental transports utilize a large amount of unit types -much more than hinterland (sea) transportation- and that increases the amount of possible loading cases for the trains. In that sense, there would be an optimal wagon for each case but this wagon could be sub-optimally utilized for other cases. This variety of cases makes difficult to know which wagon is the optimal for an averaged situation, for instance the case of a mainstream shuttle, e.g. shuttle between Milano and Cologne.

Wagons represent an important investment for companies -c.a. 100.000 € per wagon- and they should be extensively utilized during their whole life cycle -25-30 years- to achieve profitability. For this reason, wagons specialized in one kind of units are usually employed for other unit types even if they are not 100% efficient at it. See the picture of a pocket wagon employed for the transport of a 30 ft tank container.

FIGURE 122: TWIN WAGON FOR SEMITRAILERS CARRYING AN 30 FT CONTAINER FOR BULK. SOURCE PICTURE: THE INTERMODAL CONTAINER WEB PAGE

Apparently, the articulated wagon for two semitrailers with total length of 106 ft (53 ft each half) is a popular wagon solution for continental intermodal transports nowadays. Hence this wagon has been used as reference for comparison.

The results of the capacity simulations have showed that an 80 ft long wagon could lead to important advantages in efficiency. These advantages would be amplified by averaged cases with mixture of units, for example in the case of a shuttle between two important continental terminals with an unknown and varying proportion of units.

The only-bulk segment represented by tanks, silos, 30 ft dry containers, etc. is the perfect market for 60 ft wagons. Hence, the comparison against other wagon types yields always negative results for the compared wagons. In spite of that, the 80 ft wagon yields less bad results than 106 ft wagon when addressing bulk market. In this way, an 80 ft it performs at same level but with fewer axles, shorter trains and less deadweight that a 106 ft.

The simulation for 90 ft wagons only yields better results for the case of only-45 ft units. In the rest of the cases the utilization of a 90 ft wagon would lead to poorer loading factors than other solutions.

It could be concluded that the 80 ft wagon would bring about an important gain for continental transports since it would enable better utilization of space (loading length) on trains than existing wagon technologies. 80 ft wagons would be able to transport same of even more amount of TEUs with fewer axles and less deadweight. Furthermore the aerodynamics would

improve (fewer gaps between containers, fewer bogies per meter) and the noise emissions would be reduced due fewer axles per train.

However its application on pure-semitrailer traffics would be on clear disadvantage against existing wagons, in concrete against the 106 ft (Twin) wagon. For this reason its attribute as pocket wagon could be not that valuable when compared to other existing solutions on the market. However an 80 ft wagon with a pocket would be very useful in shuttles between continental terminals with high traffic with an important mixture of different units.

A strategic procedure would be to design a 80 ft without pocket and try to make it as cheap as possible. By this it could be very competitive in its market segment.

Summarizing, in continental intermodal transportation a container-only 80 ft wagon would:

- **Increase the loading factor (amount of TEUs per train) in 10%**
- **Decrease the amount of axles in 15%**
- **Decrease the gross train weight in 7%**
- **Improve aerodynamics**
- **Decrease noise emissions**

6.2.5. CONCLUSIONS OF THE SIMULATIONS

After analyzing the intermodal traffics (hinterland and continental) it can be concluded that an 80 ft container wagon for ISO-containers and swap bodies would offer an important improvement in terms of logistics and energy efficiency.

Longer loading lengths -85 ft and 90 ft- could have an advantage too, but only if the 45 ft unit is widely introduced and if it dominates in intermodal traffics, which is not the actual case. A revision of this issue has to take place in approximately 5 years.

On the other hand, an 80 ft pocket wagon is an interesting solution for continental transports. It would target mainstream traffic flows with great diversity on unit types, including semitrailers. However the available solutions on the market for the transportation of only-semitrailers would offer a better performance at this time. This issue, together with the 45 ft-unit issue, have to be examined again in about 5 years.

Hence, an 80 ft without pocket, this is, only for the transportation of containers and swap bodies, would be more competitive than other wagons in its market range.

7. LONGER WAGONS' EFFECT ON INFRASTRUCTURE

The present section is an introduction to the effects that extra-large wagons with fewer axles may have on infrastructure and railway network.

These effects are studied attending to these concepts:

- Axle load
- Loading gauge
- Noise
- Network capacity

7.1. AXLE LOAD

An increased axle load has repercussions on the track components, the track geometry and the track structures, e.g. bridges.

The effects of increased axle load have been studied for many years, in Sweden [Nelldal], but especially in the U.S.

The HAL (Heavy axle load) traffic increases the benefit of the operation because it is possible to transport more tonnage with the same amount of wagons. It is a clear principle of economies of scale.

On the other hand, an increased axle load leads to higher investments and maintenance on infrastructure and on rolling stock since it needs more capable components that degrade faster due to increased forces. Hence the HAL will be interesting only if the benefits on operation offset the losses on track maintenance and the total account is positive.

There should be a limit on axle load increase after which the total balance of the railways productivity is negative and therefore the HAL is not interesting anymore. This happens when the productivity of the rail operation cannot offset the extra expenses on infrastructure and rolling stock.

The infrastructure degradation due to increased axle loads grows faster than the benefits resulting from the operation with increased axle loads. The following diagram is an approximation to the previous statement; it has been produced with information from the paper *"Economics of Increased Axle Loads, FAST/HAL Phase II Results"* of Hargrove, Guins, Otter, Clark and Martland 1991. The thin lines are an own interpretation of further axle loads increases, no data was available. "t" refers to metric tonnes.

FIGURE 123: COST VARIATION DUE TO INCREASED AXLE LOAD. DATA SOURCE: FAST/HAL PHASE II RESULTS.

Link: www.rta.org/Portals/0/Documents/Research Paper & Articles/R&D Compendiums I & II/Vol.2-1. Life Cycle Performance R&D/Economics of Increased Axle Loads.pdf

Further studies confirmed these statements, such as the study by Kalay, Semih and Tom Guins, which was gathered on the publication “The economics of heavy axle loads” by S. K. Shrivastav and K. Jalan. It states that freight cars of 286.000 pounds are more economic than 263.000 cars and than 315.000 cars. (263 000 pounds are equivalent to 29,8 t/axle, 286000 to 32,4 t/axle and 315000 to 35,7 t/axle.

Link: http://wiki.ircen.gov.in/doku/lib/exe/fetch.php?media=ipwe_seminar_2011:shrivastava_jalan.pdf (“t” refers to metric tons))

This diagram will look much different in the case of European tracks provided the intense passenger traffic at higher speeds that demands higher track quality.

FIGURE 124: SIMULATED HAL SAVINGS ON A WESTERN COAL ROUTE - COMPARISON TO 263,000-POUND CARS. "HEAVY AXLE LOADS: THE DOLLARS AND SENSE CASE" IN THE RAILWAY AGE, MARCH 1998

In principle there was a cost advantage when increasing the gross car load in U.S. railways from 263000 pounds to 286000, but only up to the point where the benefits on operation were interesting in comparison to the expenses on track and upgraded vehicles. In this way the extension to 315000 pounds (35,7 t/axle) seemed no to be interesting. In the U.S. it seems to be an optimum on 32,4 t/axle.

In Europe the most common max. allowed axle load is 22,5 t. Usually the increase of axle load is regarded as an action oriented towards heavy goods like coal, iron ore, sands, gravels and the like. However in this doctoral thesis it is defended that an axle load increase could and should be also interesting for lighter transports such as containers. Hence, **the objective is to reduce the amount of axles and therefore to increase the net-load-to-tare ratio of the wagons and trains.**

An example of this direction is the VEL-Wagon.

VEL-Wagon will have higher axle loads because having fewer axles per meter. A first estimation indicates that the increase of tonnage per axle should be around 20% both on hinterland and on continental traffics. This estimation has been achieved together with the calculations on hinterland and continental traffics, a summary including the averaged axle loads for each case is presented as follows.

Note: The calculations do not include empty container transport, which means that on the real praxis the axle load would be lower.

	Articulated wagon 80 ft 4 m of loading length per axle	Short wagon 60 ft 4,6 m of loading length per axle	Articulated wagon 106 ft 5,6 m of loading length per axle	VEL wagon 80 ft 6 m of loading length per axle
Hinterland transport	12,6 t/axle	13,1 t/axle	Normally not used	16,1 t/axle

Continental transport	Normally not used	13,5 t/axle	15,2 t/axle	16,6 t/axle
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Generally it can be said that intermodal transports do not make fully use of the allowable axle load in the main European tracks, being this axle load 22,5 t/axle. Typically, intermodal trains are quite light if compared with other trains like the bulk unit trains or trains of the single wagon load system.

The 22,5 t/axle seem in principle enough for the intermodal transport, however it can happen that on heavy transportations, e.g. tanks, bulk containers and containers with steel products, the allowed axle load may be not sufficient. For these cases there are wagons with more axles per length, as it happens with the 80 ft articulated wagon. This wagon has the advantage of increasing the payload capacity, however this capacity may not be efficiently used in other cases, which are the majority, being its net-weight-to-tare ratio quite poor.

Apparently, VEL-Wagon would have no big problem with its reduced payload. The initial estimations indicate a tare of 21-22 t for the wagon, which yields a total payload of 69-68 tonnes, this is 17 tonnes per TEU or two 40' containers of max. 34 t each. Further reductions of tare will be studied.

In the worst possible case, having to transport only heavy 20 ft units of 30 tonnes each, VEL-Wagon could only transport two of them, whereas a 80 ft with articulation could transport only 3 units, and not 4, due to shared bogie in the articulation.

On this subject some questions arise:

Is it sustainable to use over-dimensioned wagons like the 6-axled 80 ft wagon just to cope with few extreme cases or to have better container capacity arrangement?

Could the logistics on terminals and companies be improved to make better use of wagon capacity and available axle loads by allocating the containers optimally?

Is the punctual overpass of the 22,5 t/axle too bad for the operation and the infrastructure?

In any case VEL-Wagon will necessitate the 22,5 t axle load in order to achieve a reasonable payload and make an efficient use of it. For this reason it is a condition to employ 920 mm wheels and to circulate on infrastructures that are prepared for this axle load. Fortunately, most of the important tracks (84% of the ERIM network, Source UIC/ERIM) in Europe are prepared for 22,5 t/axle. In Germany about 95% of all track-km are already class D4 (22,5 t) as observed in the Network Statement for 2012.

Only in some eastern countries lower axle loads can be found in some important tracks, however this situation should be corrected in a short term.

The following map shows the distribution of axle loads in the main European tracks.

FIGURE 125: AXLE LOADS IN EUROPE. SOURCE: ERIM ATLAS 2009, UIC.

In principle, the axle load issue could be a problem in some infrastructures of Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Ex-Yugoslavia, South Italy, Romania and Greece. Obviously, this problem is not only an issue for VEL-Wagon but actually it is an problem for the freight railway system in general. For this reason it is expected that these countries overcome soon their axle load problems in order to become more competitive and thereby more sustainable.

In European main network (ERIM network) there is about 11% of the track-km prepared for more than 22,5 t/axle, this is what is called Class E (25 t/axle). ERIM Atlas states:

“The parts of the network most dedicated to heavier axle load (25 tonnes) are to be found in Sweden and the UK. In Sweden 30% of the main network is upgraded to 25 tones. Only one line in ERIM network accepts 30 tonnes, the “Malmbanan “ (45 km) in Northern Sweden.”

In spite of the trend existing in Nordic countries for higher axle loads in Continental Europe it is not for the moment not a reality and a systematic upgrade to 25 t is not expected in the short term.

The axle load extension would be interesting for light goods if the length of the wagons is increased and/or the amount of wheels per meter is reduced. In this way, the extension of the wagon length leads to another problem which is the small, compared to the U.S. loading gauge.

7.2. LOADING GAUGE

When a new or renewed wagon is intended to be used for intermodal transportation it needs to be produced, coded and exploited in accordance with the existing guidelines, importantly:

- The TSI-WAG “*Technical Specification for Interoperability relating to the subsystem Rolling Stock — Freight Wagons*”. In concrete, Annex C specifies the reference profile and the rules for the maximum construction gauge for wagons.
- The UIC Leaflet 571-4 “*Standard wagons – Wagons for combined transport – Characteristics*” Where important constructional details are given for standardized or partly standardized wagons. Apart of this leaflet, many other UIC-Leaflets contain technical information for construction of particular wagon’s components as well as other conditions relevant for operation.
- (Included in Annex C of TSI-WAG) The UIC Leaflet 505-1 “*Railway transport stock - Rolling stock construction gauge*” which governs the application of the European gauges on vehicle and load dimensioning. Other related leaflets, 505-4, 505-5 and 506 govern specific gauging issues.
- The UIC Leaflet 596-6 “*Conveyance of road vehicles on wagons – Technical organization – Conditions for coding combined transport load units and combined transport lines*”. Where it is set out the coding and organization of loading units in respect of road vehicles on wagons.
- GCU: General Contract of Use for Wagons
- RIV2000: Übereinkommen über den Austausch und die Benutzung von Güterwagen zwischen Eisenbahnverkehrsunternehmen

These documents contain an important amount of formulae and tables necessary to calculate the maximal outside dimensions of a freight vehicle plus its loads inside a given loading gauge.

7.2.1. CODES OF LOADING GAUGES

In the Leaflets 505-5, and 506, standard intermodal loads are used for determining gauges.

(“a” is the distance between bogie pivots)

Standard loads used to define gauges GA, GB and GC

GA Gauge

- Containers 8' (2,438 m) wide and 8'6 ½" (2,604 m) high, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) with ($a \leq 16$ m) and floor height $\leq 1,246$ m.
- Containers 8' (2,438 m) wide and 9'6" (2,896 m) high, loaded on (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) wagons ($a \leq 16$ m) and floor height $\leq 0,954$ m (block trains).
- Swap bodies 2,50 m wide and 2,60 m high, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) with ($a \leq 12,50$ m) and floor height $\leq 1,246$ m.
- Special semi-trailers 2,50 m wide, used in rail-road traffic loaded on recess or low-loader wagons (tolerance on centering ± 20 mm) with ($a \leq 12,50$ m), and edge height not exceeding 3,85 m above the running surface.

GB gauge

- Containers 8' (2,438 m) wide and 9'6" (2,896 m) high, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) with ($a \leq 16$ m) and floor height 1,18 m.

GC gauge

- Container 8' (2,438 m) wide and 9'6" (2,896 m) high loaded on any type of standard flat wagons with ($a \leq 16$ m).

- Lorries and semi-trailers built to road gauge 2,50 m wide and 4,00 m high, loaded on special wagons (tolerance on centering ± 100 mm) with ($a \leq 12,50$ m) and floor height $\leq 0,65$ m.

FIGURE 126: STATIC LOADING GAUGES GA, GB AND GC. SOURCE: TSI-WAG.

Leaflet 506 includes the following descriptions about the gauges:

- The GA gauge may be implemented in the more or less long term on all railway lines.
- The GB gauge, which incorporates the GA gauge, is relevant for short or medium-term projects involving a maximum number of lines in order to develop a cohesive network over a relatively extensive area.
- The GC gauge, which incorporates the GA and GB gauges, is relevant for new lines and major rebuilding projects (for example: tunnels) on specially-targeted existing lines.

Apart of these gauges, the Leaflet 505-4 names the following gauges used at international level:

- The minimum gauge to be implemented on all lines: G1. This gauge is the international minimum that must be provided on all lines (except in Great Britain, see UIC Leaflet 503, see Bibliography - page 35).
- Enlarged gauges provided by some IMs: G2. G2 gauge is a raised gauge used by different IMs (mostly in eastern Europe) based on the basis of bi-lateral or multilateral agreements (see UIC Leaflet 505-1).
- Enlarged gauges necessary for certain well defined routes: GA, GB, GC, GB1 and GB2 (see UIC Leaflet 506, see Bibliography - page 35) rebuilding projects (for example: tunnels) on specially-targeted existing lines.

The following image gives an overview of the above described loading gauges. The lines represent static loading gauges (horizontal and vertical dimensions respect proportions)

FIGURE 127: HI-CUBE ONTO 1180 MM FLOOR VS. STATIC EUROPEAN LOADING GAUGES. DATA: VARIOUS SOURCES.

By looking at this graph it can be anticipated that Hi-Cubes could be transported in GB or superior loading gauges if using conventional intermodal wagons with standard wheel diameter of 920 mm. GA and G1 gauges would require special low floor wagons.

Furthermore Hi-Cubes can be transported gently in Spanish gauge with standard wheel diameters of 920 mm. However an important remark has to be done as regards as the plans of the Ministerio de Fomento to introduce a third rail to provide UIC international gauge -1345 mm- in some Spanish lines. This is that the centre line of the rolling stock circulating on 1435 mm gauge would be displaced 233 mm to one of the sides -the one of the shared rail-, with the consequent loss of gauge. This would be equivalent to degrade Spanish loading gauge to GA gauge. Hence, a loading gauge check and/or a loading gauge extension have to accompany the third rail installation. Otherwise the Hi-Cube transport could not be done with standard intermodal wagons in that infrastructure. A loading height of ~ 930 mm would be necessary, which would require the utilization of special low floor wagons.

Furthermore, the leaflet 506 defines loading gauges GB1 and GB2 from the position of standard intermodal loads.

GB1 and GB2 gauges were developed on the basis of specific combined-transport requirements that emerged from 1989. Railways may conclude bi- or multi-lateral agreements covering application of GB1 and GB2 gauges on certain routes.

GB1 gauge

In conjunction with the gauges for lower parts given in UIC Leaflet 505-1

- *Containers 8'6" (2,591 m) wide and 9'6" (2,896 m) high, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) with $a \leq 16$ m and floor height 1,18 m.*
- *Swap bodies 2,60 m wide and 3,00 m high, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) with $a \leq 16$ m and floor height 1,18 m.*
- *Semi-trailers 2,50 m wide, loaded on recess wagons (tolerance on centering ± 20 mm) with $a \leq 12,5$ m and height of edges not exceeding 4,18 m above the running surface.*
- *Semi-trailers 2,60 m wide, loaded on recess wagons (tolerance on centering ± 10 mm) with $a \leq 13,3$ m and height of edges not exceeding 4,18 m above the running surface.*

In conjunction with GI3 gauge for lower parts - with the general wagon and load characteristics defined for GB2 gauge under point C.3.2 - page 52.

- *Semi-trailers with deflated air suspension 2,60 m wide and the height of which does not exceed 3,92 m, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 70 mm) with $a \leq 14,4$ m and floor height 0,235 m.*

GB2 gauge

In conjunction with GI3 gauge for lower parts

- *Semi-trailers with deflated spring suspensions 2,60 m wide and not in excess of 4,10 m high, loaded on wagons (tolerance on centering ± 70 mm) with $a \leq 14,4$ m and floor height 0,235 m.*

FIGURE 128: 3-METER HIGH AND 2,6 M WIDE SWAP BODY ONTO 1180 MM FLOOR VS. STATIC EUROPEAN LOADING GAUGES. DATA: VARIOUS SOURCES.

By looking at the graph it can be said that wide and tall swap bodies, for instance a 3-m tall refrigerated pallet-wide container, could be transported on intermodal wagons only in GB1 or a superior gauge. Minor gauges would require special low floor wagons.

An interesting point is to look as well to the lower parts of the loading gauges. In this way, the loading gauge G13 becomes relevant. The following text is extracted from UIC leaflet 506:

Gauge G13 was initially defined to enable optimum use to be made of infrastructure, in conjunction with gauge GB1, to enable the transport of semi-trailers on well wagons derogating from the gauge in UIC Leaflet 505-1. However, it can be used in conjunction with all other gauges.

Vehicles conforming to the enlarged G13 gauge shall only be allowed on lines whose lower parts have been enlarged accordingly; routing of such vehicles calls for bi- or multi-lateral agreements.

The GI3 gauge may be used on existing or future lines. It can be achieved at a lower cost than the gauges for lower parts defined in UIC Leaflet 505-4 since it primarily encounters occasional obstructions without consequence for larger obstacles such as platforms and structures.

In the practice gauge GI3 is nowadays very important for the unaccompanied semitrailer rail service Lorryrail between Perpignan and Luxemburg, which allows the transportation of 4-m tall semitrailers on special pocket wagons. Apparently this is the only line in France able to accommodate 4-m tall semitrailers nowadays. The Modalohr technology, with horizontal transfer, is employed for this transport service. The wagons have a pocket floor of only 22 cm above the top of the rail, reason for which they need a wider lower part on the gauge, therefore the GI3 gauge provides it.

The UIC Leaflet 596-6 refers to the conditions for coding combined transport lines. By this it ensures the compatibility of the intermodal loading units and intermodal wagons with the permissible profile for combined transport lines.

Combined transport lines in Europe have a code that permits to know if a given intermodal loading unit on a given wagon is transportable on the line. The code refers to swap bodies semitrailers and roller units.

The base conditions considered for the wagons are:

- (Code "C") For swap bodies
 - Standard loading height: 1175 mm
 - Distance between bogie pivots: 13,5
- (Code "P") For semitrailers
 - Standard loading height: 33 cm
 - Distance between bogie pivots: 11,2 m

Some examples:

C45 means that a container up to 2,55 m wide and 2,90 m tall ($290=45+245^*$) can be transported by a 1175 m high wagon which pivot distance "a" is $\leq 13,5$ m. If "a" is longer, then a lower loading height is required to fulfil the code. $*245$ is just a number that has to be added to the code in order to obtain the maximum height.

C364 means that a 2,79 m high container ($279=364-85^{**}$), which width is between 2,55 and 2,6 m (the latter inclusive) can be transported by a 1175 m high wagon which pivot distance "a" is $\leq 13,5$ m. If "a" is longer, then a lower loading height is required to fulfil the code. $**85$ is just a number that has to be detracted to the code in order to obtain the maximum height.

The coded lines and explanations can be found in the next exhibit.

FIGURE 129: MAP OF THE RAILWAY LINES IN CT - VERSION 2011 (SWAP BODIES). SOURCE:UIRR

7.2.2. GEOMETRIC OVERTHROW

The pivot distance “a” -distance between the bogies of a wagon- is a parameter that determines the structural gauge of a railway vehicle plus its loads.

This distance has a role on the calculation of the geometrical overthrow. TSI-WAG defines overthrow as:

The expression geometric overthrow means, for an element of a vehicle located on a radius R curve, the difference between the distance from this element to the track centreline and that which would exist on straight track, the axes being, in both cases, placed in a median position on the track, the play also being evenly distributed, the vehicle symmetrical and not tilted on its suspensions; in other words, it is that part of the vehicle element offset which is due to the track curvature.

On the same side of the track centreline, all the points in the same vehicle body cross-section have the same geometric overthrow.

FIGURE 130: GEOMETRIC OVERTHROW. SOURCE: TSI-WAG.

A VEL-Wagon with 80 ft loading length would require a longer “a” than the standard intermodal wagons. Obviously this would mean an increased geometric overthrow and a loss of gauge when running on a curve. The following section introduces a rough calculation of this issue with information purposes.

Let us suppose a wagon with:

- l = loading length
- a = pivot distance
- b = width of loading unit on the wagon

and other geometric parameters necessary for the calculation:

- R = radius of the curved track
- r1 = resulting interior radius of the vehicle
- r2 = resulting exterior radius of the vehicle

r1 and r2 are obtained with trigonometric formulae as follows:

And the overthrow would be calculated as:

Inner overthrow: $R-r_1-b/2$

Outer overthrow: $r_2-R-b/2$

In next exhibit there is a graphical representation of the parameters and the triangles used for the formulae and calculations:

FIGURE 131: SIMPLIFIED GEOMETRIC REPRESENTATION OF A WAGON RUNNING ON A CURVE.

The calculations of the overthrows for a standard 60 ft would result in:

Sgnss 60 ft		
l loading length 18,5 m	a bogie distance 14,2 m	(l-a)/2 headstock 2,15 m
(figures in meters)		
R curve radius	Inner Overthrow	Outer Overthrow
150	0,17	0,11
190	0,13	0,09
250	0,10	0,07
350	0,07	0,05
600	0,04	0,03
1000	0,03	0,02
5000	0,01	0,00
6000	0,00	0,00

FIGURE 132: OVERTHROWS OF A 60 FT WAGON

In that way, a Sgnss 60 ft wagon running on a curve of 250 m radius would be thrown roughly 10 cm towards the centre of the curve and 7 cm towards the outer part of the curve. For this reason tunnels are given an extra clearance to allow the free pass of long vehicles. Eventually this is what normally determines the loading gauge of a line.

An 80 ft-long VEL-Wagon could have the following dimensions and overthrows:

VEL-Wagon 80 ft		
l loading length 24,4 m	a bogie distance 17,4 m	(l-a)/2 headstock 3,5 m
(figures in meters)		
R curve radius	Inner Overthrow	Outer Overthrow
150	0,253	0,239
190	0,199	0,190
250	0,151	0,145
350	0,108	0,104
600	0,063	0,061
1000	0,038	0,036
5000	0,008	0,007
8000	0,005	0,005

FIGURE 133: OVERTHROWS OF A 80 FT VEL-WAGON

This means that a VEL-Wagon would be thrown roughly 5 cm more than a Sgnss 60' inside a 250 m curve. In very narrow curves, e.g. switches at marshalling yards and side yards with 190 m radius, the overthrow would be about 7 cm more than a Sgnss 60'.

According to the Combined Transport Profile Number (CTPN of UIC Leaflet 596-6) a line with a code C375 enables the transportation of a 2,6 m* x 2,9 m** (width x height) container on a wagon with pivot distance 13,5 m and a loading height of 1175 mm. * Plus 10 mm of maximum off-centering position of the load unit as a result of centering tolerances. ** 2,9 obtained as 375+85 as indicated by INTERUNIT.

This can be depicted as follows:

FIGURE 134: INTERMODAL WAGON AND ITS LARGEST LOAD IN A C375 PROFILE.

This wagon and its load would have the following overthrows:

Wagon with "a" = 13,5 m		
l loading length 18 m	a bogie distance 13,5 m	(l-a)/2 headstock 2,25 m
(figures in meters)		
R curve radius	Inner Overthrow	Outer Overthrow
150	0,15	0,12
190	0,12	0,09
250	0,09	0,07
350	0,07	0,05
600	0,04	0,03
1000	0,02	0,02
5000	0,00	0,00
8000	0,00	0,00

FIGURE 135: OVERTHROWS OF A WAGON WITH PIVOT DISTANCE 13,5 M AND LENGTH 18 M

According to calculations, an 80 ft-VEL-Wagon with "a" = 17,4 m would have the following extra overthrows in respect to a wagon with "a" = 13,5 m:

Curve radius	Inner overthrow VEL-80 ft with a=17,4	Inner overthrow REF wagon with a= 13,5	Difference (Extra overthrow)
150	0,253	0,15	10,1 cm
190	0,199	0,12	7,9 cm
250	0,151	0,09	6 cm
350	0,108	0,07	4,3 cm
600	0,063	0,04	2,5 cm
1000	0,038	0,02	1,5 cm
5000	0,008	0,00	0,3 cm
8000	0,005	0,00	0,2 cm

FIGURE 136: EXTRA OVERTHROWS OF A VEL-WAGON IN RESPECT TO A REFERENCE WAGON.

Which means that a VEL- Wagon with a=17,4 m would be thrown towards the interior of a 250 m radius curve about 6 cm more than the wagon employed for the definition of the Combined Transport Profile Number with a= 13,5 m. In case of 190 m radius the extra overthrow would be 7,9 cm.

Hence, a VEL-Wagon 80 ft with a=17,4 m is not be able to transport a 2,6 m x 2,9 m container in an infrastructure coded C375 with a loading height of 1175 mm. However, this could be possible at lower loading heights.

On the other hand, the transportation of an ISO-Hi-Cube container (8 ft wide) could in theory take place in a C375 profile with loading height of 1175 mm. This could be justified because the overthrow caused by the longer pivot distance is offset by the reduction on width of the loading unit.

2600 mm of the reference case – 2438 mm of an ISO container = 162 mm

Reduction in each side: 8,1 cm (16,2 / 2), which offsets the 7,9 cm extra overthrow in 190m-radius curves.

Hence, in theory, C375 is the minimum code line in which the transportation of a Hi-Cube (2,438 wide x 2,896 m tall) on an 1175 mm high VEL-Wagon 80 ft could be possible.

FIGURE 137: VEL-80 FT WITH A ISO HI-CUBE (2,438 X 2,896) IN A C375 PROFILE.

The wagon would have to be limited to curves of minimum 190 m radius when loaded. For curves of 150 m the wagon should be empty or have a lower loading height. Hence, a reduced loading height, say 1100 mm, could be sufficient to guarantee the intermodal gauge in 150 m curve radius.

Apparently, a code C375 is satisfied by most of the important lines in Europe, except Spain, France, South Italy (below Milano and Verona), few lines in Switzerland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Ex-Yugoslavia and Greece. On the other hand, Hupac and Kombiverkehr intermodal relations are on 90% over C375.

The remaining questions are:

- Could a VEL-Wagon 80 ft transport 2,6 m wide containers? How tall can they be? At which loading height? In which intermodal gauge?
- Could a VEL-Wagon 80 ft transport ISO-Hi-Cubes in smaller intermodal gauges? At which height?

To answer these questions, a rough approximation is presented, just for information purposes.

Assuming a C45 intermodal gauge, (e.g. Spain Italy and France) it is possible to affirm that:

A 2550 mm broad container 2900 high can be transported on floor height of 1175 m by a wagon with "a"=13,5 m.

A graphic interpretation of this limitation is presented below.

FIGURE 138: C45 PROFILE VS GB KINEMATIC GAUGE (PARALLEL LINE).

A VEL-Wagon with $a=17,4$ m would have an extra overthrow (in comparison to the reference wagon with $a=13,5$) of 10,1 cm in a curve of 150 m radius.

A ISO Hi-cube with 2438 mm width is 11,2 cm narrower than a 2550 mm wide unit, which results on 5,6 cm on one side.

The extra width that an ISO Hi-cube would represent in a VEL-Wagon is obtained as follows:

$$10,1 \text{ cm extra overthrow} - 5,6 \text{ cm} = 4,5 \text{ cm}$$

According to the dimension proportion of the GB kinematic profile (3:1) this would require a loading height of $1040 = 1175 - (45 \times 3)$

Graphically this could look as follows:

FIGURE 139: VEL-80 FT IN C45 INTERMODAL GAUGE.

A loading height of only 1040 mm with a 920 mm wheel seems complicated to achieve. 1090 mm seem feasible without too much technical development. One of the problems is the draw gear position.

An idea could be to take out the draw gear from underneath the load and place it in front of the wagon, like the low floor wagons (see picture).

FIGURE 140: LOW FLOOR WAGON WITH LOADING HEIGHT 980 MM AND WHEEL DIAMETER 840 MM. SOURCE: GREENBRIER.

However this would increase the wagon length in about 7% which goes against the principles of length efficiency pursued by VEL-Wagon.

Other ideas are to use special draw gears underneath the load, which may require new technical developments; further investigations on this issue have to take place.

In conclusion, it seems difficult to transport ISO-Hi-Cubes on 80 ft VEL-Wagons inside loading gauges of C45/C364 (Spain, France, Italy) because the required loading height would be quite low ~1040 mm. However this solution seems to be achievable with some technical development. Hence further investigations should be conducted on this direction.

On the other hand The transportation of 2,6 m wide x 2,9 m tall containers on VEL-Wagon would mean smaller-than-1000-mm loading heights which are impossible to reach with standard 920 mm wheels. To this aim, VEL-Wagons intend to have a second floor level between the bogies with a lower loading height for taller and wider containers.

The following table intends to be a very rough approach to which loading heights would be necessary for VEL-Wagon for each case of loading gauge. The author advises about the inexactness of the provided figures, which should be taken as mere indicators.

Unit	C364 (GB Gauge) Loading height	C375 (GB+ Gauge) Loading height	C400 (Larger gauge) Loading height
ISO Hi-Cube 2896 x 2438	~1040 mm	~1155 mm	~1175 mm
Swap body Hi-Cube 2896 x 2550	~ 855 mm	~1040 mm	~1175 mm
Swap body 2750 x 2550	~1000 mm	~1185 mm	~1175 mm
Frigo Swap body 2750 x 2600	~ 930 mm	~1100 mm	~1175 mm
Mega Swap body 3125 x 2550	~740 mm	~ 810 mm	~1175 mm

As it can be seen, the narrower the loading gauge and larger the container the lower the loading height required.

A lower loading height can be achieved by decreasing the diameter of the wheels and/or by reducing the thickness of the frame.

The reduction of the wheel diameter has the inconvenience that it decreases the surface contact between rail and wheel. By this, when higher axle loads occur then the RCF (Rolling Contact

Fatigue) is increased, which entails higher maintenance costs and crack risks. Hence the higher the axle load the larger the wheel diameter should be.

Minimum wheel diameter for an axle load

FIGURE 141: MINIMUM WHEEL DIAMETER FOR AXLE LOADS. DATA SOURCE: EIM POSITION PAPER ON AXLE LOAD IN RELATION TO WHEEL DIAMETER, MAY 2010.

The author is aware that many investigation is needed on the area above 22,5 t as well by higher speeds (<120 km/h) in order to know which are the limits for small wheels (that enable more volume) in consonance with higher axle loads.

On the other hand the reduction of the frame thickness is possible to gain (or loose) loading height. Apparently, one of the problems is the reduced space for the draw gear, which makes necessary new technical development for this element, like extra thin components.

7.3. NOISE

The reduction of the amount of axles per length implies an immediate decrease of the noise.

The noise dependency on this parameter, “apl” (axles per length) has been well studied in the past and has been already implemented on the legislation, namely the TSI noise.

It states that:

New wagons with an average number of axles per unit length (apl) up to 0,15 m⁻¹ at 80 km/h have a limit of 82 dB(A)

New wagons with an average number of axles per unit length (apl) higher than 0,15 m⁻¹ up to 0,275 m⁻¹ at 80 km/h have a limit of 83 dB(A)

New wagons with an average number of axles per unit length (apl) higher than 0,275 m⁻¹ at 80 km/h have a limit of 85dB(A)

With this information and some inputs from M. Kalivoda (Presentation at Infra TRANS 2007 – Bucharest page 25) it is possible to do a graph that portrays roughly the relation between axles per length and noise of wagons which grows exponentially.

FIGURE 142: NOISE VS. APL (AXLES PER LENGTH) BASED ON THE VALUES OF TSI, KALIVODA (AUSTRIA) AND [HECHT] TU BERLIN.

Apparently, the reduction of noise when using VEL-Wagon in respect to an articulated 80 ft wagon would be of about 1 to 1,5 dB without any special other measure. This would be a Top-Down calculation.

A bottom-up calculation leads to similar results, this calculation was produced by Dipl.-Ing. Gonzalo de Ana Rodríguez and Dipl.-Phys. Martin Balsler.

FIGURE 143: APL EFFECT VEL-WAGON SOURCE: DIPL.-ING. GONZALO DE ANA RODRÍGUEZ, DIPL.-PHYS. MARTIN BALSER DELIVERABLE 4.5 EFFECT ON THE TRACKS, AVAILABLE AT WWW.VEL-WAGON.EU

This speaks also in favour of reducing the amount of axles in order to decrease the noise of the freight trains.

Another interesting effect is that by higher axle loads the noise produced may be lower or less annoying than the one produced by lighter axle loads. This may be explained by the higher contact surface between rail and wheel which acts as an absorber of the higher frequencies. This issue has not been yet thoroughly studied and remains as an open question.

FIGURE 144: TYPICAL NOISE SPECTRUM IN THE FREIGHT TRANSPORT (80 KM / H, WHEEL DIAMETER 920 MM). (—) EMPTY (WHEEL CONTACT FORCE OF 25 KN) GG PADS, (---) LOADED (WHEEL CONTACT FORCE 100 KN) GG PADS, (- · - ·) EMPTY (WHEEL CONTACT FORCE OF 25 KN) K-PADS, (• • •) LOADED (WHEEL CONTACT FORCE 100 KN) K-PADS. SOURCE: C. GRAMOWSKI DOCTORAL DISSERTATION 2012 TUB.

Apparently, according to this research loaded wagons seem to be 2 to 5 dB quieter than empty wagons. However more investigation of this fact is needed.

7.4. NETWORK CAPACITY

Longer wagons, with uninterrupted length, have the capacity of being more efficient when it comes to loading length utilisation. A clear example can be seen in intermodal wagons, where the longer ones have higher possibilities to accommodate a great variability of loading units. In other words, longer wagons permit a higher variability on loading schemes.

Here is an example that considers VEL-Wagon.

It is accepted that 20 ft and 40 ft (standard and Hi-Cube) containers are almost exclusive in maritime traffic, however in the last times the 45 ft unit is more and more employed. Hence, it can happen that at some point 45 ft units have to be transported too. This will immediately reduce the loading factor of the trains since the wagon arrangement is not optimal for such container length.

In the case of the 80 ft articulated wagon the 45 ft container is fatal since it cannot be transported at all, therefore the more 45 ft units to be transported, the more 60 ft wagons (or articulated 90 ft wagons) have to be employed in substitution of 80 ft articulated wagons. Conversely, a 45 ft container can be transported on a VEL-Wagon without any particular problem, however, up to a certain proportion of 45 ft units the VEL-Wagon would not be efficient either and a longer wagon, say a 85 ft or a 90 ft should be necessary.

FIGURE 145: EFFECT OF 45 FT CONTAINER ON INTERMODAL TRAIN.

Interpretation of the effect of 45 ft containers in a reference train, the higher the proportion of 45 ft units the more 60 ft are needed (in detriment of 80 ft articulated). At a certain point a specific designed wagon has to be employed, for example an articulated 90 ft wagon or a 90 ft VEL-Wagon.

In the case of the maritime traffic, with only 40 and 20 ft containers, the ideal wagon is the 80 ft or the 2 x 40 ft because it matches any length proportion. The 60 ft wagon will be efficient as long as the proportion of 40 ft and 20 ft containers remains 50/50. If the 40 ft containers proportion start to grow, as it happens nowadays, then the 60 ft wagon leads to empty spaces and thus to inefficiency.

FIGURE 146: LOADING FACTOR OF 60 FT WAGONS IN RESPECT TO PROPORTION OF 40 FT AND 20 FT CONTAINERS.

FIGURE 147: LOADING FACTOR OF A WAGON IN RESPECT TO ITS LENGTH. FIXED PROPORTION OF 40 FT / 20 FT CONTAINERS (60% /40%)

The intermodal continental transport demands higher effort on wagon composition in order to match with the higher variability of loading unit cases.

Here, longer uninterrupted loading surfaces lead to better loading factors. This capacity simulation has been done with the following unit proportions: 40 % tanks and swap bodies < 7,82 m, 20 % silos and 30 ft bulk containers, and 40 % 45 ft boxes.

If looking at the total aggregated intermodal market it can be interpreted that a longer (uninterrupted) wagon would have higher loading factors because accommodating better the high variability on container lengths.

In this case, a VEL-Wagon would be a wagon that could be employed indistinctly both in continental and maritime traffic offering in both cases very good loading factors.

By looking at the graph, the author interprets that an uninterrupted 80 ft long wagon would increase the loading factor of the trains on a 5 to 10% in respect to a reference train formed by shorter wagons (such as articulated 80 ft, 90 ft and 60 ft). This increase would reduce the amount of trains necessary for achieving the same transportation output, leaving free slots for other trains and hence making better use of the available capacity.

In concrete it is estimated that trains formed by VEL-Wagons could save a train slot every 10 trains.

In conclusion, it is possible to increase the capacity of a railway infrastructure by using better rolling stock, in this case by using longer wagons with more capacity and better loading factor. An alternative is to construct a new railway infrastructure which may be proportionally much more expensive. An intermediate solution is to increase the quality of the infrastructure, this is by increasing the loading gauge and the axle load.

7.5. CONCLUSION FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ANALYSIS

Longer wagons such as VEL-Wagon 80 ft need a longer distance between pivots, which increases the overthrow of some parts of the wagon when running sharp curves. This implies a loss of loading gauge, which in smaller gauges requires a lower loading height for the containers. In the infrastructures having a larger-than-GB loading gauge this seems not to be a problem even with standard loading heights of 1175 mm. Hence in Germany, Austria, Poland, Hungary, North of Italy, Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Sweden and Norway where the codes P400 are available a long wagon like a VEL-Wagon with standard height would be able to transport almost all kind of road-compatible containers and swap bodies.

For smaller loading gauges a rough calculation of the necessary loading height has been presented, obtaining that an ISO hi-cube (2896 x 2438) could be transported in a number of important lines in Europe (GB Gauge) if a low loading height of ~ 1040 mm is achieved. Such loading height is quite low for being achieved with wheels of diameter 920 mm. The use of 920 mm diameter wheel is important for guaranteeing a satisfactory payload capacity of the wagon with 22,5 t per axle and to enable standard maintenances for freight wagons.

The 25 t per axle and more is considered an interesting option for longer wagons with fewer axles, e.g. 90 ft VEL-Wagon, 93 ft VEL-Wagon. This is important to achieve longer loading surfaces, which increase the loading factor of the trains and therefore the utilisation of the railway network.

It is possible to increase the capacity of a railway infrastructure by using better rolling stock, in this case by using longer wagons with more capacity and better loading factor. An alternative is to construct a new railway infrastructure which may be proportionally much more expensive. An intermediate solution is to increase the quality of the infrastructure, this is by increasing the loading gauge and the axle load.

The noise is reduced when the amount of axles decrease, furthermore there are indications to sustain that increased axle loads decrease the noise.

Investigations are needed on the following subjects:

- Study of the axle load extension to 25 t and more,
 - From the operative point of view, this is considering the whole exploitation of the service and the hypothetic benefits derived of the use of more capable wagons with fewer wheels intended for light goods.
 - From the point of view of track components and other infrastructure items, such as ballast and sub-ballast
 - From the point of view of noise emissions
- Study of the rail-wheel interaction (Rail Contact Fatigue) with smaller wheel diameters such as 840 mm together with high axle loads (22,5 t) and higher speeds, up to 140 km/h.
- Study of the available loading gauges and their interaction with increased distance between pivots “a” of the wagons, in order to achieve longer wagons with longer uninterrupted surfaces compatible with the existing infrastructures.
- Study the investments necessary for the extension of the freight capacity and compare it with an alternative based on the gauge extension and axle load increase.

8. BUSINESS CASE VEL-WAGON

During the last years there has been clear dominance of the shuttle production system in intermodal transportation. The shuttle represents the simplest form of exploitation in transport systems. In many cases it may be the only feasible production system for operators, especially when considering small companies and startup companies. Yet, the shuttles have the risk of not being filled up by the demand, in this way the demand may vary from one day to another whereas a shuttle may be designed for a semester or for a year. Furthermore the cost elements of the shuttle, such as locomotive and wagons, track path and indirect costs are long-term bounded, which increases the risk of the whole entrepreneurship. Other productions systems such as linear trains, direct trains (with changing wagon composition), multi-block trains, hub-and-spoke systems or the like need shunting and / or marshaling procedures which are only at the reach of big companies and have an important impact on the final costs of the service.

In the VEL-Wagon project a study of the European intermodal traffic was produced. By this, the typical and most frequent intermodal loading units were identified, providing as well their weight distribution based on real statistical data. Furthermore a simulation of probable cases showed that longer wagons -like VEL-Wagon- behaved better under averaged conditions of traffic. These averaged conditions refer mainly to mainstream traffic corridors e.g. services along the Rhine Corridor, between Italy and Scandinavia, Austria, Czech Republic, Poland etc. which represent nowadays the backbone of the European intermodal transport.

On the other hand the conventional railway freight transportation offers good possibilities for VEL-Wagon too. The typical application for long or extra-long cargo e.g. beams, pipes, masts, rails, long plates, profiles, trunks, etc., is very interesting for VEL-wagon, however these longer surfaces with lower loading heights would be also very adequate for weather-sensitive voluminous cargo. This includes for example: grouped goods in pallets, food and consumer goods, bottled and packed beverages, paper rolls, white goods, brown goods, textiles, rubber parts, plastics and machine parts (also auto parts). In European freight railways the wagons addressing such cargo types are categorized as "H" wagons (covered wagons). To emulate an H wagon, VEL-Wagon should be equipped with a detachable superstructure consisting of a removable floor and a cover with lateral sliding walls.

Provided that the shuttle production system is widely employed in European railways, not only in combined transportation but also in conventional transportation in form of regular unit trains, the VEL-Wagon team proposes to evaluate the economics of the shuttle with a particular case referred to VEL-Wagon. In so doing, the shuttle case will have several advantages:

A number of variables can be kept fixed, especially when it comes to operational parameters such as:

- Train length and wagon composition
- Circulations and mileage of wagons / trains
- Locomotive type and personnel employed
- Use of infrastructure, railway facilities, terminals etc.

The sensible parameters under study can be more easily isolated qualified and quantified, namely:

- Wagon investment breakeven
- Wagon maintenance costs
- Energy consumption

- Capacity efficiency
- Averaged axle load
- Payload efficiency
- Other

The shuttle production system is as well easier (than other productions systems) to simulate and to obtain useful results from, which may lead to a better validation and comparison with existing cases in the literature and in the praxis

The ultimate objective is to compare the economic terms of VEL-Wagon against the current best possible market solutions. These market solutions include a freight railway option and a pure-road option. In addition, according to the Swedish experience, the comparison will be done against the Swedish lorry with 25 m long and 60 ton payload.

8.1. FORMULATION AND PARAMETERS

The railway shuttles will be defined according to the most frequent operational parameters found in the praxis and in the literature. According to this, an important source of operational data is the report *"Costs and performance of European rail freight transportation"* published by NEA Transport research and training in 2008 –henceforth NEA-report-. NEA has given specific authorization to TUB for using its contents in VEL-Wagon project; this will help to focus on the specific wagon-dependent parameters rather than to focus on the definition and validation of the production systems themselves.

The train services that will be taken in account for the calculations are:

- 5 intermodal shuttles a week between Rotterdam and Busto Arsizio (25km north of Milan) with maritime containers or continental units or both of them.
- 5 unit trains a week with covered wagons (H-type) between Cologne and Lyon carrying palletized cargo.

8.2. BUSINESS CASE 1 ROTTERDAM-BUSTO ARSIZIO MARITIME INTERMODAL SHUTTLE

Background

Route:
 (NL) Rotterdam
 Zevenaar (Betuwe)
 (D) Emmerich
 Oberhausen
 Cologne
 Mainz
 Mannheim
 (CH) Basel
 Bern
 (Lötschbergbasistunnel)
 (IT) Domosdosola
 Gallarate
Busto Arsizio
 Distance (one way):
1.100,71 km

Route 1: Rotterdam-Busto Arsizio. Source: Googlemaps 2012 (approximation).

Train characteristics:

	Train length	Train g. weight	Train tare	Train payload	No. wagons	Wagons Sgns 60 ft	Wagons Sggmrrss 80 ft	No. axles	No. TEUS	TEUs / Container	Axle load
Train NEA report	520 m	1385 t	635 t	750 t	20	5	15	114	75	1,6	12,15 t

The incurred costs of a complete turnaround intermodal train (two-way) are depicted on the following table (NEA-Report):

Country	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
Netherlands	1.811,54	277,05	250,16	742,10	236,46	3.317,31
Germany	2.380,84	1.199,49	5.408,96	3.745,50	821,03	13.555,82
Switzerland	945,32	476,26	2.436,01	1.155,15	857,04	5.869,78
Italy	1.509,62	169,82	413,68	404,51	294,81	2.792,44
Overall	6.647,32	2.122,62	8.508,81	6.047,26	2.209,34	25.535,35
Overall incl. 30%						33.195,96

overhead						
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Red figures indicate costs items that will be modified by the use of VEL-Wagon, overhead is calculated as 30% of overall costs. Figures in Euros.

Costs categories of an intermodal shuttle train

FIGURE 148: COST CATEGORIES OF AN INTERMODAL SHUTTLE TRAIN BETWEEN ROTTERDAM AND BUSTO ARSIZIO. RED SECTORS INDICATE VEL-WAGON-AFFECTED ITEMS. SOURCE: [NEA].

Recalculation of the cost items affected by the utilization of VEL-Wagon

This section will analyze and re-calculate the costs chapters that may be affected by the use of VEL-Wagon.

8.2.1. WAGON COSTS

The wagon costs are taken directly from the NEA publication; VEL-Wagon costs have been estimated.

Wagon	Units	Depreciation per wagon and year	Interest per wagon and year	Insurance per wagon and year	Maintenance per wagon and year	Total per wagon and year	Total costs per year	Cost per turn (260 turns/ year)
Sgns 60ft	15	2.400	1.650	720	1.800	6.570	98.550	379,04
Sggmrss 80ft	45	3.680	2.530	1.104	2.760	10.074	453.330	1.743,58
60ft + 80ft (train)	60	3.360	2.310	1.008	2.520	9.198	551.880	2.122,62
VEL	57	3.040	2.090	912	2.300	7.882	449.274	1.828,82

FIGURE 149: ESTIMATION OF VEL-WAGON COSTS IN EUROS.

A first estimation of the VEL-Wagon costs has been done taking in account the amount of bogies it has, which is 2.

It can be assumed that the cost of a VEL-Wagon will be slightly superior to the cost of a regular 60 ft wagon (2 bogies) and clearly inferior to the cost of an articulated 80 ft wagon (3 bogies and an articulation). According to this, if VEL-Wagon assumes the averaged cost between a 60 ft wagon and an articulated 80 ft wagon this assumption will be on the pessimistic side.

Then:

$$\text{VEL-Wagon cost (pessimistic)} = \frac{(\text{Cost of a 60 ft wagon} + \text{Cost of an articulated 80 ft wagon})}{2}$$

The interest and insurance costs are calculated following the same principle as they depend majorly on the investment costs.

The maintenance costs are much related to the amount of bogies that a wagon has, for this reason it is assumed that the maintenance costs of VEL-Wagon will be higher than the costs of a 2-bogie wagon because although it has the same amount of axles, these axles have a higher axleload on average. In concrete the axles will be loaded a 25% more, which entails more wear and tear of the wheels and thus more maintenance costs.

To be conservative it has been assumed that the maintenance costs of a VEL-Wagon will be equal to the maintenance costs of an 80 ft wagon divided by 6 (amount of axles) multiplied by 4 (amount of axles VEL-Wagon) and multiplied by 1,25.

The necessary amount of VEL-Wagons for the service, 57, has been calculated as follows:

According to NEA report it is necessary to have 3 complete trains in order to complete the 260 turnaround circulations a year that result from a 5-time weekly shuttle service.

According to NEA a train unit is formed by:

Train= 1 x Locomotive + 5 x Sgns (60 ft) + 15 x Sggmrss (80 ft art). It has a length of 500 m (locomotive excluded).

Since a VEL-Wagon has an approximated length of 26 m, the necessary amount of VEL-Wagons for making a 500 m train is 19. Then so, 3 complete trains need 57 VEL-Wagons.

Summarizing, the total cost per circulation imputable to the wagons is 2.122,62 € in the reference case and 1.727,98 for the VEL-Wagon.

VEL-Wagon would represent a 13,84% save on wagon cost against the reference case.

A variation of the wagon costs for VEL-Wagon and a breakeven cost will be discussed in the sensitivity analysis chapter.

8.2.2. ENERGY COSTS

A calculation is presented here utilizing the values published in the NEA report.

The NEA report employs the following train parameters, blue figures are calculations done for VEL-Wagon:

	Train length	Train g. weight	Train tare	Train payload	No. wagons	No. axles	Axle load	Train energy consumption in kWh per km				
								Total (100%)	Rolling (33%)	Aero (32%)	Potential (27%)	Rest (8%)
NEA report	520 m	1385 t	635 t	750 t	20	114	12,15 t	26,00	8,58	8,32	7,02	2,08
VEL-Wagon	520 m	1253 t	503 t	750 t	19	80	15,66 t	22,52	7,19	6,90	6,35	2,08

A first appraisal of the energy consumption of a VEL-Wagon train was undertaken in a previous chapter of VEL-Wagon project (See D2.2, pages 83 to 101).

The energy consumption is subdivided in 5 categories:

- Rolling resistance: Due to the wheels rolling on the rails. (33% of total energy consumption)
- Aerodynamic resistance: Due to the air friction against the train body. (32% of total energy consumption)
- Potential energy: Due to a change on the potential energy on ramps and slopes. (27% of total energy consumption)
- Acceleration resistance: Due to the acceleration to increase speed. (6% of total energy consumption)
- Curve resistance: transverse, rotating and longitudinal movements due to runs on curves. (2% of total energy consumption)

FIGURE 150: ENERGY CONSUMPTION CATEGORIES OF A TYPICAL INTERMODAL TRAIN IN EUROPE. SOURCE: VERGLEICHENDE BERECHNUNGEN ZUM ENERGIEBEDARF VON ZWEI GÜTERZÜGEN DES KV IM RAHMEN DES FORSCHUNGSPROJEKTS VEL-WAGON, SIMON STOLZ, TU-BERLIN.

According to the results presented in fig. X, it is possible to break down the energy consumption item in 4 categories. By this it is possible to recalculate each category in respect to the VEL-Wagon characteristics.

The rolling resistance is directly proportional to the train weight and the amount of axles (or the axle load). In exhibit 51 of Deliverable 2.1 is portrayed a chart that establishes the relation between these parameters.

According to the calculated data, VEL-Wagon train will be lighter and have fewer axles than the reference train. The average axle load will be higher in a VEL-Wagon train and this will imply less rolling friction and therefore less energy consumption. In concrete, a diminishment of 16,3% is expected. See figure below:

FIGURE 151: CORRELATION OF TRAIN MASS AND ROLLING RESISTANCE. (HIGHER AXLE LOAD IS A CONSEQUENCE OF HAVING FEWER AXLES AND THEREFORE THE LOWER ENERGY CONSUMPTION, PARAMETRIZED FOR VEL WAGON) SOURCE: VEL-WAGON DELIVERABLE 2.1

The aerodynamic resistance, among many other things, depends on the gaps existing along the train. In this case the aerodynamic properties of the upper part of the train will be considered equal since the arrangement of the containers is very similar for both cases. However the part underneath the train is very different since the reference case has more bogies than the VEL-Wagon train and that increases the amount of gaps and thus the aerodynamic resistance.

The drag force resulting from the aerodynamic properties of the wagons has been as well chartered in Deliverable 2.1, exhibit 54. It displays the relation between container arrangement, wagon length and aerodynamic resistance.

The wagons of the reference train are 15 x Sgmrss (art. 80ft) and 5 x Sgns (60 ft). Each articulated 80 ft wagon can be assumed as 2 x 12 m long wagons, the Sgns wagon is an 19,8 m long wagon. Therefore the average length of a reference wagon is 13,11 m, calculated as:

$$\text{Ref. wagon length (aerodynamic)} = \frac{(19,8 \times 5 + 12 \times 15 \times 2)}{5 + 15 \times 2} = 13,11 \text{ m}$$

VEL-Wagon length is 26 m, thus, introducing these values in the depicted chart the resulting energy decrease is 17,07%.

The potential energy consumption is directly proportional to the train gross weight.

The reduction on potential energy consumption due to a reduced train mass can be obtained directly by a simple rule of three.

	Train mass	Potential energy consumption
Reference train	1385 t	7,02 kWh / km
VEL-Wagon train	1253 t	6,35 kWh / km

It is obtained a 9,53% reduction on the energy consumed by a VEL-Wagon train due to potential energy reasons.

The rest of the energy categories will be neglected for not having enough representation on the total energy sum, in any case they should favor the VEL-Wagon case due to reduced mass and amount of axles.

Hence, making the sum according to the obtained values:

Train energy consumption in kWh per km				
Rolling (33%)	Aero (32%)	Potential (27%)	Rest (8%)	Total (100%)

Reference train	8,58	8,32	7,02	2,08	26,00
VEL-Wagon train	7,19	6,90	6,35	2,08	22,52
Change	-16,20%	-17,07%	-9,53%	0% neglected	-13,38%

VEL-Wagon would represent a 13,38% save on energy cost against the reference case.

8.2.3. TRACK ACCESS COST

The track access charge depends, among many other things, of the train weight and train length. Depending of the track access system considered the importance of the weight is different.

Suitably, there is a tool called EICIS (European Infrastructure Charging Information System) of RailNetEurop based on the RNE Corridors context which is able to deliver approximate price information of track utilization for many European routes.

The EICIS software yields for the case of the rail service between Rotterdam and Busto (NEA report) a cost of 4254,4 € one way (2008 prices). Today in 2012 the same calculation with the same software online tool and same train parameters yields 4387,22 €. In order to do the comparison between the VEL-Wagon train and the train described on NEA report it is necessary to know the track access costs of VEL-Wagon train in 2008. This will be calculated by a rule of three using the data of 2012.

The VEL-Wagon train is about 10% lighter than the reference case, using the EICIS tool the track access charge is 4276,47 €, which is a -3% in respect to reference. This relation is used to calculate the 2008 value. See table below:

Track access charge Rotterdam-Busto (EICIS software RailNetEurope)	Reference	VEL-Wagon
Year 2008	4254,40 €	4.147,00 €
Year 2012	4387,22 €	4276,47 €

Naturally, VEL-wagon increases the averaged axle load and this has an effect on the infrastructure. This effect is being appraised in WP4 of VEL-Wagon.

For the moment and with the existing track access system it is possible to enunciate that:

VEL-Wagon would represent a 2,52% save on track access cost against the reference case.

8.2.4. OVERALL COSTS

The overall costs are summed up according to table X in order to produce the following table:

Turnaround costs	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
------------------	------------	-------	--------	--------	-----------	---------

Reference	6.647,32 €	2.122,62 €	8.508,81 €	6.047,26 €	2.209,34 €	25.535,35 €
VEL-Wagon	6.647,32 €	1.828,82 €	8.294,01 €	5.238,08 €	2.209,34 €	24.217,57 €
Change	0,00%	-13,84%	-2,52%	-13,38%	0,00%	-5,16%

According to the available information it is possible to enunciate that:

VEL-Wagon would represent a 5,16% save on total rail cost against the reference

Rail costs summary:

	Cost per turnaround (includes 30% overhead)	Cost per one way	Transported TEUs	Cost per TEU (one way)	Distance (km)	Cost per TEU/km
Reference	33.195,96 €	16.597,98 €	75	221,31 €	1.101,71	0,2009 €
VEL-Wagon	31.482,84 €	15.741,42 €	76	207,12 €	1.101,71	0,1880 €

Annual savings in rail transport:

Annual savings = (Cost turnaround reference - Cost turnaround VEL-Wagon) * 260 = 445.410,8€

In this business case,

The rail operator could save up to a half million Euros a year if using VEL-Wagon instead of using the typical rolling stock.

The savings per wagon are: 445.410,88 € / 57 = **7.814,23 € / wagon and year.**

8.3. BUSINESS CASE 2 CONVENTIONAL TRAFFIC, PART-LOAD TRAFFIC.

8.3.1. BACKGROUND

In the past the freight railways used to have an important amount of traffic dedicated to the part-load consignments, “Stückgutverkehr” in German.

FIGURE 152: PART-LOAD TRAFFIC ACTIVITY IN BERLIN AND COLOGNE IN THE 1930S. SOURCE [HTTP://WWW.EISENBAHNSTIFTUNG.DE](http://www.eisenbahnstiftung.de) AUTHOR: RVM (ITTENBACH).

FIGURE 153: CROSSDOCKING ROAD-RAIL STATION IN HOLZWICKEDE IN 1930. SOURCE [HTTP://WWW.EISENBAHNSTIFTUNG.DE](http://www.eisenbahnstiftung.de) AUTHOR: RVM (ITTENBACH).

FIGURE 154: PART-LOAD TRAFFIC IN WÜRZBURG HBF. (1978) SOURCE [HTTP://WWW.EISENBAHNSTIFTUNG.DE](http://www.eisenbahnstiftung.de) FOTO: A. WAGNER

With the gain on efficiency of the road transportation during the second half of the 20th century this kind of traffic was progressively shifted to the road, which was better suited for the modern logistics requirements. Hence, nowadays the part-load traffic does not form part of the typical market of European railways anymore.

FIGURE 155: CROSSDOCKING ROAD-ROAD STATION IN ASIA. SOURCE: [HTTP://WWW.MWPVL.COM/HTML/KNOWLEDGE.HTML](http://www.mwpvl.com/html/knowledge.html)

In the last years there has been a clear intention to revitalize the freight railways at all levels; an accent has been put into the combined transport (road-rail intermodal transport) which pursues the exchange of defined intermodal loading units between the modes. There are also actors focused on the so called multimodal transport, which strives for the concept of the part-load traffic. In this way, the Railport @ product of DB Schenker and some products of Rail Cargo Austria are aligned with this concept. Typically, the part-load traffic is one of the lightest and

more valuable traffics to be found in freight transportation, therefore the VEL-Wagon application may be considered very positive as regards as its very focus on light transportations.

8.3.2. DEFINITION

The present business case will analyze the costs of a rail connection between two multimodal centers (logistics centers), one placed in Cologne and the other one in Lyon. Again, the calculations performed in NEA report will be of important use when making the comparison against a VEL-Wagon solution and a pure road solution.

It has been supposed that the rail service is dedicated to the transportation of grouped goods. In this case the europallets are the employed transport unit to consolidate and carry the cargo in the cross-docking station and/or the logistics center.

The europallet averaged load has been calculated as a consequence of the values obtained for loaded semitrailers in Europe (See page 38 of VEL-wagon deliverable 2.1).

$$\text{Averaged weight of loaded pallet} = \text{Averaged net weight of loaded semitrailer} / \text{pallets per semitrailer}$$

$$0,61 \text{ t} = 20 / 33$$

The author is aware that this is a pessimistic estimation since the pallets are lighter on average than this, they may weight around 400-500 kg (confirmed after conversations with truckers and IRU statistics). However it is preferable to work with this conservative value, 610 kg per pallet, to take in account that there are cases in which heavier non-palletizable, cargo e.g. paper rolls, big bags, etc. have to be transported too.

Route in NEA report:

(DE) **Cologne**

Mainz

Manheim

Kehl (border)

(FR) Strasbourg

Mulhouse

Besançon

Lyon

Distance (one way):

869,00 km (381,4 km in DE; 487,6 in FR)

Alternative route via Koblenz, Perl, Metz, Dijon; distance 741,44 km. (Rne Corridor n°6)

Route 2: Cologne-Lyon. Source: Googlemaps 2012 (approximation).

Train characteristics

	No. wagons	Pallets / wagon	No. pallets in train	Total length	Total tare	load	Gross weight	No. axles	Axle load	Total volume	Pallets / tare	m ³ /tare
Habbins train	20	63	1260	484 m	615 t	764 t	1379 t	84	16,4 t	3348 m ³	2,0	5,4
H-VEL train	18	70	1260	486 m	553 t	764 t	1317 t	76	17,3 t	3528 m ³	2,3	6,4
Change %			0%	0%	-10%	0%	-4%	-10%	+6%	+2%	11%	17%
European articulated lorry (2+3 axles semitrailer)			33	16,5 m	14 t	20 t	34 t	5	7 t	<100 m ³	2,4	7

Wagon drawing

FIGURE 156: HABBINS WAGON. SOURCE SLOVENIAN RAILWAYS

Under these suppositions the following costs are obtained:

Country	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
Overall	3.538,46	1.684,62	6.085,78	5.232,77	1.406,19	17.947,82
Overall incl. 30% overhead						23.332,16 €

Table X: Cost categories and values in a freight train service between Cologne and Lyon, Source: NEA Report and own calculations. Red figures indicate costs items that will be modified by the use of VEL-Wagon, overhead is calculated as 30% of overall costs. Figures in Euros.

FIGURE 157: HABBIINS-14, SOURCE TRANSWAGGON.

The VEL-Wagon characteristics would be:

	Length over buffers	Loading length	Pivot distance	Tare	Volume	Payload	EUR-pallets	Gauge
H-type VEL-Wagon	25,94 m	24,70 m	18,00 m	26,5 t	196 m ³	63,5 t	70	G1
Habbins	23,26 m	22,02 m	17,72 m	26,5 t	167,4 m ³	63,5 t	63	G1
Habbiins-14	23,86 m	22,60 m	18,32 m	26 t	173 m ³	64 t	65	G1

FIGURE 158: H-VEL-WAGON

8.3.3. WAGON COSTS

The wagon costs are obtained from the NEA publication; VEL-Wagon costs have been estimated.

Wagon	Units	Depreciation per wagon and year	Interest per wagon and year	Insurance per wagon and year	Maintenance per wagon and year	Total per wagon and year	Total costs per year	Cost per turn (260 turns/ year)
Habbins	40	4.000	2.750	1.200	3.000	10.950	438.000	1.684,62
H-VEL	36	4.459	3.066	1.338	3.344	12.206	439.431	1.690,12

The necessary amount of VEL-Wagons for the service is 36, this has been calculated as follows:

According to NEA report it is necessary to have 2 complete trains in order to complete the 260 turnaround circulations a year (5 trains a week) between Cologne and Lyon with a travel time of 17h and 30 min. The train length is 484 m, which divided by the VEL wagon length 25,94 m gives 18 units in a VEL-Wagon train.

H-VEL costs have been very roughly estimated as follows.

Habbins costs / Habbins length = H-Wagon costs per m

H-VEL-Wagon costs = H-Wagon costs per m * VEL-Wagon length

The author is aware about the roughness of this approximation, which may be pessimistic provided that both wagons have the same amount of axles and mobile parts, however it is considered sufficient for this stage of calculation. Further discussion about the costs and variability thereof will be presented in the sensitivity chapter.

Hence, in principle there would be not a significant variation on the costs for wagon.

8.3.4. ENERGY COSTS

A calculation is presented here utilizing the values published in the NEA report.

NEA reports a consumption of 26 kWh per km and train. According to calculations carried out in the TUBerlin Fachgebiet Schienenfahrwege und Bahnbetrieb, the energy consumption can be divided in four categories which have the following percentages.

- Rolling resistance: Due to the wheels rolling on the rails. (33% of total energy consumption)
- Aerodynamic resistance: Due to the air friction against the train body. (32% of total energy consumption)
- Potential energy: Due to a change on the potential energy on ramps and slopes. (27% of total energy consumption)
- Other 8%
 - o Acceleration resistance: Due to the acceleration to increase speed. (6% of total energy consumption)
 - o Curve resistance: transverse, rotating and longitudinal movements due to runs on curves. (2% of total energy consumption)

Train energy consumption in kWh per km					
	Rolling -33%	Aero -32%	Potential 27%	Rest -8%	Total -100%
habbins	8,58	8,32	7,02	2,08	26

The rolling resistance is directly proportional to the train weight and the amount of axles (or the axle load). In exhibit 51 of Deliverable 2.1 is portrayed a chart that establishes the relation between these parameters.

According to the calculated data, VEL-Wagon train will be lighter and have fewer axles than the reference train. The average axle load will be higher in a VEL-Wagon train and this will imply less rolling friction and therefore less energy consumption. In concrete, a diminishment of 4,3 % is expected. See figure below:

FIGURE 159: CORRELATION OF TRAIN MASS AND ROLLING RESISTANCE. (HIGHER AXLE LOAD IS A CONSEQUENCE OF HAVING FEWER AXLES AND THEREFORE THE LOWER ENERGY CONSUMPTION, PARAMETRIZED FOR VEL WAGON) SOURCE: VEL-WAGON DELIVERABLE 2.1

The aerodynamic resistance, among many other things, depends on the gaps existing along the train. In this case the aerodynamic properties of the upper part of the train will be considered equal, although the VEL-Wagon train has two wagons less and thus it has two gaps less, they will be neglected as these gaps are very small, only 1,2 m. The part underneath the train is somewhat different since the habbins train case has 4 more bogies than the VEL-Wagon train, this increases the amount of gaps and thus the aerodynamic resistance.

The drag force resulting from the aerodynamic properties of the wagons has been as well chartered in Deliverable 2.1, exhibit 54. It displays the relation between container arrangement, wagon length and aerodynamic resistance.

The wagons of the reference train are 23,26 m long. VEL-Wagon length is 26 m, thus, introducing these values in the depicted chart the resulting energy decrease is 1,5 %.

The potential energy consumption is directly proportional to the train gross weight.

The reduction on potential energy consumption due to a reduced train mass can be obtained directly by a simple rule of three.

	Train mass	Potential energy consumption
Reference train	1379 t	7,02 kWh / km
VEL-Wagon train	1317 t	6,70 kWh / km

It is obtained a 9,53% reduction on the energy consumed by a VEL-Wagon train due to potential energy reasons.

The rest of the energy categories will be neglected for not having enough representation on the total energy sum, in any case they should favor the VEL-Wagon case due to reduced mass and amount of axles.

Hence, making the sum according to the obtained values:

	Train energy consumption in kWh per km				
	Rolling -33%	Aero -32%	Potential 27%	Rest -8%	Total -100%
habbins	8,58	8,32	7,02	2,08	26
H VEL	8,21	8,20	6,70	2,08	25,2
Change	-4,30%	-1,50%	-4,50%	0% neglected	-3,11%

VEL-Wagon would represent a 3,11 % save on energy cost against the reference case.

8.3.5. TRACK ACCESS COST

The cost variation in track access charge due to a decreased mass of the train (62 tones) will be neglected.

8.3.6. OVERALL COSTS

The overall costs are summed up according to table X in order to produce the following table:

Turnaround costs	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
Reference	3.538,46 €	1.684,62 €	6.085,78 €	5.232,77 €	1.406,19 €	17.947,82 €
VEL-Wagon	3.538,46 €	1.690,12 €	6.085,78 €	5.069,82 €	1.406,19 €	17.790,37 €
Change	0,00%	0,33%	0,00%	-3,11%	0,00%	-0,88%

According to the available information it is possible to enunciate that:

VEL-Wagon would represent a 0,88 % save on total rail cost against the reference

Rail costs summary:

	Cost per turnaround (includes 30% overhead)	Cost per one way	Transported pallets	Cost per pallet (one way)	Distance (km)	Cost per pallet/100km
Reference	23.332,16 €	11.666,08 €	1260	9,26 €	869,00	1,07 €
VEL-Wagon	23.127,48 €	11.563,74 €	1260	9,18 €	869,00	1,06 €

Annual savings in rail transport:

$$\text{Annual savings} = (\text{Cost turnaround reference} - \text{Cost turnaround VEL-Wagon}) * 260 = 53.216,9 \text{ €}$$

Hence in this business case,

The rail operator would not see a cost difference between using a Habbins or an H-VEL-Wagon.

The important conclusion is that this alternative use of VEL-Wagon would be perfectly competitive or even slightly better than the most advanced wagons on the market such as the Habbins.

8.4. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS AND EXTRAPOLATION

In this section some assumptions, parameters and concepts will be varied in order to know the effect on the business case results.

8.4.1. VEL-WAGON COSTS

In the first business case, the cost of VEL-Wagon is assumed to take the averaged value between the cost of a 60 ft container wagon and an 80 ft container wagon. This assumption is pessimistic since most probably the cost of a VEL-Wagon will be closer to the cost of a 60 ft wagon provided that it has the same amount of axles.

The relation between expected VEL-Wagon costs and percentage of wagon costs variation is plotted as follows.

However the wagon costs only represent 8% of the total rail costs. The variation of the VEL-Wagon costs and its influence in the total savings on rail costs is chartered as follows.

FIGURE 160: WAGON COSTS VERSUS SAVINGS IN BUSINESS CASE 1

The most relevant conclusion is that the parameter “cost of VEL-Wagon” does not have a significant influence on the total expected benefits of the business case. Hence, the significant gain of VEL-Wagon is in energy and capacity efficiency rather than the wagon construction costs.

The elasticity of the rail costs savings in respect to the cost of the wagon is -0,62, which is not a very sensitive dependency.

The same occurs with the business case n°2.

The recommendation is not to spare expenses on wagon construction or design.

8.4.2. DISTANCE OF TRANSPORTATION AND MODE CHOICE

The distance of transportation is a parameter that influences very much the costs of the rail service. It is one of the key arguments for the modal choice between pure rail (e.g. single wagon load), intermodal (combined transport), multimodal (eg. part-load traffic road-rail) and pure-road.

The intermodal costs refer to the total door-to-door costs using a container or an interchangeable intermodal loading unit. These costs are interesting from the point of view of the intermodal operator who competes against the all-road solution.

These are the principal cost items (simplification):

- Cost for transshipment: 25 € per crane movement, 2 crane movements per service.
- Cost for pre- and post-haulage: Cost per trip, 1 €/ km with a minimum fee of 50 € each.
- Container leasing: 50 € per service.

(Prices from RENFE http://www.contrenrenfe.com/condiciones_redmulticliente.html)

- Rail costs (already calculated in business case 1)
- Overheads (would not be taken in account neither for the intermodal solution nor for the all-road solution)

Therefore the total door to door costs for the different modalities are:

	(1) Rail cost per TEU (one way)	(2) Terminal costs (per container)	(3) Pre- and post-haulage (per container)	(4) Container leasing (per container)	(5) TEU per container	(6)=((2+3+4)/5) Non-rail costs (per TEU)	(1+6) One way service (per TEU)
Reference	218,39 €	50 €	100 €	50 €	1,65	121,21 €	339,61 €
VEL-Wagon	203,97 €	50 €	100 €	50 €	1,65	121,21 €	325,18 €
Lorry (EU)	The European lorry (articulated vehicle 2+3 axles-semitrailer) has a cost of 1,243€/ km and a capacity of 2,3 TEU. Source Observatorio del transporte de mercancías por carretera 2011, Spain. (Cost per TEU=1101,71 x 1,243 / 2,3)						595,40 €

The intermodal solution is in every case cheaper than the all-road solution, this is mainly because the distance of transportation is very long and thus the rail mode deploys its economic advantages fully. For shorter distances the rail mode would not be viable, the breakeven for this case would be around the 350 km, VEL-Wagon would contribute to diminish this breakeven distance. See figure:

FIGURE 161: MODAL CHOICE VS. DISTANCE

The multimodal costs are quite difficult to calculate on a door-to-door basis. This is because the multi-modal production systems may include as well some other logistics operations such as warehousing, sorting, distribution and packaging among many others. As regards as the difficulty of performing such bottom-up calculation that would include the warehouse and logistics costs calculation, the author is going to perform a bottom-up calculation of the total costs on a hypothetical service.

Let's suppose that between two big cities, say Cologne and Lyon, there is an important flow of goods.

A company in Lyon has to send a consignment to Cologne, for that, a standard articulated lorry (semitrailer) is employed.

The lorry has a capacity of 33 pallets, a volume of 90 m³ and a payload capacity of 25 t, this is more than enough for the service.

The average cost of an all-road service may be around 1,243€ / km (Source Spanish Ministerio de Fomento).

There are some toll costs to add to this figure, after observing the values of <http://www.toll-collect.de> and due to the variability on cases it is going to be assumed that these costs will be around 15% of the lorry costs. Hence the total cost of the all-road service will be 1,42 €/ km.

The distance is 730 km (Googlemaps), hence total costs will be: 1036,6 € per service.

Which gives ca. 31 € per pallet.

The revenue speed of the lorry for distances >600 km decreases because of the regulations concerning to rest times for the lorry driver. In this case the average revenue speed is 35 km / h (Source Intermodal Transport in Europe EIA).

The transport time is. $730 \times 35 = 20\text{h } 48\text{ min.}$ (Which is a Day A /Day C Schedule)

In order to increase this speed, two lorry drivers should be employed, which increases the all-road costs in about 40 % (own appraisal based in data of Ministerio de Fomento Spain).

According to the calculations performed in Business Case 2 the **rail costs** per pallet and 100 km are 1,07 €.

Which gives ca. 7,81€ per pallet. Hence:

The rail transport costs are 4 times less than the road costs.

Now, in order to be competitive, and that is the problem, the multimodal transport has to offer good transport quality, this is: good transport time, punctuality, safety, security and flexibility.

Let's suppose that a rail company offers a service of 5 trains a week between Cologne and Lyon. This makes 260 circulations a year, with 1260 pallets per train, which gives a total of 655.200 pallets to be moved back and forth.

The total rail costs are calculated as: Distance * 2 * circulations a year * pallets on a train * cost per pallet and km = $730 \times 2 \times 260 \times 1260 \times 0,0107 = \text{ca. } 5 \text{ Million euros a year in rail transport costs.}$

The equivalent road costs would be: Pallets to be moved / pallet capacity of a lorry * distance * cost lorry per km = $655.200 / 33 \times 730 \times 1,42 = 20,5 \text{ million euros a year in road transport costs.}$

Now the question is:

Is the difference $20,5 - 5 = 15$ million euros a year enough incentive for:

- Building and operating two multimodal stations? and
- Arranging and operating a distribution and pick-up system for the pallets with short distance lorries? and
- Doing the necessary marketing and client gathering for guaranteeing a good loading factor of the trains? and
- Being fast, punctual secure, safe, flexible and reliable? and
- Make a reasonable percentage of benefits from all these operations?

The answer to these questions is very difficult, it would require another business case appraisal, which is out of the scope of this project.

In this context other questions would arise when it comes to other logistics services that could be transferred to the multimodal stations, namely:

- Can the warehousing and warehousing management be outsourced efficiently at multimodal stations?
- What about the customer service?
- What about the distribution decisions in respect to demand or supply?
- What about partnerships developments possibilities and know-how transfer with local hauliers?
- Is the product development, added value, post-packaging, labeling, further cargo groupage something that can be outsourced and performed efficiently in multimodal stations too?
- What would be the costs prospects for all these outsourced operations if centralized in a multimodal station?

Finally the distance of transportation plays an important role here, then, the longer the distance of transport the higher the potential savings due to the rail use. These savings may be around 1 million euro per 50 km longer distance of transport in the studied business case (see figure).

FIGURE 162: RAIL COSTS VS.ROAD COSTS

Another point is the threshold of 600-700 km transport distance, which has to do with the quality of transport. This would be the distance at which a lorry driver should legally rest, making the deliverable schedule one night longer, the solution with two lorry drivers increases the road costs in a 40%. The rail mode should be able to compete in quality at distances longer than 700 km.

8.4.3. CONTINENTAL TRANSPORT.

The intermodal continental transport demands higher effort on wagon composition in order to match with the higher variability of loading unit cases. An important characteristic of this traffic is the presence of semitrailers. The unaccompanied semitrailer traffic has undergone a boom during the last decade and it is expected that it continues growing during the next years.

Here, longer uninterrupted loading surfaces lead to better loading factors. The simulation has been done with the following unit proportions: 40 % tanks and swap bodies < 7,82 m, 20 % silos and 30 ft bulk containers, 40 % Semitrailers and 45 ft boxes.

The TWIN wagon is a quite popular wagon employed in continental transport, it is able to transport 2 semitrailers and a wide combination of other loading units. The T5 could be understood as the 60 ft wagon for semitrailers. The simulation shows that T5 has better loading factor than the TWIN wagon as it can fit a good number of loading cases, however a shorter wagon of 50 ft would be even better, this is because the majority of units are 7,45 m long and two of them would fit perfectly in one wagon.

The observed trend is that the longer a wagon is, the smaller the variability of loading factor in respect to a length change and the better loading factor overall. In this way the VEL-wagon 75 ft long would offer the better arrangement and a 80 ft VEL-wagon would be an acceptable solution.

The wagons for semitrailers are more expensive than the container-only wagons, about 50% more according to Tatravagonka. The maintenance costs are slightly higher too.

The business case will be reformulated. These are the new train parameters:

Train characteristics:

	Train length	Train g. weight	Train tare	Train payload	No. wagons	Wagons Sgns 60 ft	TWIN wagons	No. axles	TEU Capacity	Axle load
REFERENCE	520 m	1385 t	605 t	780 t	17	5	12	96	80	14,43 t
VEL Wagon 80 ft for 1 semitrailer	512 m	1340 t	560 t	780 t	19	-	-	80	76	16,75 t

The incurred costs of a complete turnaround intermodal train (two-way) are depicted on the following table (NEA-Report):

	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
Reference	6.647,32 €	2.356,68 €	8.508,81 €	6.047,26 €	2.209,34 €	25.769,41 €
VEL-Wagon						33.195,96

Of which:

Wagon costs

Wagon	Units	Depreciation per wagon and year	Interest per wagon and year	Insurance per wagon and year	Maintenance per wagon and year	Total per wagon and year	Total costs per year	Cost per turn (260 turns/ year)
Sgns 60ft	15	2.400	1.650	720	1.800	6.570	98.550	379,04
TWINt	36	5.520	3.795	1.656	3.312	14.283	514.188	1.977,65
60ft + TWIN (train)	51	7.920	5.445	2.376	5.112	20.853	612.738	2.356,68
VEL	57	3.600	2.475	1.080	2.160	9.315	530.955	2.042,13

As said, the acquisition costs of a TWIN wagon have been estimated as 1,5 times the cost of an 80 ft articulated wagon and its maintenance costs in 1,2 times.

The cost of a VEL-Wagon able to carry semitrailers will increase too, the supposition is that the cost of a VEL-wagon able to carry semitrailers will be 1,5 times (1,2 on maintenance) the costs of a 60 ft wagon.

Under these suppositions, VEL-Wagon would represent a 13,3% save on wagon cost against the reference case.

Energy costs

	Train length	Train g. weight	Train tare	Train payload	No. wagons	No. axles	Axle load	Train energy consumption in kWh per km				
								Total (100%)	Rolling (33%)	Aero (32%)	Potential (27%)	Rest (8%)
NEA report	520 m	1385 t	605 t	780 t	17	96	14,43 t	26,00	8,58	8,32	7,02	2,08
VEL-Wagon	512 m	1340 t	560 t	780 t	19	80	16,75 t	24,25	7,88	7,49	6,81	2,08

A first appraisal of the energy consumption of a VEL-Wagon train was undertaken in a previous chapter of VEL-Wagon project (See D2.2, pages 83 to 101).

The rolling resistance is directly proportional to the train weight and the amount of axles (or the axle load). In exhibit 51 of Deliverable 2.1 is portrayed a chart that establishes the relation between these parameters.

According to the calculated data, VEL-Wagon train will be lighter and have fewer axles than the reference train. The average axle load will be higher in a VEL-Wagon train and this will imply less rolling friction and therefore less energy consumption. In concrete, a diminishment of 8,2% is expected. See figure below:

Correlation of Train Mass and Rolling Resistance. Source: VEL-Wagon Deliverable 2.1

The aerodynamic resistance, among many other things, depends on the gaps existing along the train and their length. The arrangement of the containers and the semitrailers along the train yields gaps, these gaps are different for any loading case, which varies along the time. We are going to suppose that the compared trains have the same aerodynamic resistance on the upper part, this is a pessimistic assumption for VEL-Wagon provided that a longer wagon entails better loading factor and thus better compression of the containers and fewer gaps.

The drag force resulting from the aerodynamic properties of the wagons has been as well chartered in Deliverable 2.1, exhibit 54. It displays the relation between container arrangement, wagon length and aerodynamic resistance.

The wagons of the reference train are 12 x TWIN (art. 106ft) and 5 x Sgns (60 ft). Each articulated 106 ft wagon can be assumed as 2 x 16 m long wagons, the Sgns wagon is an 19,8 m long wagon. Therefore the average length of a reference wagon is 16,6 m, calculated as:

$$\text{Ref. wagon length (aerodynamic)} = \frac{(19,8 \times 5 + 16 \times 12 \times 2)}{5 + 12 \times 2} = 16,6 \text{ m}$$

VEL-Wagon length is 26 m, thus, introducing these values in the depicted chart the resulting energy decrease is 10%.

The potential energy consumption is directly proportional to the train gross weight.

The reduction on potential energy consumption due to a reduced train mass can be obtained directly by a simple rule of three.

	Train mass	Potential energy consumption
Reference train	1385 t	7,02 kWh / km
VEL-Wagon train	1340 t	6,79 kWh / km

It is obtained a 3% reduction on the energy consumed by a VEL-Wagon train due to potential energy reasons.

The rest of the energy categories will be neglected for not having enough representation on the total energy sum, in any case they should favor the VEL-Wagon case due to reduced mass and amount of axles.

Hence, making the sum according to the obtained values:

Train energy consumption in kWh per km				
Rolling	Aero	Potential	Rest	Total

	(33%)	(32%)	(27%)	(8%)	(100%)
Reference train	8,58	8,32	7,02	2,08	26,00
VEL-Wagon train	7,88	7,49	6,81	2,08	24,25
Change	-8,20%	-10,00%	-3,00%	neglected	-6,72%

VEL-Wagon would represent a 6,72% save on energy cost against the reference case.

Track access cost

Change neglected.

Overall costs

The overall costs are summed up according to table X in order to produce the following table:

Turnaround costs	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
Reference	6.647,32 €	2.122,62 €	8.508,81 €	6.047,26 €	2.209,34 €	25.535,35 €
VEL-Wagon	6.647,32 €	2.042,13 €	8.508,81 €	5.641,13 €	2.209,34 €	25.301,28 €
Change	0,00%	-13,35%	0,00%	-6,72%	0,00%	-2,80%

According to the available information it is possible to enunciate that:

VEL-Wagon for semitrailers would represent a 2,80% save on total rail cost against the

Annual savings in rail transport:

Annual savings = (Cost turnaround reference - Cost turnaround VEL-Wagon) * 260 = 187.377,84 €

Hence, in this business case about continental transport:

The rail operator could save up to 200.000 Euros a year if using VEL-Wagon for semitrailers instead of using the typical rolling stock.

The variability of the VEL-wagon cost and its influence on the benefits would look as follows.

The conclusion is that a VEL-Wagon for semitrailers should have a cost lower than 1,5 times the cost of a standard 60 ft wagon in order to generate sufficient benefits for this business case.

8.4.4. AVERAGED MARKET (MARITIME AND CONTINENTAL TOGETHER)

The VEL-Wagon project intends to address the case that both maritime and continental traffics share the same intermodal trains. The basic objective by this is to diminish the risk of having wagons idle when the demand of a specific market shrinks.

Usually in European intermodal transportation the continental and maritime markets are differentiated and are served with different kind of trains. Nowadays the trend is that articulated 80 ft wagons are employed in maritime shuttles while articulated pocket wagons, e.g. TWIN, are employed in continental trains. 60 ft wagons are employed in both types of trains indistinctly.

In this case it happens again that the longer a wagon is (uninterrupted length) the better loading factor it has.

In this case, a VEL-Wagon with one pocket for a semitrailer would be a wagon that could be employed indistinctly both in continental and maritime traffic offering in both cases very good loading factors.

Obviously a VEL-Wagon for semitrailers would be more expensive than a wagon for containers-only, it is estimated that the pocket version could be 40% more expensive than the container-only version (Estimation based in observation of pocket wagons compared to equivalent container-only wagons.. This would entail a cost up to 100.000 euros a year of difference in wagon costs.

A VEL-Wagon for semitrailers would be also heavier than a wagon for containers-only. According to observations a wagon for semitrailers can weigh up to 10-30 % more than its version for containers only. This could lead to important losses on payload capacity.

The recommendation is to focus on the container-only segment.

8.4.5. MARKET FOR TALL CONTAINERS (E.G. MEGABOXES)

VEL-Wagon can have a design that allows transporting very tall boxes on a lower level between the bogies.

This ability may be interesting for traffics that require the transportation of tall boxes e.g. automobile parts, tires, machines in racks etc. or traffics that require the transportation of standard boxes in very narrow gauges, for instance in Great Britain.

A VEL-Wagon transporting a tall unit between the bogies can only be partially employed since the remaining free edges are not sufficiently long to accommodate any standard loading unit.

A wagon employed in Europe for such transports is the Sffggmrrss (MEGAFRET), this is the reference wagon.

This wagon has the following technical properties:

Technical details	
Length over buffers	36'440 mm
Loading length	2 x 16'105 mm
Floor height above top of rail, unloaded	825 mm
Cargo weight (at 120 km/h)	89 t
Tare weight	39 t
Maximum axle load	16 t
Wheel diameter	730 mm
Maximum Speed	120 km/h
Minimum curve-radius	150 m*
Ferry boat capability	1' 30'

VEL-Wagon has a loading length of ca. 15 m between the bogies, which has place for two swap-bodies. The swap bodies can be only top-lifted since it is physically impossible to introduce the grapple arms for bottom-lift inside the pocket of VEL-Wagon

For a given length of train the Megafret is able to accommodate about 50% more units and TEUs than a VEL-Wagon, this is because the loading factor is much more better in the Megafret, which is a wagon specifically designed for such transportations.

Apparently VEL-wagon would not bring about any especial advantage but rather a general decrease on efficiency.

The calculation using the same methodology yields a negative result for VEL-Wagon, in concrete the values are:

Country	Locomotive	Wagon	Track access	Energy	Personnel	Overall	TEUs	€/ TEU
Megafret	6.647,32 €	1.804,22 €	8.508,81 €	6.047,26 €	2.209,34 €	25.216,95 €	73,97	340,89 €
VEL 2nd Level	6.647,32 €	1.828,82 €	8.508,81 €	5.731,23 €	2.209,34 €	24.925,52 €	46,75	533,14 €

The conclusion is that the pocket of VEL-Wagon is not an interesting option, in comparison with existing rolling stock, for the transportation of tall units. Furthermore the necessary structural design to allow this transportation leads to higher tare and higher cost of VEL-Wagon which has a negative effect on its application for regular transports.

The recommendation is to discard the option of a central pocket for tall containers in order to focus on a simplified and lighter VEL-Wagon design.

8.4.6. WAGON TARE, PAYLOAD AND AXLE LOAD.

One of the most sensible questions to criticize VEL-Wagon is the apparent inability to carry heavy loads.

In principle the target weight of a VEL-Wagon for containers-only would be 21 t, this yields a payload of 69 t over 4 TEUs space. Which makes 17,25 t payload capacity per TEU.

Provided that:

The average weight of a **loaded** TEU in Europe is **12,8 t**,

Then the VEL-Wagon has more than enough payload capacity for the majority of loading cases.

EXHIBIT. X WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION IN EUROPEAN CONTAINER TRAFFIC (IN NO. CONTAINERS AND GROSS WEIGHTS, ONLY LOADED CONTAINERS). SOURCE DATA: 2011 EUROGATE AND EUROMAX TERMINALS, ANTWERP PORT STATISTICS AND EUROSTAT.

In addition, if considering empty containers (16 % of total containers) the average TEU weight decreases to 11 tones, which makes VEL-Wagon even more suitable.

The next graph represents the efficiency lost in a market by a wagon type in respect to its offered averaged payload per TEU. It has been obtained with data from the Deliverable 2.1.

Market efficiency loss of a wagon in respect to its averaged payload per TEU

It is possible to see that the 80 ft articulated wagon is able to address almost any kind of traffic (95% of the cases), especially the very heavy one, however when it comes to 45 ft units this wagon is useless. 45 ft units represent about 5% of maritime traffic, a market that is lost for an articulated 80 ft.

Hence the articulated 80 ft is able to address the market efficiently in terms of loading surface utilization, however it is rather inefficient in terms of deadweight utilization since it is a very heavy wagon for the majority of transportation cases.

A 60 ft wagon is also able to address an important number of traffics, however it results inefficient when there is a majority of 40 ft containers.

An 80 ft VEL-Wagon cannot address very heavy containers efficiently, this market is estimated in a 15%. However it is very efficient (in terms of length and weight) for the remaining 85%.

A 40 ft two axle wagon has an important market efficiency loss of 25%.

It is important to notice that the market efficiency loss begins to be very important from 18 tones downwards, this means that a decrease of 1 tone in payload capacity per TEU entails an important market efficiency loss of about 10%.

The next graph displays the relation between the tare of VEL-Wagon and its market ability. It is assumed a maximum axle load of 22,5 t which gives a total wagon gross weight of 90 t.

In this case each tone extra of wagon tare entails about 1,3 % of market efficiency loss. Considering the target weight of 21 t for a VEL-Wagon it is expected an efficient market covering of 85 % of the cases.

In conclusion VEL wagon is able to address 85% of the market very efficiently both in terms of deadweight and surface, the remaining 15% can be still addressed but it entails a loss of loading factor. A VEL-Wagon for semitrailers (with a pocket) will be heavier than a VEL-Wagon for container only and this will decrease the payload entailing an efficiency loss of 5%.

The efficiency loss in the heavy cases can be corrected with empty container transport.

An 80 ft articulated will address very efficiently almost all kind of traffics but it will be over-dimensioned in terms of deadweight when doing it, especially when transporting light

containers, which are majority. This entails important energy consumption and waste of resources.

8.5. CONCLUSIONS OF THE BUSINESS CASE

From a business perspective VEL-Wagon is a very interesting and profitable wagon for intermodal transports, especially when it comes to the maritime market. In this context it would be able to generate a yearly saving potential of 500.000 € in a shuttle relation between Rotterdam and Milan. The business case of continental transport shows a positive yield as well. The application for volumetric loads, pallets and the like is as well very interesting since the VEL-Wagon with a detachable superstructure can perform at the same or even slightly better level than the typical wagons for this kind of cargo such as the habbins.

In the sensitivity chapter it has been observed that the wagon cost of production has much less influence in the total business than the properties of it such as the tare and length capacity. For this reason it is recommended to focus very much on achieving a good design and reliability even if the price becomes slightly higher.

The tare of the wagon has a high influence on the market that the wagon can address, every extra tone of tare may entail about 1,3% of market loss.

Finally, the uninterrupted loading length of the wagon has an enormous impact on the loading factor of it being longer loading lengths better for the loading factor. From a pragmatic view VEL-Wagon should have 80 ft of loading length, however it is expected a growth of the lengths of the containers e.g 45 ft units and this may make necessary to extend the length of VEL-Wagon to 90 ft or even more.

9. CONCEPTS FOR THE FUTURE

9.1. COMPACT 2-SEMITRAILER VEL-WAGON (91 FT)

The following concept was rejected in the project VEL-Wagon due to the enormous technical and regulative challenges that it posed. However it is considered by the author as the future wagon for the transportation of semitrailers, provided that this kind of unit will increase its presence on European intermodal transports.

Compact 2-semitrailer wagon concept.

VEL-Wagon concept TC-3, Source:Tatravagonka.

Characteristics:

Length over buffers: 29,2 m

Loading length: 27,940 m (91 ft)

Pivot distance: 21 m

Tare: 25,6 t

Payload:

By 22,5 t/axle= 64,4 t (32,2 t per semitrailer)

By 25 t/axle= 74,4 t (37,2 t per semitrailer)

The author anticipates an important cost advantage of this concept against the reference wagon, the TWIN wagon for two semitrailers over 6 axles. The economic advance should be similar to the one existing between the 80 ft VEL-Wagon against the 80 ft articulated wagon.

However, the 91 ft concept requires an important technical development in order to deal with the important forces occurring in the central parts of the wagon as well as the static and dynamic stability properties. It also defies the current regulations on wagon design and construction, which are imposed by the restriction of the infrastructure (small gauges) reason for which its real development and implementation may take a huge technical and administrative work.

This concept will be very interesting if in the future the 45 ft container unit makes a breakthrough. This tendency is not observed in maritime traffic for the moment, except by the cases of Short Sea Shipping. However in European continental transportation it is observed more and more presence of 45 ft units. This, added up to the proliferation of semitrailers' intermodal transports will make the necessity of longer wagons even more necessary in a short term.

9.2. LIGHTER ARTICULATED VEL-WAGON.

The following wagon concept is proposed for a further study.

- Total loading length $2 \times 24 = 48$ m
- Length over buffers: Loading length + 2 buffers (0,6m)+ interspace articulation (1,20 m)= 50,4 m
- Pallet capacity: $2 \times 68 = 136$ pallets
- TEU capacity: $2 * 80 \text{ ft} = 8$ TEU
- Total weight = Weight of two VEL-Wagons – weight of 1 bogie – weight of 4 buffers = $22 + 22 - 4,8 - 2 = 37,2$ t.
- If adding a cover it is possible to have an H wagon, weight of the cover ~ 11 t
- Total payload (only platform)

- By 22,5t/axle $22,5 * 6 - 37,2 = 97,8$ t (12 t/TEU)
- By 25 t/axle $25*6 - 37,2 = 112,8$ t (14,1 t/TEU)
- In the case of an H-Wagon (with cover) the payload per pallet would be
 - By 22,5t/axle, 638 kg/ pallet
 - By 25 t/axle, 748 kg/ pallet
- Volume of H-VEL-Wagon~ 400 m³

The next table compares a standard road vehicle with the articulated VEL-Wagon for pallets, and other vehicles such as the Giga liner and a wagon habbins:

vehicle	tare	payload	volume	pallets	payload/ pallets	volume/ pallets	payload/ tare	pallets /tare	tare/ volume	payload/ volume
Standard Lorry	14	26	100	33	788	3,0	1,86	2,36	140	260
giga 60 t (SE)	22	38	150	51	745	2,9	1,73	2,32	147	253
bigmaxx	16,5	27,5	110	37	743	3,0	1,67	2,24	150	250
giga 44 t (EU)	18	26	150	51	510	2,9	1,44	2,83	120	173
Habbins	26,5	63,5	167	63	1008	2,7	2,40	2,38	158	379
H-VEL articulated	48,2	97,8	400	136	638	2,9	2,02	2,82	120	244

Source: Study on the Effects of the Introduction of LHVs on Combined Road-Rail Transport and Single Wagonload Rail Freight Traffic (K+P, 2011) and Deliverable 2.1 VEL-Wagon.

An important figure to observe is the maximal payload per pallet, which in the case of the standard lorry is 788 t per pallet. This amount is more than enough to handle the normal traffic situations since it is assumed that the average weight of the pallet in road transportation is 400 kg (Source K+P). In concrete the following values are declared:

- 400 kg the pallet space for general cargo
- 270 kg the pallet space for textiles
- 730 kg the pallet space for paper, e.g. paper roll

This may be one of the reasons for which the road industry is lobbying for longer lorries with same payload capacity, as the volume and loading length seems to be more important than the payload.

In this way an articulated VEL-Wagon is addressing such light and volumetric requirements, whereas a habbins wagon is offering more than the double of necessary payload per pallet, this may be not competitive in a modern logistics concept.

A comparison against a habbins train would yield the following parameters:

	No. wagons	Pallets / wagon	No. Pallets in train	Train length	Train tare	Train payload	Train g. weight	No. axles	Axle load	train volume m3
Habbins train	20	63	1260	484 m	615 t	764 t	1379 t	80	17,2 t	3348
Art H-VEL train	9	136	1224	483 m	433 t	742 t	1175 t	54	21,7 t	3600

An approximation of the costs of an articulated H-Wagon has been done as follows:

Cost of articulated H-VEL wagon = 1,6 x cost of a habbins.

The cost of maintenance has been calculated as:

Maintenance of articulated VEL-Wagon= (2 x maintenance of Habbins – maintenance of a bogie) * 1,23 (due to increase of axleload)

Thus, the wagon costs result in (figures in Euros):

Wagon	Units	Depreciation per wagon and year	Interest per wagon and year	Insurance per wagon and year	Maintenance per wagon and year	Total per wagon and year	Total costs per year	Cost per turn (260 turns/ year)
Habbins	40	4.000	2.750	1.200	3.000	10.950	438.000	1.684,62
VEL	20	6.400	4.400	1.920	6.248	18.968	379.368	1.459,11

The wagon costs could be 13,4% cheaper.

A calculation of the business case for an articulated H-VEL-Wagon yields the following results:

Rolling resistance will decrease in about a 12% due to fewer axles and lighter mass.

Aerodynamic resistance will decrease in about 4% due to fewer bogies

Potential energy will be reduced in a 14% due to a lighter train.

The total costs would look as follows:

	Locomotive	Wagon	Access	Energy	Personnel	Overall
Habbins	3.538,46 €	1.684,62 €	6.085,78 €	5.232,77 €	1.406,19 €	17.947,82 €
VEL	3.538,46 €	1.459,11 €	6.085,78 €	4709,5€	1.406,19 €	16.569,04 €
difference	0 %	-13,39%	0%	-10%	0%	-4,17%%

This means a potential saving of about 200.000 euros per year in respect to the habbins solution.

The conclusion is that this new design could save an important amount of energy and be more sustainable and competitive against road transportation.

The same concept can be employed for intermodal transportation with a capacity for 8 TEU, 4 x 40 ft containers.

In this case the savings in respect to a reference case could be of 10 to 15 % which could mean savings of about 1.000.000 € a year or more in a fixed shuttle relation as the one utilized in the business case described more above.

In this case axle loads of 25 t should be necessary.

An extension to this concept would be an articulated wagon formed by 10 or 5 wagon sections of 80 ft each.

For this concept, high axle loads of more than 30 t should be necessary.

This concept would be equivalent to the ten-pack or five-pack double stack wagons that are found in North America, Australia, China and India.

The whole concept of extending the length of the wagons is equivalent to a capacity increase on the horizontal dimension, provided that in Europe the growth on the vertical dimension (double stack) looks very difficult from the point of view of the infrastructure.

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10. CONCLUSIONS

The most important conclusion of this Doctoral Thesis is that there is sufficient evidence to confirm the initial enunciate:

The freight trains have to become lighter* in order to lower the logistics costs and compete better against the road transport.

* Lighter per transported m³, which make the trains more oriented to volumetric goods rather than to heavy goods.

As well as to confirm the working hypothesis:

To achieve a better utilization of the track capacity, the trains and the wagons, the loading length of these must be longer and at the same time with less or same number of axles.

Which paves the way for enunciating the following challenge:

The extension of the maximum axle load in European tracks, from 22,5 to 25 t and beyond, is a desired action that will benefit the light rail transports and will help to increase the competitiveness of freight railways against the road, leading to a more sustainable transport system.

The important middle arguments and conclusions that sustain these affirmations are summarized as follows:

Background trends:

- ☞ The amount of t-km performed by European railways has slightly decreased or stagnated during the last two decades.
- ☞ During that time railways have lost much market share against the road; the economic crisis has just worsened this trend.
- ☞ Railways lack principally of quality, single wagon load evolution is a good example of this.
- ☞ The wagon fleet has diminished more sharply than the t-km performance, which indicates that railways are employing the wagons more efficiently, this is, the wagons are doing more loaded km than before.
- ☞ Intermodal wagons and company-dedicated wagons are doing larger mileages per year and show better loading factors than other wagons. They could be considered “light wagons”.
- ☞ Big challenge of railways is to gain in quality and achieve the excellence on transportation.

Demand analysis:

- ☞ Light goods are the immense majority of transported goods (c.a. 75%).
- ☞ The transport of light goods grows faster than other heavy goods’ transports.
- ☞ Longer and higher containers as 40 ft HC or 45 ft units are preferred over shorter units as the 20 ft or short swap bodies.
- ☞ Light goods travel longer distances than heavy goods.

- ☞ Light goods demand higher quality of transportation, which is satisfied by road transportation.
- ☞ To increase rail share in the modal split there has to be a focus on light goods in the forthcoming years.

Supply analysis:

- ☞ The conventional railways have lost market share in total railways, especially when considering the Single Wagon Load branch, this is mostly due to a fall in quality. The economic crisis has accentuated this trend.
- ☞ European railways performed about 400 Mrd. t-km in 2010 of which: ~45% were trainloads TL, ~25% single wagonloads SWL and ~25% intermodal loads.
- ☞ Intermodal trains are the lightest trains with ~350 net tons per train, then SWL trains with 510t and finally TL trains with 670t.
- ☞ The combined transport has increased its share on railways and has resisted better the crisis.
- ☞ Intermodal trains are growing rapidly in terms of amount of trains and distance of transportation (~600km). Train averaged length is 650m (Germany).
- ☞ Intermodal wagons represent about 15% of the total fleet and they perform about 25% of the total t-km, are by large the most efficiently-employed wagons.
- ☞ The combined transport has increased very much its share on international transports, interoperability and administrative works are helping.
- ☞ Freight railways and intermodal transports become more competitive by longer distances, which are possible due to border free operations.
- ☞ An investment in wagons that would improve the overall efficiency of the system, in terms of availability, energy consumption, capacity utilisation, etc. would have an important effect with little proportional cost.
- ☞ Axle load extension is very interesting for light goods if lighter wagons with fewer wheels are employed. This may be even more interesting than train length extension.
- ☞ In the last times there are more and more examples of conventional rail freights that are being containerized and/or standardized in detachable units.
- ☞ H-wagons are the conventional wagons closest to be “road competitors” since they can address similar markets as the road does.
- ☞ Both wagon types and especially intermodal wagons are able to address different markets in a multipurpose way.

Intermodal market analysis:

- ☞ There is a manifest increase of utilization of longer units (longer than 8:30m, mostly 40 ft HC and 45 ft containers)
- ☞ There is a decrease of the averaged gross weight of consignment
- ☞ The averaged weights of the containers could stagnate around 13 tones per loaded TEU in 2020

- ☞ Goods transported in containers can be classified in 4 groups: light goods (~6 t/TEU, 43%), medium light goods 14 t/TEU (~14 t/TEU, 30%), heavy goods (~23 t/TEU, 19%) and very heavy goods (~30 t/TEU, 8%).
- ☞ The optimal wagon length for such combination of units is 80 ft. Hence, a popular wagon nowadays is the 6-axled 80 ft wagon; however this wagon may be over-dimensioned in terms of deadweight and axles for many transport cases.
- ☞ Continental transport is participated mainly from semitrailers, swap bodies and tank, bulk and silo containers.
- ☞ The semitrailer segment has experienced an important growth during these last years. The average gross weight of a loaded semitrailer is 27 t. Apparently, this weight is decreasing as semitrailers carry more and more volumetric goods.
- ☞ A craneable semitrailer is nowadays equivalent in price, life cycle costs and payload capacity to a non-craneable one. As road fleet is replaced quite frequently it can be assumed that in a future, and if necessary, an important part of the semitrailer fleet could be craneable without major investment.
- ☞ 45 ft unit is quite common and is growing in share in continental transports
- ☞ .The light goods in continental transportation tend to travel longer distances than the heavy goods. Hence, it is expected to see a decrease of the average TEU weight for continental intermodal trains.

Long wagons and VEL-Wagon:

- ☞ 80-ft container wagons without articulation are entering in operation in Europe. (21t empty weight, 14t/TEU payload) They are employed for hinterland transport of containers.
- ☞ 80-ft articulated wagons offer a very high payload (28t/TEU). They are dimensioned for the transport of heavy short units, which do not represent the majority of cases.
- ☞ In that way, intermodal trains are not designed for such extreme cases. Shorter trains or more locomotives would be necessary in these situations.
- ☞ In the U.S. the mainstay is the double stack car in its articulated version. Its payload is around 10t/TEU. It replaced the 93-ft flat car employed massively until the 80's.
- ☞ The performance of a VEL-Wagon with 80 ft has been simulated, under these traffic conditions it is obtained a ~10% increase of capacity against a reference case.
- ☞ The optimal traffic for VEL-Wagon is the one with great assorted types of units, like the main stream shuttle trains running between important terminals. In this case the extra length of VEL-Wagon offers greater loading case possibilities.
- ☞ Summarizing, a container-only 80 ft wagon would:
 - Increase the loading factor (amount of TEUs per train) in 10%
 - Decrease the amount of axles in 15%
 - Decrease the gross train weight in 7%
 - Improve aerodynamics (fewer gaps)
 - Decrease noise emissions (fewer axles)
 - Decrease maintenance (fewer axles)

Effect on infrastructure and network:

- ☞ Longer wagons such as VEL-Wagon 80 ft need a longer distance between pivots, which increases the overthrow of some parts of the wagon when running sharp curves. This implies a loss of loading gauge,
- ☞ The 25 t per axle and more is considered an interesting option for longer wagons with fewer axles, e.g. 90 ft VEL-Wagon, 93 ft VEL-Wagon. This is important to achieve longer loading surfaces, which increase the loading factor of the trains and therefore the utilisation of the railway network.
- ☞ It is possible to increase the capacity of a railway infrastructure by using better rolling stock, in this case by using longer wagons with more capacity and better loading factor.
- ☞ The noise is reduced when the amount of axles decrease, furthermore there are indications to sustain that increased axle loads decrease the noise.
- ☞ Investigations are needed on the following subjects:
 - Study of the axle load extension to 25 t and more,
 - Study of the rail-wheel interaction (Rail Contact Fatigue) with smaller wheel diameters such as 840 mm together with high axle loads (22,5 t) and higher speeds, up to 140 km/h.
 - Study of the available loading gauges and their interaction with increased distance between pivots “a” of the wagons, in order to achieve longer wagons with longer uninterrupted surfaces compatible with the existing infrastructures.
 - Study the investments necessary for the extension of the freight capacity and compare it with an alternative based on the gauge extension and axle load increase.

Business case analysis:

- ☞ From a business perspective VEL-Wagon is a very interesting and profitable wagon for intermodal transports, especially when it comes to the maritime market. In this context it would be able to generate a yearly saving potential of 500.000 € in a shuttle relation between Rotterdam and Milan.
- ☞ The business case of continental transport shows a positive yield as well. The application for volumetric loads, pallets and the like is as well very interesting since the VEL-Wagon with a detachable superstructure can perform at the same or even slightly better level than the typical wagons for this kind of cargo such as the habbins.
- ☞ In the sensitivity chapter it has been observed that the wagon cost of production has much less influence in the total business than the properties of it such as the tare and length capacity. For this reason it is recommended to focus very much on achieving a good design and reliability even if the price becomes slightly higher.
- ☞ The tare of the wagon has a high influence on the market that the wagon can address, every extra tone of tare may entail about 1,3% of market loss.
- ☞ Finally, the uninterrupted loading length of the wagon has an enormous impact on the loading factor of it being longer loading lengths better for the loading factor. From a pragmatic view VEL-Wagon should have 80 ft of loading length, however it is expected a growth of the lengths of the containers e.g 45 ft units and this may make necessary to extend the length of VEL-Wagon to 90 ft or even more.

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